

**MAINSTREAMING THE AFRICAN
CHARTER ON
DEMOCRACY,
ELECTIONS AND
GOVERNANCE
PROGRAM IN
SCHOOL
CONTEXT
IN AFRICA
[ACDEG]**

MAINSTREAMING THE AFRICAN CHARTER ON DEMOCRACY, ELECTIONS AND GOVERNANCE [ACDEG] PROGRAM IN SCHOOL CONTEXT IN AFRICA

This document reflects the first of three parts.

Part 1 examines the implementation of ACDEG in schools.

Note: **Part 2** [based on UNESCO recommendation and empirical studies] which examines ACDEG implementation outside of the school context - parent and community education; and **Part 3** which examines joint implementation of the in-school and out-of-school context, are developed and available.

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ACRONYMS

ADHD: Attention deficit hyperactive disorder

AFTHD: Africa Human Development Department World Bank

ANC: African National Congress

APC: All Progressives Congress

APR: Alliance for the Republic

AU: African Union

AGFUND: Arab Gulf Program for Development

BSBH Better Seed Best Harvest

BYOD: Bring your own device

CAR Central African Republic

4Cs: Collaboration, Communication, Creative and Critical thinking

CDVTA: Community Development Volunteers for Technical Assistance

CECAFE: Centre for Community Advancement and Family Empowerment

CENESA Civic Education Network for Eastern and Southern Africa

COSN: Consortium for School Networking

CPDM: Cameroon People's Democratic Movement

CVF: Computing Value Framework

DGC Democracy and Good Citizenship

DDP: Democracy Development Program

DGC: Democracy and Good Citizenship

DRC Democratic Republic of Congo

EACSO: East African Civil Society Organizations' Forum

ECD Early Childhood Development

ECES: European Centre for Electoral Support

EISA: Electoral Institute for Sustainable Democracy in Africa

ENP: European Neighborhood Policy

ENS: Ecole Normale Supérieure

EU: European Union

FADS: Foreign Aid Dependency Syndrome

FDI: Foreign Direct Investment

FDA: Foundation for Democracy in Africa

FPU: Free Patriotic Union

GDP: Gross Domestic Product

GPE: Global Partnership for Education

HDI: Human Development Index

HOD: Higher Order Discussion

ICT: Information and Communication Technology

IFES: International Foundation for Electoral Systems

ACRONYMS

IOs:	International Organizations
NDI:	National Democratic Institute
NGOs:	Non-Governmental Organizations
NED:	National Endowment for Democracy
NACE	Networking Arab Civic Education
NCCI	National Commission for Civic Education
NID	Namibia Institute of Democracy
OCAI-C:	Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument for Classrooms
PBL:	Project-Based Learning
QQ	Question Quadrant
RESEAC:	Electoral Knowledge Network of the Central African States
RPPs:	Research Practice Partnerships
SADR:	Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic
SDGs:	Sustainable Development Goals
TSDA:	Tesfa Social and Development Association
TVET:	Technical and Vocational Education and Training
UN:	United Nations
UNHCR:	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
ZPD:	Zone of proximal development

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The social-economic and political challenges in Africa at the beginning of the 21st century are urgent and unprecedented. The challenges include wide spread corruption, violent conflicts, political fragmentation, gross human rights abuses, poor health system, poor accountability to public services, gender inequality, food insecurity, foreign aid dependency syndrome, reduction in foreign direct investment (FDI) that correlates with poor human capital, and climate change dilemma (economic development in the face of environmental sustainability). A rich and growing literature has identified a “developed human capital” as the key fulcrum to resolve these challenges. Faced with persistent gaps of what is actually learned in schools in terms of civic education, and the continuous vicious cycle of social malice that has plague the continent, changes in civic curricula and pedagogy were deemed inevitable. This recommendation is supported by the Africa Human Development Department (AFTHD) World Bank in 2015. But more important, it should change the mental models of schooling and governance that dominate African education policy and practice.

In an endeavor to “create” a new African citizen who will be an effective change agent for the continent’s sustainable development as envisioned by the World Bank, United Nations (UN), European Union (EU) and African Union (AU), a team of thirty education experts met in Abuja, Nigeria, in 2015 to forge a new context and content for civic education that should deal with current pressing challenges and address future needs, at the same time accelerating social, economic and political growth. The identified context and content is in line with the objectives of the AU’s Charter on Democracy, Elections, and Governance (ACDEG), which includes:

1. Promote adherence, by each State Party, to the universal values and principles of democracy and respect for human rights;
2. Promote and enhance adherence to the principle of the rule premised upon the respect for, and the supremacy of, the Constitution and constitutional order in the political arrangements of the State Parties;
3. Promote the holding of regular free and fair elections to institutionalize legitimate authority of representative government as well as democratic change of government;
4. Prohibit, reject and condemn unconstitutional change of government in any Member State as a serious threat to stability, peace, security, and development;
5. Promote and protect the independence of the judiciary;
6. Nurture, support, and consolidate good governance by promoting democratic culture and practice, building and strengthening governance institutions and inculcating political pluralism and tolerance;

7. Encourage effective coordination and harmonization of governance policies amongst State Parties with the aim of promoting regional and continental integration;
8. Promote State Parties' sustainable development and human security;
9. Promote the fight against corruption in conformity with the provisions of the AU Convention on Preventing and Combating Corruption adopted in Maputo, Mozambique in July 2003;
10. Promote the establishment of the necessary conditions to foster citizen participation, transparency, access to information, freedom of the press, and accountability in the management of public affairs;
11. Promote gender balance and equality in the governance and development processes;
12. Enhance cooperation between the Union, Regional Economic Communities and the International Community on democracy, elections and governance; and
13. Promote best practices in the management of elections for purposes of political stability and good governance (Article 2 of ACDEG).

The aim and objectives of the new context and content are supported by the following strategic objectives of the Continental Education Strategy for Africa 2016-2025 (CESA 16-25):

1. Revitalize the teaching profession to ensure quality and relevance at all levels of education
2. Build, rehabilitate, preserve education infrastructure and develop policies that ensure a permanent, healthy and conducive learning environment in all sub-sectors and for all, so as to expand access to quality education
3. Harness the capacity of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) to improve access, quality and management of education and training systems
4. Ensure acquisition of requisite knowledge and skills as well as improved completion rates at all levels and groups through harmonization processes across all levels for national and regional integration
5. Accelerate processes leading to gender parity and equity

6. Launch comprehensive and effective literacy programmes across the continent to eradicate the scourge of illiteracy
7. Strengthen the science and mathematics curricula in youth training and disseminate scientific knowledge and culture in society
8. Expand Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) opportunities at both secondary and tertiary levels and strengthen linkages between the world of work and education and training systems
9. Revitalize and expand tertiary education, research and innovation to address continental challenges and promote global competitiveness
10. Promote peace education and conflict prevention and resolution at all levels of education and for all age groups
11. Improve management of education system as well build and enhance capacity for data collection, management, analysis, communication, and use
12. Set up a coalition of stakeholders to facilitate and support activities resulting from the implementation of CESA 16-25.

Further, the aim and objectives of the new context and content are in resonance with the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030, adopted in 2015 by Heads of States and Governments at a special UN summit. Specifically, strong resonances are observed with the following goals:

- Goal 1: Eradication of Poverty
- Goal 3: Access to health
- Goal 4: Access to quality education
- Goal 5: Gender equality
- Goal 16: Justice and Peace

Also, the aim and objectives of the new context and content are in line with AU's Agenda 2063 aspirations:

- A Prosperous Africa, based on Inclusive Growth and Sustainable Development
- An Integrated Continent Politically united and based on the ideals of Pan Africanism and the vision of African Renaissance

- An Africa of Good Governance, Democracy, Respect for Human Rights, Justice and the Rule of Law
- A Peaceful and Secure Africa
- Africa with a Strong Cultural Identity Common Heritage, Values and Ethics
- An Africa Whose Development is people driven, relying on the potential offered by African People, especially its Women and Youth, and caring for Children
- An Africa as A Strong, United, Resilient and Influential Global Player and Partner

Achieving all these goals and objectives is not an easy task. The practice of education reform is a complex and multifaceted process that has often failed to produce the promised results. The best ideas often have faltered on the rocks of implementation. Many have followed the diffusion enterprise approach, which involves implanting fast and learning slow. Fortunately, research has provided us with new implementation tools (evolutional enterprise) that involve learning fast and implementing well. The ACDEG program shall be implemented through evolutional enterprise, which entails multiple piloting faces, gradually sequencing reform in an expanding context, and using system thinking to address pressing needs. It involves bringing diverse perspectives to bear, starting small and scaling up changes reliably through Plan-Do-Study-Act cycle. Evolutional enterprise is a network based approach to school improvement, and unlike like previous approaches, is not only focused on final results, but the processes that produce the results – rigorously evaluating qualitative and quantitative data.

The program is holistic, inclusive, ICT-embedded, progressive, spiral, and transformative in character. One key aim of the program is to free women and children from poverty, domestic violence and sexual abuses. The program also aims to promote African cultures and multilingualism. However, the language of instruction in each member state shall be governed by the national policy on education in member states. The competencies learners should develop include transformational civic dispositions, 4Cs skills, ICT skills, and life-long learning skills. It is also important to note that the program shall be adaptable to the context of application, which shall be informed by facts. The overarching goal of the program is to align power, identity, and productivity for inclusive growth in Africa. In other words, to end coup d'états, conflicts, corruption, constitutional and human rights abuses in Africa.

A successful implementation of the new curriculum (called Democracy and Good Citizenship - DGC) will involve paying specific attention to learners from low income homes, those from rural communities, and parent education. Poor parents often struggle to keep up with their children's school fees. In addition, distance and socio-cultural traditions in many communities makes regular attendance and school completion difficult, especially for girls. Strategies that effectively address these inequities will have to be put in place. Some of these strategies include providing equity through free food program in school during break time, providing equity through free transportation to school, and providing equity through free access to digital tools and internet to improve the quality of learning and opportunities. And measures that eliminate financial barriers, possibly through conditional cash grants for poor parents will also have to be exploited. This will involve tapping into the readiness of communities, parents,

and organizations to support the development of schools in their community –financially and otherwise. Through Parent Education, parents and caregivers will be guided not to use authoritarian parenting style that is prevalent in the continent, and to adopt democratic style that promotes communication, collaboration, creativity and critical thinking. Achieving all these will mean increasing the network of school-community education through learning hubs. Equity is not just limited to access to the curriculum, it also imbedded in the quality of the curriculum delivered.

Implementing the ACDEG program will be done through teams of experts that collectively make up a learning hub. In all, there are four teams. Team 1 develops the new DGC curriculum. Team 2, which is made up of clusters of teams from primary, secondary and tertiary education, will implement the curriculum within the formal sector and conduct process evaluation. Team 3 will implement the program in the informal sector and conduct process evaluation. In other words, Team 3 will be responsible for parent education and exploring equity resources for underprivileged pupils in the community and otherwise. Meanwhile, Team 4 will evaluate the effectiveness of each team, and work collaboratively with the state inspectors to conduct program evaluation.

The ACDEG program deviates from the way things have always been done and it requires different ways of thinking about how schooling is organized and how the available infrastructure is used; it also requires different ways of teaching and measuring students' outcomes and opportunities. These changes might also include innovative ways of providing resources to schools. The resource requirement for the implementation of the ACDEG program is appropriately consistent with national means. This makes it imperative for the government of each member states to assume full responsibility in providing resources for the program. This means that available resources should be used intensively and efficiently as possible. There is also the strong need for the public-private partnerships to be efficiently developed to expand implementation capacity with particular attention to the needs of poor pupils. The challenge is to structure these partnerships in such a way that they work effectively and that public and private sector partners can contribute in those areas where they are best placed to do so. And in accordance with Goal number 17 of the SDGs 2030, which state that implementation should be strengthened and revitalized through global partnership, the AU and member states will mobilize external resources to effectively and successfully implement the new curriculum.

The development of the ACDEG program took into consideration the developmental aims and objectives of each member states and ensures that the program evolves with the continent's economy and helps young people adopt values and attitudes that help them function as responsible citizens and productive workers. It also took into consideration the pressing need to incorporate ICT into school practices in order to improve the quality of learning for students and meet their dot-com aspirations. Reforming examination and assessment systems to focus on both students' cognitive and participation skills, as well as participation in international or regional assessments was also deemed necessary. The curriculum was developed on "Key Stage" geometry and the appropriate pedagogical approaches, grounded in rigorous research, were cited. Emphasis is put on creative and active learning and equity. Without ensuring the quality of opportunities to learn, expansion of access to education is a meaningless waste of resources.

Successfully attaining the goals and objectives of the ACDEG program will require that primary, secondary and tertiary educations are given almost the same priority in terms of financing. The existing body of literature shows that secondary education has always been less financed compared to the other two sectors. Between 1999 and 2004 total aid commitments to education in Sub-Saharan Africa increased by 75% from \$1.2 to \$ 2.1 billion. Virtually all of this increase was allocated to primary and tertiary education. In 2015, the World Bank, Africa branch, made a strong call for Sub-Saharan governments to invest more in secondary education. That call met some positive endorsement but much remain to be done.

Thus far, due to differences in history, culture and policy choices, the state of civic education varies dramatically across the continent. Most often ideology rather than pragmatism determines civic education benchmarks in the continent. It is evident that such organic benchmarks have sown seeds of some of the terrible malice that have plagued the continent and stifled economic growth. On the other hand, where benchmarks are based on pragmatism, peaceful coexistence and accelerated economic growth is observed. The African Union intention is to support member states to attain maximum economic growth and stability, by setting basic threshold frequency in civic education for all African pupils, irrespective of geopolitical identify and socio-economic status. Achieving such an ambitious dream will require we all work collaboratively together to effectively and efficiently implement the ACDEG program with the vigour and commitment that it merits.

The ACDEG program provides opportunities to learn for all, ensures equitable access for the disadvantaged, and is relevant to each member state development aspirations and opportunities. As recommended by the ACDEG (Article 12), State Parties should implement the ACDEG program and carry out activities designed to promote democratic principles and practices as well as consolidate a culture of democracy and peace. To this end, they should, inter alia, integrate civic education in their educational curricula and develop appropriate programmes and activities.

This document is made up of nine chapters. Chapter 1 is the general framework. It provides an overview of the document. Chapter 2 looks at the strategies for mainstreaming the ACDEG program in-and-out of the school context. Chapter 3 gives a relative in-depth of the DGC curriculum. Chapter 4 explores the recommended student-centred pedagogies that will be used to implement the curriculum. Chapter 5 looks at all the assessment and evaluation approaches that will be used to fine tune the program. Chapter 6 dives into all the possible resource outlets that can be used to successfully implement the program. Chapter 7 scans through the best piloting approach for the program. Chapter 8 looks at how parent/community education (BSBH) will be used to effectively realize the goals and objectives of the ACDEG program. Chapter 9 is the conclusion.

PART 1

MAINSTREAMING THE ACDEG PROGRAM IN SCHOOLS

Chapter 1:

GENERAL FRAMEWORK

1: General Framework

1.1: Overview

The social-economic and political challenges in Africa at the beginning of the 21st century are urgent and unprecedented. These include wide spread corruption, violent conflicts, political fragmentation, gross human rights abuses, poor health system, poor accountability to public services, gender inequality, food insecurity, foreign aid dependency syndrome, reduction in foreign direct investment (FDI) that correlates with poor human capital, and climate change dilemma (economic development in the face of environmental sustainability). A rich and growing literature has identified a “developed human capital” as the key fulcrum to resolve these challenges. Faced with persistent gaps of what is actually learned in schools in terms of civic education, and the continuous vicious cycle of social malice that has plague the continent, changes in civic curricula and pedagogy were deemed inevitable. This recommendation is supported by the Africa Human Development Department (AFTHD) World Bank in 2015. But more important, it should change the mental models of schooling and governance that dominate African education policy and practice.

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1. Promote adherence, by each State Party, to the universal values and principles of democracy and respect for human rights;
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3. Promote the holding of regular free and fair elections to institutionalize legitimate authority of representative government as well as democratic change of government;
4. Prohibit, reject and condemn unconstitutional change of government in any Member State as a serious threat to stability, peace, security, and development;
5. Promote and protect the independence of the judiciary;

6. Nurture, support, and consolidate good governance by promoting democratic culture and practice, building and strengthening governance institutions and inculcating political pluralism and tolerance;
7. Encourage effective coordination and harmonization of governance policies amongst State Parties with the aim of promoting regional and continental integration;
8. Promote State Parties' sustainable development and human security;
9. Promote the fight against corruption in conformity with the provisions of the AU Convention on Preventing and Combating Corruption adopted in Maputo, Mozambique in July 2003;
10. Promote the establishment of the necessary conditions to foster citizen participation, transparency, access to information, freedom of the press, and accountability in the management of public affairs;
11. Promote gender balance and equality in the governance and development processes;
12. Enhance cooperation between the Union, Regional Economic Communities and the International Community on democracy, elections and governance; and
13. Promote best practices in the management of elections for purposes of political stability and good governance (Article 2 of ACDEG).

Further, the aim and objectives of the new context and content are supported by the strategic objectives of the Continental Education Strategy for Africa 2016-2025 (CESA 16-25), which include:

1. Revitalize the teaching profession to ensure quality and relevance at all levels of education
2. Build, rehabilitate, preserve education infrastructure and develop policies that ensure a permanent, healthy and conducive learning environment in all sub-sectors and for all, so as to expand access to quality education
3. Harness the capacity of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) to improve access, quality and management of education and training systems

4. Ensure acquisition of requisite knowledge and skills as well as improved completion rates at all levels and groups through harmonization processes across all levels for national and regional integration
5. Accelerate processes leading to gender parity and equity
6. Launch comprehensive and effective literacy programmes across the continent to eradicate the scourge of illiteracy
7. Strengthen the science and mathematics curricula in youth training and disseminate scientific knowledge and culture in society
8. Expand technical and vocational education and training (TVET) opportunities at both secondary and tertiary levels and strengthen linkages between the world of work and education and training systems
9. Revitalize and expand tertiary education, research and innovation to address continental challenges and promote global competitiveness
10. Promote peace education and conflict prevention and resolution at all levels of education and for all age groups
11. Improve management of education system as well as build and enhance capacity for data collection, management, analysis, communication, and use
12. Set up a coalition of stakeholders to facilitate and support activities resulting from the implementation of CESA 16-25.

Further, the aim and objectives of the new context and content are in resonance with the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030, adopted in 2015 by Heads of State and Government at a special UN summit. Specifically, strong resonances are observed with the following goals:

- Goal 1: Eradication of Poverty
- Goal 3: Access to health
- Goal 4: Access to quality education
- Goal 5: Gender equality

- Goal 16: Justice and Peace

Also, the aim and objectives of the new content are in line with the seven AU's Agenda 2063 aspirations, which include:

- A Prosperous Africa, based on Inclusive Growth and Sustainable Development
- An Integrated Continent Politically united and based on the ideals of Pan Africanism and the vision of African Renaissance
- An Africa of Good Governance, Democracy, Respect for Human Rights, Justice and the Rule of Law
- A Peaceful and Secure Africa
- Africa with a Strong Cultural Identity Common Heritage, Values and Ethics
- An Africa Whose Development is people driven, relying on the potential offered by African People, especially its Women and Youth, and caring for Children
- An Africa as A Strong, United, Resilient and Influential Global Player and Partner

Strategies for Mainstreaming the ACDEG program in-and out of the school context

The primary aim of the ACDEG program is to implement the Democracy and Good Citizenship (DGC) curriculum in schools. To this end, a roadmap on how to achieve the prime aim is required. As recommended by a consultative meeting of experts in Nouakchott, Mauritania, 2019, the roadmap should start by raising awareness. The principal intention of the awareness raising campaign is to inform both stakeholders and the community at large, and to solicit feedback and commitments for the effective and successful implementation of the curriculum. The awareness campaign will be paralleled by efforts to map the existing resources in the community, and create new ones for the successful implementation of the curriculum. A portion of the human asset shall constitute the Learning Hub, which shall be divided into teams. One team shall be responsible for mainstreaming the curriculum in schools. And another team will be responsible for monitoring the effectiveness of the aforementioned team.

The integration strategies for the effective and successful implementation of the DGC curriculum in school shall be done on two fronts:

- The curriculum will be taught as a stand-alone subject – with the establishment of a school parliament plus the celebration of Human Rights Day, Anti-Corruption Day, Peaceful Co-existence Day, Women Day, Youth Day, and Accountability in Public Service Day.

- Aspects of the curriculum will be integrated (taught) in other subjects - with the establishment of a school parliament plus the celebration of Human Rights Day, Anti-Corruption Day, Peace Co-existence Day, Accountability in Public Service Day and Independence Day.

It is worth noting that these two integration approaches will disrupt the status-quo, since it involve adapting the pedagogy of all other subjects to learner-centered teaching/learning and the entire management of institutions will have to be democratic. Further, Curriculum Design will be a compulsory part of pedagogy.

Commissioning both approaches to improve learners' outcomes and opportunities is recommended by a growing body of rigorous literature, particularly by key global and continental frameworks such as the 2030 SDGs, AU's Agenda 2063, and CESA 2016-2025.

Curriculum

The DGC curriculum contains the six key thematic identified by the consultative meeting of experts of Ministries of Education in Abuja, Nigeria, 2015 to be taught to all African children, starting from pre-primary to tertiary education level. It incorporates the Civic and Human Rights curriculum that already exist in member states. And it is a set of concepts, principles, and values for learners in Africa, to ensure they all learn the same things and grow up into well rounded individuals familiar with and knowledgeable with adept democracy and good governance. As such, pupils of compulsory school age in community and foundation schools, including community special schools and foundation special schools, and in voluntary-aided and voluntary-controlled schools, must follow the DGC curriculum.

The six identified strands include:

1. Constitutionalism and the rule of law
2. Democracy and human rights
3. Culture and peace
4. Governance and governing institutions
5. Elections and electoral processes
6. Political, economic and social issues

The basic values include:

- Freedom, Patriotism, Tolerance, Acceptance, Openness, Love, Compassion, Transparency, Civility, Dignity, Hospitality, Equity and Equality;
- Respect for the Constitution, Human Rights, Properties, Fairness, Empathy, Integrity, Honesty, Justice and Accountability.

The curriculum aims to equip learners with right knowledge, skills, attitudes and tools to be active participants in their communities; to ensure peaceful co-existence in Africa; eradicate corruption and coup d'états, improve accountable in public services; and uphold human rights values and practices with pride.

The curriculum is organized into blocks of years called 'key stages' (KS). There are a total of six key stages. And at the end of each key stage, the teacher will formally assess learners' performance. Although the curriculum is divided into key stages, the key concepts are spiraled upward – with the 6 thematic gradually expanding across the 6 key stages. It is also important to note that each of the thematic has three core themes qualities, namely: (1) fundamental concepts; (2) promotion and protection attributes; and (3) social-economic and political benefits attributes.

The DGC curriculum deviates from the way things have always been done and it requires different ways of thinking about how education is organized and how the available infrastructure is used; it also requires different ways of teaching and measuring learners' outcomes and opportunities. These changes might also include innovative ways of providing resources to schools. A high-quality DGC education provides learners with the finest knowledge, skills, values, attitude and tools to become positive and inclusive leaders in society. A leadership not merely defined by official position, but by a practical commitment to improve humanity. In particular, the DGC education should foster learners' keen awareness and understanding of peaceful coexistence, the detrimental effect of unconstitutional change of government, of corruption, the strong need for accountability and strong institutions, and how laws are made and upheld.

To this end, the AU and the Ministry of Education in each member state is required to publish the DGC curriculum, setting out the 'matters, skills and processes' to be taught at each key stage. Schools are free to choose how they organize their school day, as long as the content of the DGC curriculum is taught and applied to all learners.

Pedagogy

Faced with the persistent gaps of what is actually learned in schools in terms of civic education, and the continuous vicious cycle of social malice that has plagued the continent, changes in civic pedagogy and curricula are deemed inevitable. The Sage on Stage, which is the dominant teaching approach in Africa, has been shown by research to be too weak in improving learners' outcomes and opportunities. To achieve the African Union dream of creating a new African citizen who will be an effective change agent for the continent's sustainable development, changes in pedagogy are inevitable. Teaching should value and encourage learners' voice and choice; it should equip them with collaboration, communication, creative, and critical thinking skills; learners should be able to explore political and social issues critically, to weigh evidence, debate and make reasoned arguments. More so, the teaching should equip learners with the schema, language and tools to manage their resources on a day-to-day basis, and plan for future financial needs. This form of teaching puts learners at center of the learning process. This sort of teaching includes: Higher Order Discussion (HOD) technique, use of Question Quadrant (QQ), Project based learning (PBL), use of Drama, use of Songs, use of Games, etc. Effective Cultural-based pedagogy and teaching approaches used during the COVID-19 lockdown shall also be explored. Teaching within the informal sector shall strongly make use of radio and television media. The development of teaching and learning tools, unit plan, and lesson plans shall come at the second phase of the program development.

Assessment & Program Evaluation

To systematically determine the merits, worth and significance of the ACDEG program, the DGC curriculum shall be subjected to evaluation. The DGC curriculum evaluation will include "Class Assessment", "Program Evaluation" and "Process Evaluation". Class Assessment is any activity which checks how well a learner is learning in order to adapt teaching and learning approaches to improve his/her outcomes and opportunities. This assessment can either be formative or summative or both. Program Evaluation includes studying how teachers and learners interact with each other and with the curriculum or syllabus in a particular setting. Usually, unintendedly, it is confined to investigating only what learners have learned or to analyzing curriculum designs and lessons plans.

Process Evaluation is the systematic, rigorous, and meticulous application of scientific methods to assess the design, implementation, improvement, or outcomes of a program - focusing on the daily processes of the program. It uses Deming Cycle, iterating between exploration and exploitation, to improve change reliably at scale. Process evaluation, unlike Program evaluation (that is focused on accountability), is focused on measurement for improvement.

Resources

The resource requirement for the implementation of the ACDEG program is appropriately consistent with national means. This makes it imperative for the government of each member states to assume full responsibility in providing resources for the program. This means that available resources should be used intensively and efficiently as possible. There is also the strong need for the public-private partnerships to be efficiently developed to expand implementation capacity with particular attention to the needs of poor learners. The challenge is to structure these partnerships in such a way that they work effectively and that public and private sector partners can contribute in those areas where they are best placed to do so. There are twenty four (24) distinct potential sources of resources for the successful and effective implementation of the ACDEG program. These pools of resources include government, non-governmental, local, and international sources. However, it is highly recommended for the government of each member state to take full responsibility in providing the resources needed for the successful and effective implementation of the program.

The AU should follow-up and ensure that every member state prioritise adequate resource allocation for the implementation of ACDEG program. Therefore each state should have realistic strategy, work plan and budget for the program. The AU on its part would provide a clear policy for the resource allocation and monitoring which every member state has to adhere to. While other sources of funding may definitely be sought, these should be supplementary to government funding.

Africa spends roughly the same percent of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on education as East Asian countries. In 2004, African countries spent 4.6% of GDP on education, comparable to the between 4.3% and 4.6% in Korea, Singapore, Thailand and Vietnam. One can find similar ratios in the 1960s and the 1980s. But the outcomes are very different, mainly because of differences in the quality of curriculum and pedagogy, and the efficient use of resources. The ACDEG program has taken into account the issues related to quality curriculum and pedagogy, the efficient use of resources for the effective implementation of the program is largely the responsibility of the implementing country. More so, some countries may actually have to do much better in providing resources for education. Whereas the averages educational expenditure in Africa is about 4.6% of GDP, in some countries, it is as low as 2%.

Piloting

The ACDEG program shall be implemented through evolutionary enterprise. This entails multiple piloting faces, gradually sequencing reform in an expanding context, and using system thinking to address pressing needs. It involves bringing diverse perspectives to bear, starting small and scaling up changes reliably through Plan-Do-Study-Act cycle. Evolutionary enterprise, unlike Diffusion and Shell enterprise, is not only focused on final results, but also the processes that produce the results – rigorously evaluating qualitative and quantitative data.

In the course of the sequential implementation, the Learning Hub will be confronted by two improvement problems: innovation problem and adaptive implementation problem. Innovation problems are problems for which there is inadequate research, few established solutions, and little practical experience that can serve as a resource for collaborative problem solving. Innovation problems arise when we do web or library searches, or when we interview colleagues, and we struggle to find a solution in which we can have much confidence. Innovation problems require exploration, a type of divergent learning involving invention, design, experimentation, and refinement. On the other hand, Adaptive implementation problems are encountered while importing, or spreading and using promising solutions, either developed in-house or adopted from outside. It is a type of convergent, trial and error learning associated with leveraging promising solutions in new contexts. It can focus on modifying solutions to succeed in new context, and on additional exploratory learning that comes with local adaptation.

Five countries, who have ratified the ACDEG, have been selected as sample countries to pilot the document; however, only those countries who have showed willingness to serve as piloting countries shall run the piloting program. The proposed piloting countries include:

- Algeria, Lesotho;
- Central African Republic;
- Nigeria and Comoros.

1.2 Definition of Terms

The following are operational definitions

- **Ambitious instruction:** This refers to a teaching approach in which learners' brain is very busy. It demands high levels of socio-cognitive activity. It aims to have learners meet high but largely achievable expectations - sometimes failure is an important tool for learning.
- **Ambitious project:** It is a project in which diverse perspectives are brought in to bear. It is a project with higher but achievable expectation. And the resources are aligned. It is a project in which constant research is brought in to bear, for developmental aim.
- **Best Governance:** This refers to a government system in which the Rule of Law, Transparency, Responsiveness, Consensus Orientation, Equity and Inclusiveness, Effectiveness and Efficiency, Accountability, and Participation are the practical cultural norms, and infrastructure, and are constantly been improve through research.
- **4Cs:** These are the four competences a learner has to attain: Critical and Creative thinking, Communication and Co-operation.
- **Civic Education:** This include broader concepts underpinning democratic society such as the respective roles and responsibilities of citizens, government, political and special interest groups, the mass media and the business and non-profit sectors, as well as the significance of periodic and competitive elections. Civic education is a continuous and long-term process which is usually embedded in education curriculum and other programs.
- **Curriculum:** This is a document in which the expected behavior of students are stated; how to attain such behavior and how such expected behavior can be evaluated.
- **Democracy:** Is government by the people in which the supreme power is vested in the people and exercised directly by them or by their elected agents under free and fair elections.
- **Diffusion enterprise:** This is an approach to educational reform in which designed programs are rapidly implemented with fidelity, and neglecting to address the variation in local context.

- **Education for Democracy:** Is an educational ideal in which democracy is both the goal and method of instruction. It brings democratic values to education and can include self-determination, as well as promoting values of equity, equality, justice, respect, participation and tolerance.
- **Evolutional enterprise:** This is a network-based approach to educational reform in which central hubs collaborate with large numbers of schools to devise, use, and refine systemic, school-wide improvement programs.
- **Family:** This is networks of people who share their lives over long periods of time bound by ties of marriage, blood, or commitment, legal or otherwise, who consider themselves as family and who share a significant history and anticipated future of functioning in a family relationship.
- **Guide on the side:** It is a teaching approach in which learners' communication, collaboration, creative and critical thinking skills are constantly been developed. The learners' voice and agency is prioritized. It is a teaching approach not only for the 21st century learners but for future learners.
- **Improvement science:** This is the bright light at the end of the tunnel – not another train. It is a proven approach to school improvement grounded in rigorous research. It is a collaborative research - practice partnership to improve students' opportunities and outcomes.
- **Learner:** A person who is learning a subject or skill through formal or non-formal education systems or programs.
- **Learning hub:** A body of experts who work hand-in-gloves with schools and policymakers, and other stakeholders, on daily basis, to bring promising solutions, based on rigorous research, to pressing needs.
- **Learning systems:** These are networks of schools, improvement teams and other organizations that collaborate to produce, use, adapt and constantly refine the knowledge, norms and resources needed to improve educational opportunities and outcomes for large numbers of students. In other words, a learning system is community of teachers, leaders, developers, coaches, evaluators, and others working collaboratively together to discover and explore new paths toward desired ends, paving smooth those paths that show the most promise in inviting others to join-in in traveling those new roads. Metaphorically, a learning system is an epistemic community that share common tools, schema (theory) and language (code) to address specific social problems.

- **Mainstreaming:** This is the spreading of the ACDEG Agenda into every thread of the social fabric in Africa.
- **Pedagogy:** The approach and method of teaching, especially as an academic subject or theoretical concept.
- **Positive and Inclusive leadership:** This is a leadership approach that set higher but achievable expectations, aligns resources, and includes everyone in the leadership process.
- **Quality Education:** it is an educational system in which students' collaboration, communication, creative and critical thinking skills are constantly been developed. It is a system in which students are constantly creating artifacts in the course of consuming knowledge.
- **System thinking:** This is a holistic approach to analysis that focuses on the way that a system constituent parts interrelate, and how they work over time and within the context of larger systems.
- **Sage on stage:** This is sometimes termed teacher-centered teaching. It is a teaching approach, predominantly used in many primary and secondary schools, where the teacher is active while the learners are passive. The learners are considered to be empty vessels while the teacher monopolizes the blackboard.
- **Transformational leaders:** Unlike transactional leaders who are extrinsically motivated and are committed to stability, transformational leaders are intrinsically motivated and committed to change. Transformational leaders do not necessary hold official positions. They set high expectations and align resources. They motivate and inspire followers to achieve extraordinary.
- **Zone of proximal development:** This zone consists of skills too difficult for a child to master on his/her own, but that can be done with guidance and encouragement from a knowledgeable person.

Chapter 2: STRATEGIES FOR MAINSTREAMING THE ACDEG PROGRAM IN SCHOOLS

2.1: Introduction

The primary aim of the ACDEG program is to implement the DGC curriculum in schools/institutions of education. To this end, a roadmap on how to achieve the prime aim is required. As recommended by a consultative meeting of experts in Nouakchott, Mauritania, December 2019, the roadmap should start by raising awareness. The main intention of the awareness raising campaign is to inform both stakeholders and the community at large, and to solicit feedback and commitments for the effective and successful implementation of the DGC curriculum. The awareness campaign will be followed by efforts to map the existing resources in the community, and create new ones for the successful implementation of the DGC curriculum. A part of the human asset shall constitute the Learning Hub, which shall be divided into teams. One team shall be responsible for mainstreaming the curriculum in schools. And the other team will be responsible for monitoring the effectiveness of the previous teams. Both teams shall receive training on how to implement and evaluate the program. And the teacher's guide shall constitute one of the main tools for the implementing team. It is important to note that the asset mapping initiative will be paralleled efforts to survey the implementing environment and generate a risk-factors list. This is to ensure the implementation is effective and efficient.

The integration strategies for the effective and successful implementation of the DGC curriculum in school shall be done on two fronts:

- The curriculum will be taught as a stand-alone subject – with the establishment of a school parliament plus the celebration of Human Rights Day, Anti-Corruption Day, Peace Co-existence Day, and Accountability in Public Service Day.
- Aspects of the curriculum will be integrated (taught) in other subjects - with the establishment of a school parliament plus the celebration of Human Rights Day, Anti-Corruption Day, Peace Co-existence Day, Freedom Day and Accountability in Public Service Day.

It is worth noting that these two integration approaches will disrupt the status-quo, since it involve adapting the pedagogy of all other subjects to learner-centered teaching/learning and the entire management of institutions will have to be democratic. Further, Curriculum Design will be a compulsory part of pedagogy.

Commissioning both approaches to improve learners' outcomes and opportunities is recommended by a growing body of rigorous literature, particularly by key global and continental frameworks such as the 2030 SDGs, AU's Agenda 2063, and CESA 2016-2025.

Within the school context, a strong focus will be on mapping and facilitating the interdependent processes that occur between students, curriculum, and the teacher. It is worth noting that there are no easy solutions to the challenges confronting Africa. By bringing diverse perspectives to bear, our chances of overcoming the problems facing the continent are high.

A successful implementation of the curriculum will require paying attention to two key areas: pedagogy and parent involvement. These include paying specific consideration to kids from low income homes, those from rural communities. Poor parents often struggle to keep up payment of their children school fees. In addition, distance from the school and socio-cultural traditions makes regular attendance and school completion difficult -especially for girls. Strategies that effectively address these inequities will have to be put in place. And measures that eliminate financial barriers, possibly through facilities such as conditional cash grants for poor parents will also be exploited. Further, parents and caregivers will be guided to move away from the authoritarian parenting style that is prevalent in the continent to a democratic style that promotes communication, collaboration, creativity and critical thinking. This will mean increasing the network of school-community opportunities through a learning hub. This will involve tapping into the readiness of communities and parents to support the development of schools in their community –financially and otherwise. Equity is not just limited to access to the curriculum, it is also imbedded in the quality of the curriculum delivered through learner-centered pedagogy.

Therefore, the plan of action involves:

- Raising Awareness for buy-in ;
- Creating Asset Map each member state to build on promising efforts and resources on the ground;
- Creating new learning hubs, in each member state, and conducting training for effective and efficient implementation; and
- Mainstreaming in schools – with the aid of teacher’ guide.

2.2: Raising Awareness

Raising public awareness involves creating a specific messaging campaign about a particular issue. The importance of raising public awareness is to develop and sustain public support for the ACDEG program. More importantly, to invite public opinion to fine-tune the program.

Some channels to raise people’s awareness include (but not limited to):

1. Use of media (radio, press, and television);
2. Use of social media (Facebook, twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube);
3. Use of educational events;

4. Use of public events;
5. Use of Youth groups and Women Youths;
6. Use of village and community heads;
7. Make informational pamphlets;
8. Engage goodwill ambassadors;
9. Engage religious leaders;
10. Engage civil societies ;
11. Development of ACDEG App; and
12. Use the Regional Economic Communities (RECs).

2.3: Creating Asset Map for each African country

What is Asset Mapping?

- Community asset mapping is a strength-based approach to community development.
- The goal of asset mapping is to document a community's existing resources, incorporating these strengths into community development work.
- The process of asset mapping can include identifying the **institutions, individuals, and citizen associations** existing within communities that serve as positive resources.
- Approaching individuals and communities from an asset-based mentality empowers them to recognize their own strengths and capacities.

How Does Asset Mapping Work?

Institution Mapping creates a map of institutions within the community that can be oriented towards solving a particular problem.

For example:

- Higher institutions such as universities, Pan African Universities, School of Education (FASTEF and ENS), School of Law, School of Public Security, and the School of Policymakers.
- Government bodies such as Ministry of Education, Parliament, House of Representative, Municipalities, Councils, Police and Gendarmerie.
- Philanthropic institutions such as SDG Philanthropy Platform, Africa Philanthropy Network, Arab University Alliance for Civic Engagement and Global Philanthropy Alliance
- Refugees' organizations such as the Catholic Relief Services, Mercy Corps, Save the Children, Muslim Refugees Association of South Africa, and UNHCR.
- Democratic organizations such as the Democracy Development Program (DDP), Foundation for Democracy in Africa (FDA), National Democratic Institute (NDI), and National Endowment for Democracy (NED).
- Political parties such as Alliance for the Republic (APR, Senegal), Free Patriotic Union (FPU, Tunisia), National Super Alliance (NASA, Kenya), Cameroon People's Democratic Movement (CPDM), African National Congress (ANC), and All Progressives Congress (APC).
- Electoral organizations such as the Electoral Institute for Sustainable Democracy in Africa (EISA), Electoral Knowledge Network of the Central African States (RESEAC), European Centre for Electoral Support (ECES) and International Foundation for Electoral Systems (IFES).
- Philanthropic Companies (specializing in corporate social responsibility) such as Coca-Cola, Chevron, ExxonMobil, Microsoft, Merck and foundations.
- Local businesses such as Sole Rebels, Africa Felix Juice, Paystack, AgriProtein, and Takamoto Biogas.
- Regional Economic Communities (RECs) and Global Partnership for Education.

Individual Mapping creates a map of the “gifts, skills and capacities” of the individuals living in and out of the community whose efforts will be oriented towards solving a particular problem.

For example:

- Academicians such as supervisors, researchers, reformers, lawyers and psychologists. Namely: Andre Mbata Mangu, Margaret Mungherera, Khabele Matlosa, Adebayo Olukoshi, Charles Fombad, Theodore Holo, Babacar Kante, Abena Busia, Theo Sowa. Ama Ata Aidoo, Quarraisha Abdool Karim, Francisca Nneka Okeke and Umang Mostapha.
- Activists such as judicial and citizen activists, economic activists, and internet activists. Namely: Osai Ojigho, Leymah Gbowee, Amina Mama, Aisha Fofana Ibrahim, Rainatou Sow, Wangari Maathai, Akwannuasah Gyimah, Nabimanya Humphrey, Isaac Ejakhegbe, and Brian Mutebi.
- Artists such as Abdoulaye Konaté, Lionel Smit, Ransome Stanley, Gonçalo Mabunda, Nnenna Okore, William Joseph Kentridge, Amos Tutoula, J.M. Coetzee, Meja Meja Mwangi, Mia Couto, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, Ines Abassi, and Fadhili Frank Mtanga.
- Local philanthropists such as Francois van Niekerk, Alain Gray, Theophilus Danjuma, Aliko Dangote, Strive Masiyiwa and Othman Benjelloun.
- International philanthropists such as Mo Ibrahim, Bill Gates, Warren Buffett, George Soros, Azim Premji, Charles Francis Feeney, Sulaiman bin Abdul Aziz Al Rajhi, Dietmar Hopp, Pierre Omidyar, Jon Huntsman Sr., Li Ka-shing, Mark Zuckerberg, Paul Allen.
- Musicians such as Salif Keita, Youssou N'dour, Oumou Sangare, Onyeka Onwenu, Angélique Kidjo, Khaled, Femi Kuti, Fally Ipupa, Manu Dibango, Koffi Olomide, Sona Maya Jobarteh, Davido, Mary Boyoi, Vanessa Mdee, Alpha Blondy and Angella Katatumba.
- Footballers such as Sadio Mané, Mohamed Salah, Riyad Mahrez, Kalidou Koulibaly, Pierre-Emerick Aubameyang, Samuel Eto'o, Nicolas Pépé, Hakim Ziyech, Naby Keita, Wahbi Khazri, Cédric Bakambu, and André Onana.
- Politicians such as Lindiwe Mazibuko, Mbali Ntuli, Alengot Oromait, Diane Shima Rwigara, Sophia Abdi Noor, Joice Mujuru, Aja Fatoumata Jallow, Ellen Johnson Sirleaf, Hellen Zille, and Julius Malemma.

Citizen Association Mapping creates a map of the associations through which people within communities come together.

For example:

- Community Development Volunteers for Technical Assistance (CDVTA).
- Moje Foundation.

- Tesfa Social and Development Association (TSDA).
- Knowledge and Advancement (Karika).
- The Maseru Women Senior Citizens Association.
- Center for Community Advancement and Family Empowerment (CECAFE).
- Almanar Voluntary Organization
- East African Civil Society Organizations' Forum, (EACSOFF)
- African Citizens Development Foundation

2.4: Creating new learning hubs, in each member state, and conducting training for effective and efficient implementation

Why do we need to create new learning hubs in each member state?

Imagine yourself standing by the window of a classroom, and ask yourself: what determines these students' day to day experiences in the class?

1. Is it the teacher?

What s/he knows and what s/he can do?

What s/he believes and value, and how s/he works together with others to improve his/her practice?

2. Is it the curriculum materials and other resources used in the classroom?

3. Is it the way the school principal engages the teacher to improve his/her practice?

4. Is it the classroom assessment or state assessments used to hold schools accountable for their learning?

5. Is it the students' families?

6. Is it the students' communities?

7. Is it the level of inspection and other monitoring practices?
8. Is it how the teacher was trained?
9. Or is it the expertise of the trainer?

It is obvious that what students experience daily in classrooms is not just one of these things, but rather the product of complex interactions amongst all of these things and more over time. Practicing good governance and providing quality education to Africans, requires that leaders develop capabilities in themselves and in others to see this complexity, to describe it, to think and reason about it, and ultimately to intervene in it. To provide equity and excellence to our learners, to improve the democratic culture of the continent, to meet the challenges placed on us by the 21st century, we will have to make the extraordinary ordinary. We will have to create new types of learning hubs and function as an epistemic community - sharing the same schema, tools and language. The principal aim is to move away from targeted improvement efforts to continuous improvement efforts.

A hub, also called a network hub, is a common connection point or central part of other organizations in a network. Hubs can be commonly used to connect segments of an education sector. These new hubs will contain multiple organizations, both local and international, so that when an education initiative arrives from one organization, it is easily copied to the other parts of the network. As such, the same innovation is seen by all the other organizations and the required amount of synergy is injected into it. That is, the new hubs will allow multiple organizations to communicate with each other over a network more efficiently.

These hubs will collaborate with schools to form learning systems. Members of these learning systems will include teachers, principals, coaches, supervisors, district heads, researchers, reformers, psychologists, philanthropists, human right activists, experts in the use of technology in classrooms, experts in literacy, mathematics, science and other disciplines. With such a diverse collaborative community, guided by a specific theory of practice improvement, different members will hold different roles contributing unique knowledge, skills and values to systemic improvement efforts of schools for the realization of the ACDEG program.

Once the hub is formed, what next?

First let us compare Old ways of schools improvement and new ways of schools improvement based on rigorous research.

Old ways of school improvement using Inspectors (Targeted improvement initiative)

1. Inspectors show up ones in a year in schools to observe teachers, ask them few questions, and encourage them to improve their practice or else.
2. Inspectors organize few workshops for teachers and tell them to transfer the knowledge acquired to those teachers who were not present in the workshop.
3. Strictly performance management.

New ways of school improvement using improvement teams (Continuous improvement initiative) – base on rigorous research.

1. This approach requires that the improvement team (a team of diverse experts) work closely with teachers and policymakers on daily bases.
2. The improvement team uses the following tools to improve learners' outcomes and opportunities:
 - i. The Principles of Improvement Science (see page 202)
 - ii. The 5 Essential Framework (see page 203)
 - iii. The Triple Es Framework (see page 121)
 - iv. The Computing Value Framework (see page 208)
 - v. The Positive and Inclusive Leadership Framework (see page 210)
3. Strictly improvement management.

Note: Questions asked in “Performance Management” are quite different from questions asked in “Improvement Management”. This means Inspectors will have to learn new skills, values, knowledge and attitudes.

Once a hub is formed, for a particular country, they will undergo training and will be responsible for generating improvement teams for each school in the country. The improvement teams, and the rest of the hub, are basically researchers of some sort.

Research – Practice Partnerships (RPPs)

One unique feature of these new learning systems is the idea of having researchers (improvement teams) in schools, on daily bases, working closely together with practitioners and policymakers to tailor innovations, grounded in evidence-based solutions, to pressing needs. Such collaborations between researchers and practitioners aimed at improving the core work of schools - teaching and learning – is called research-practice partnerships (RPPs). RPPs are long-term, mutualistic collaborations between practitioners and researchers that are intentionally organized to investigate problems of practice and solutions for improving learners’ outcomes.

When researchers work collaboratively with teachers, points of interest include:

1. Providing technical and social support.
2. Framing specific problems that are user-centered.
3. Conducting interview, Leveraging data, and Visualizing practices.
4. Co-designing change artefacts.
5. Measuring the effectiveness of a specific change idea.
6. Measuring school strata for systemic arrangement.
7. Measuring school strata for contextual adaptation and fidelity implementation.
8. Measuring schools’ strata to identify and justify differences in performance.
9. Helping teachers use the Computing Value Framework (CVF), 5 Essential framework, and the Triple Es framework to ensure ambitious teaching and learning for all.
10. Ensure teachers and principals’ summit plans on how they wish to improve themselves every academic years – probably by taking online courses in groups from the edx platform.
11. Organize projects to synthesize communities.

And when researchers collaborate with policymakers, points of interest include:

1. Identifying common values and goals.
2. Identifying problems of practice and rooms for improvement.
3. Sharing plans and identifying resources.
4. Sharing feedbacks and recommendations.
5. Forming strong partnership, based on trust and respect, and the commitment to work together on complex problems.
6. Co-designing interventions.
7. Creating a corpus of formalized artifacts that would serve as reference for future use.

The extensive curriculum reform, considered necessary for the cultivation of a democratic Africa, has to take into account the complex narratives and identities that teachers bring into their teaching. To this end, the improvement team will create time and space for teachers to share their stories and their understandings of what it means to teach democracy and human rights, so that they begin to embody the values of democratic citizenship education, rather than merely imparting it.

2.5: Mainstreaming in Schools – with the aid of teacher’s guide.

Mainstreaming the DGC curriculum within the school context shall be conducted by team 1 of the learning hub. This team represents a broad group of experts who will be working hand-and-in-gloves with teachers to effectively and successfully implement the DGC curriculum in preschool, primary, secondary and tertiary institutions of education. Hence, team 2 consists of four separate teams, namely:

1. Team 1 Preschool (T1P) will be responsible for preschool.
2. Team 1 Primary School (T1PS) will be responsible for primary school.
3. Team 1 Secondary School (T1SS) will be responsible for secondary school.
4. Team 1 Tertiary School (T1TS) will be responsible for tertiary school.

2.5.1 Two ways to mainstream the DGC curriculum within the school context include:

1. The curriculum will be taught as a stand-alone subject – with the establishment of a school parliament plus the celebration of Human Rights Day, Anti-Corruption Day, Peace Co-existence Day, and Accountability in Public Service Day.
2. Aspects of the curriculum will be integrated (taught) in other subjects - with the establishment of a school parliament plus the celebration of Human Rights Day, Anti-Corruption Day, Peace Co-existence Day, and Accountability in Public Service Day.

Five Steps to engage learners with democracy using School Parliament

1. Create a school learners’ parliament, giving them the opportunity to campaign and vote.
2. Hold Parliament-style debates about topics that are relevant to the children, such as the start of the school day, the breath of the school curriculum, the length of the school day, the length of school holiday, and their voice and agency in pedagogical approach.
3. Invite local Member of Parliament (MP) or peer into school to talk with and work alongside the learners.
4. Visit the Houses of Parliament for free by filling out an application on the education section of their website. Don’t forget to apply for the travel subsidy too.
5. Take part in Parliament debate – through TV, Radio, live streaming online or in person. The parliament should make sure there are free resources for learners, and make possible for students to join in with their live lessons

Method

Each class should have its own Member of Parliament (MP) who represents their class’ views in meetings and then feedback the outcomes to the class.

To become an MP, the candidates must campaign, create a list of ideas and promises – their manifestos – and deliver a ‘why you should vote for me’ speech.

The learners should fill out individual ballots and vote in secret. A school prime minister (PM), from grade 6, is also voted for and they act as the school head boy or girl.

The school MPs and PM meet regularly with an improvement team member to discuss their class's ideas, feedback on previous 'actions' discussed, vote on new ideas and even set up in-school petitions for things such as 'Music on the playground at lunchtime'. Minutes are taken at these meetings and displayed in each classroom.

By explicitly linking what the learners are doing to how our actual voting system and parliament work create a much deeper understanding of elections and why it's important to vote.

This is not too different from the way schools already elect school council representatives, prefects or head boys and girls, but by making these small changes, the children are able to really articulate what democracy means, why it is important and use words like 'campaign', 'manifesto', 'ballot' and 'representative' in an informed way.

Finding time

The improvement teams will work with schools to ensure that such activities are partly embedded in the democracy curriculum time frame and partly in the extra curriculum time frame

Integrating democratic values and concepts into other academic disciplines:

In Literacy, learners should be taught how to write Report, Argumentative and Persuasive genres. In Math, Game Theory can be used to explore promising solutions to complex political problems and weighing bilateral treaties. Statistical analysis of vote is another point of convergent. In Science, scientific enquiry is widely used to analyze the benefits of policies. Further, concepts such as atom, cell, and energy offer a rich platform to talk about democratic values such as tolerance, respect, and willingness to learn and compromise. In History, learners and teachers can explore the history of democracy and how norms and values influences identity. In Geography, teachers and learners can explore the relationships between land and power, land and identity, and land and investment or productivity. In sport, learners and teachers can explore human right issues and the morals of accepting defeat after losing in a competition. In Computer lesson, students can play games such as Mine-craft which explores civic engagements and responsibilities. And democracy is applied philosophy. Appendix 7 contains ideas that teachers of other disciplines can use to teach aspects of the DGC curriculum.

CHAPTER 3: DGC CURRICULUM

KEY STAGES

3.1. Introduction

The DGC curriculum contain the six key thematic identified by the consultative meeting of experts of Ministries of Education in Abuja, Nigeria, 2015 to be taught to all African children, starting from preschool to tertiary education. It incorporates the Civic and Human Rights curriculum that already exist in member states. It is a set of concepts, principles, and values for learners in Africa, to ensure they all learn the same things. As such, learners of compulsory school age in community and foundation schools, including community special schools and foundation special schools, and in voluntary-aided and voluntary-controlled schools, must follow the DGC curriculum.

The curriculum content provides opportunities to learn for all, ensures equitable access for the disadvantaged, and is relevant to each member state development aspirations and opportunities. And as recommended by Article 12 of the ACDEG, State Parties should implement the DGC curriculum and carry out activities designed to promote democratic principles and practices as well as consolidate a culture of democracy and peace.

To this end, the AU and the Ministry of Education in each member state is required to publish the DGC curriculum, setting out the ‘matters, skills and processes’ to be taught at each key stage, and allocate the number of periods per week. Schools are free to choose how they organize their school day, as long as the content of the DGC curriculum is taught to all learners.

The curriculum aims amongst other things to equip learners with the right knowledge, skills, and tools to be active participants in their communities, to ensure peaceful co-existence in Africa, eradicate corruption and coup d’états, are accountable in public services, and uphold human rights values and practices with pride.

The curriculum is organized into blocks of years called ‘key stages’ (KS). There are a total of six key stages. And at the end of each key stage, the teacher will formally assess learners’ performances. And even though the curriculum is divided into key stages, the key concepts are spiraled upwards. It is organized on the basis of 6 key stages and 6 key thematic. It is structured in terms of thematic per key stage and key concept per academic term.

In all, this document sets out the framework for the DGC curriculum in Africa and includes:

- purpose, aims, structure of the DGC curriculum, and the developmental conceptual framework; and
- statements on inclusion, targeted attainments, and contextual information about each key stage.

3.2. Overview

The Democracy and Good Citizenship (DGC) curriculum incorporates the Civic and Human Right curriculum that already exist in member states. The DGC curriculum is a set of concepts, principles, and values for primary, secondary and tertiary school students in Africa, to ensure they all learn the same things. The curriculum is framed on the six key thematic identified by the consultative meeting of experts of Ministries of Education in Abuja, Nigeria, 2015, namely:

1. Constitutionalism and the rule of law
2. Democracy and human rights
3. Culture and peace
3. Governance and governing institutions
4. Elections and electoral processes
5. Political, economic and social issues

The key identified values include:

- Patriotism, Openness, Tolerance and Acceptance
- Justice, Transparency, Equity and Equality
- Civility, Dignity, Love and Compassion, Long life learning
- Fairness, Compliance, Empathy, and Integrity
- Honesty, Accountability, Sharing, and Hospitality, Innovation
- Rule of Law, Respect for the Constitution, Human Rights, and Properties

3.3. The Purpose and Aim

3.3.1 Purpose

A high-quality Democracy and Good Citizenship (DGC) education provides learners with the best knowledge, skills, values, attitude and tools to become not only informed and active citizens, but transformational leaders in society. A leadership not merely defined by official position, but by a practical commitment to improve humanity. In particular, the DGC education should foster learners' keen awareness and understanding of peaceful coexistence, the detrimental effect of unconstitutional change of government, the detrimental effect of corruption, the strong need for accountability and strong institutions, how laws are made and upheld, and how to manage their money on a day-to-day basis, and plan for future financial needs.

3.3.2 Aims

The DGC curriculum aims to ensure that all learners:

1. acquire a sound knowledge and understanding of how an ambitious community, state, and country, is governed, its political system and how citizens participate actively in its democratic systems of government;
2. develop a sound knowledge and understanding of the role of law and the justice system in our society and how laws are shaped and enforced;
3. develop an interest in, and commitment to, participation in volunteering as well as other forms of responsible activity, that they will take with them into adulthood;
4. are equipped with the skills and tools to think critically and debate political questions, to manage their money on a day-to-day basis, and plan for future financial needs;
5. develop a sound knowledge and understanding of diversity, the need for peaceful coexistence, the detrimental effect of corruption, the need for accountability and efficiency service delivery;
6. are equipped with the skills and tools of transformational leadership;
7. are introduced to the best that has been thought and said, and helps engender an appreciation of human creativity and achievement; and
8. are equipped with the tools and skills to love wisdom, and love pursuing it till the end of their lives.

In other words, the aim is to nurture learners who will eradicate conflicts, corruption, coup d'états, constitutional and human rights abuses in Africa.

3.4. Structure

3.4.1 Introduction: A close look at the different curriculum structures in Africa shows that the (6-3-3) and (6-4-3) patterns are the most common approaches in use – (see table 3.4.1.1). Both patterns, of 26% each, make up 52 percent of all the curriculum structures used in Africa. However, unlike the 6-4-3 approach, that is only popular with French speaking African countries, the 6-3-3 structure is used in Portuguese, Arabic, French and English speaking African countries. These different curriculum structures also exhibit different academic terms per year. As shown in table 3.4.1.2, “Trimester”, which makes 82% of all approaches, is the most dominant school term approach in the continent. To this end, the DGC Curriculum is weaved on a 6-3-3 structure with a “trimester” ridge. And since about 78% of Africa countries start primary school at age of the 6, the DGC primary curriculum starts at 6. However, reshaping the curriculum to fit each member state preferred structure during implementation is deemed necessary.

Table 3.4.1.1: The Two Main Curriculum Structures Used in Africa (2020)

	2-Stage System	3-Stage System												
Stage Type	(8-3)	(4-4-4)	(5-4-3)	(5-3-4)	(6-3-3)	(6-2-4)	(6-4-2)	(6-3-4)	(6-4-3) (6-5-2)	(7-3-2) (7-2-3)	(7-4-2)	(8-2-2)		
Educational Stage	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 8</i> <i>Secondary3</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 4</i> <i>Middle 4</i> <i>Secondary 4</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 5</i> <i>Middle 4</i> <i>Secondary3</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 5</i> <i>Middle 3</i> <i>Secondary 4</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 6</i> <i>Middle 3</i> <i>Secondary3</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 6</i> <i>Middle 2</i> <i>Secondary 4</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 6</i> <i>Middle 4</i> <i>Secondary 2</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 6</i> <i>Middle 3</i> <i>Secondary 4</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 6</i> <i>Middle 4</i> <i>Secondary3</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 7</i> <i>Middle 3</i> <i>Secondary 2</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 7</i> <i>Middle 4</i> <i>Secondary 2</i> <i>Tertiary</i>	<i>Preschool</i> <i>Primary 8</i> <i>Middle 2</i> <i>Secondary y2</i> <i>Tertiary</i>		
Age	(6-13) (14-17)	(6-10-14-18)	(6-11-15-18)	(6-11-14-18)	(6-12-15-18)	(6-12-14-18)	(6-12-16-18)	(6-12-15-19)	(7-13-17-20)	(6-13-16-18)	(7-14-16-18)	(6-14-16-18)		
Grade	11	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	13	12		
Country	Sudan	Kenya Somalia South Sudan	Algeria Djibouti Madagascar	Eritrea	Angola Egypt Gambia Guinea Bissau Liberia Mali Morocco Nigeria	Sao Tome And Principe Sierra Leone Libya South Africa Rwanda	DR Congo	Equatorial Guinea	Gabon Ghana Mauritius Tunisia Seychelles	Benin Burkina Faso Burundi Cameroon CAR Chad Congo R SADR	Comoros Cote d’Ivoire Guinea Mauritani a Niger Senegal Togo	Botswana Eswatini Lesotho Mozambi que Namibia Zambia	Tanzania Uganda Zimbabwe	Cabo Verde Ethiopia Malawi

Table 3.4.1.2: The Different Academic Terms per Year in Africa (2020)

Academic Terms per Year (K – 12 or 13)				
	Semester (2 terms per year)	Trimester (3 terms per year)		Quarter (4 terms per year)
Country	Eritrea (Sept – June) Ethiopia (Sept – May or June) Liberia (Sept – June) Morocco (Sept – June) Somalia (Jan – Dec) Sudan (Sept – July) Tanzania (Jan – Dec) Lesotho (Jan – Dec)	Angola (Feb – Dec) Algeria (Sept – July) Angola (Feb – Dec) Benin (Sept – June) Burkina Faso (Sept – May) Burundi (Sept – July) Cameroon (Sept – July) Cape Verde (Sept – June) Central African Rep. (Sept – July) Chad (Sept – July) Comoros (Sept – July) Congo, Republic (Sept – July) Congo, DR (Sept – July) Cote d'Ivoire (Sept – June) Djibouti (Sept – June) Egypt (Sept – June) Eswatini (Jan – Nov) Gabon (Sept – June) Gambia (Sept – June) Ghana (Sept – July) Guinea (Sept – July) Guinea Bissau (Sept – June) Guinea Equatorial (Sept – July)	Kenya (Jan – Nov) Mali (Oct – June) Malawi (Sept – July) Madagascar (Oct – June) Mauritania (Sept – July) Mozambique (Feb – Dec) Mauritius (Jan – Nov) Namibia (Jan – Dec) Niger (Sept – July) Nigeria (Sept – July) Rwanda (Jan – Oct) Senegal (Oct – July) Seychelles (Jan – Dec) Sierra Leone (Sept – July) Sao Tome and Principe (Sept – Jun) South Sudan (Feb – Dec) Togo (Sept – June) Tunisia (Sept – June) Uganda (Feb – Nov) Zambia (Jan – Dec) Zimbabwe (Jan – Dec) Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic (SADR) (Sept – July)	Botswana (Jan – Dec) South Africa (Jan – Dec)

3.4.2 Key Stages

The DGC curriculum is organized into blocks of years called '*key stages*' (KS), and the content is arranged in terms of strands per key stage and key concept per academic term as set out in the tables below.

Key Stage 0 is the *Early Childhood Development (ECD)* Stage. ECD is defined as the period from conception up to school entry. It is a unique window of opportunity for children's cognition, social, emotional, and physical development, which occurs as the result of interaction between the environment and the child. Children are already learning at birth, and they develop and learn at a rapid pace in their early years. Research shows that from a young age, as early as infancy, children derive theories to explain the behavior of people and the actions of objects. Specifically, children:

- ***Have a "theory of mind."*** Babies as young as 14 months old who see an adult struggling to reach for an object will interrupt their play to crawl over and hand the object to the adult. In the presence of a stranger, they look at their mothers to determine if the person is benign or dangerous.
- ***Have theories of numbers.*** Babies, as old as six months, are capable of intuitively understanding difference in magnitudes such as "4 and 8" and "16 and 32".
- ***Can make inferences about cause and effect.*** Young children can experience observations and learning that allow them to conclude that a particular factor X causes (or prevents) an effect Y.
- ***Are sensitive to the statistical probability of events.*** In one set of studies, for example, 11-month-old can look at a set of objects and express surprise if the impossible probabilistic outcome is shown to them.
- ***Are sensitive to teaching cues.*** When adults make eye contact, call a baby's name, and point for the baby's benefit, these signals lead babies to recognize that someone is teaching them, and this awareness can affect how and what they learn.

This new and growing neuroscience data dismisses the old conception that children are basically concrete learners who cannot understand abstract ideas such as "freedom, equality, and democracy". In other words, studies from the Scandinavian countries tell us that it is fairly appropriate to start teaching democratic values to children from the age of three. To this end, the ACDEG program shall start at pre-primary where children from 3 to 6 old shall be invested in democratic knowledge, skills, dispositions, and tools to become transformational leaders.

Key Stage 1 is the part of the DGC Curriculum that covers children between the ages of 6 and 8 in Years 1 and 2, and sets out which content have to be taught. It also determines how children should be tested. During key stage 1 pupils learn about themselves as developing individuals and as members of their communities, building on their own experiences and on the early learning goals for personal, social and emotional development. More importantly, they learn about their individual identity, their communal identity, and their duties and responsibilities towards their community and nation.

Key Stage 2 is the part of the DGC Curriculum that covers children between the ages of 8 and 12 in Years 3, 4, 5 and 6, and sets out which content have to be taught. During key stage 2 pupils learn about themselves as growing and changing individuals with their own experiences and ideas, and as members of their communities. They become more mature, independent and self-confident. They learn about the wider world and the interdependence of communities within it. They develop their sense of social justice and moral responsibility and begin to understand that their own choices and behavior can affect local, national or global issues and political and social institutions. They learn how to take part more fully in school and community activities.

Key Stage 3 is the part of the DGC Curriculum that covers learners between the ages of 12 and 15 in Years 7, 8 and 9, and sets out which content have to be taught. During key stage 3 learners are expected to use and apply their knowledge and understanding whilst developing skills to research and interrogate evidence, debate and evaluate viewpoints, present reasoned arguments and take informed action.

Key Stage 4 is the part of the DGC Curriculum that covers learners between the ages of 15 and 18 in Years 10, 11 and 12, and sets out which content have to be taught. During key stage 3 learners are expected to use a range of research strategies, weigh up evidence, make persuasive arguments and substantiate their conclusions. They should experience and evaluate different ways that citizens can act together to solve problems and contribute to society.

Key Stage 5A is the part of the DGC Curriculum that covers learners between the ages of 18 and 20 in Year 13 and sets out which content have to be taught. During key stage 5A learners are expected to show maturity in of all DGC standards, Integrate DGC values into personal awareness and behaviors, participation in civic organizations, fulfilling civic responsibilities, and take part in community services and actions. For some African countries, Key stage 5A marks the beginning of first year in tertiary education. And for others countries, it is the last stage of secondary education, and it is also the period when Advance levels (AL) are achieved so that students will be able to apply for university. The AL examination is set by the National Examination Board of member state in partnership with the African Union. Results of examinations at this age are published in the public sphere.

Key Stage 5B is the part of the DGC Curriculum that covers learners between the ages of 20 and 23 in Year 1, 2, and 3 of Tertiary Education, and sets out which content have to be taught. During key stage 5B learners are expected produce works (which might be books) related to Human rights, Anti-Corruption, Peaceful Co-Existence, and Accountability in Public Services.

Note: Key stage 5A and 5B collectively make up key stage 5 which is a four years program that can be taught for the entire tertiary period. However, at least, the AU priority is that first year tertiary students are taught the DGC curriculum.

Table 3.4.2: Key Stages

Age	Year	Key Stage	Assessment
3 to 4	Reception	Early years	
4 to 5	Reception	Early years	
6 to 7	Year 1	KS1	
7 to 8	Year 2	KS1	Basic DGC values check – Patriotism, Respect, and Tolerance.
8 to 9	Year 3	KS2	
9 to 10	Year 4	KS2	
10 to 11	Year 5	KS2	
11 to 12	Year 6	KS2	National tests and teacher assessment in Democracy and Good Citizenship (DGC)
12 to 13	Year 7	KS3	
13 to 14	Year 8	KS3	
14 to 15	Year 9	KS3	
15 to 16	Year 10	KS4	
16 to 17	Year 11	KS4	Some learners take national qualification exam
17 to 18	Year 12	KS4	Most learners take national qualifications
18 to 19	Year 13	KS5A	Most learners take AL exam
19 to 20	Year 14	KS5B	Semester Exam
20 to 21	Year 15	KS5B	Semester Exam
21 to 23	Year 16	KS5B	Semester Exam

Table 3.4.2.1: Early Years (ECD) Framework

Age	Strand	Content	Values	Pedagogical Approaches	Learning Style	Developmental Gains
3 to 4	Democracy and Human Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamental rights and freedoms • Children’s rights • Women’s rights • Citizenship 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Honesty • Empathy • Solidarity • Diversity • Trustfulness • Listening • Freedom • Rights and Obligations • Responsibility • Equality • Equity • Participation • Justice • Confidence • Cooperation • Self autonomy • Self-identity • Integrity • Self-esteem • Teamwork 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Song (pictures and objects) • Game (pictures and objects) • HOD (tell stories with pictures and objects) • Drama (pictures and objects) • PBL 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kinesthetic • Auditory • Visual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motto Skills: walking, climbing, jumping, hopping, crawling, skipping, running, throwing and catching, neck and eyes movement • Social-Emotional skills: positive self-identity and self-esteem; trust and respect others and get along with them; respect the environment; honest and treat others equally and with equity; exploring transformational leadership dispositions, actively participate in group activities and complete tasks; developing capacity to do things independently, self control; able to clearly express their feeling; and developing love for lifelong learning • Cognitive skills: Describe and explain their rights and responsibilities; share their ideas and interests with others; listen and respond to others appropriately; concentrate and solve problems; are patient, curious and creative; aiming high; and express themselves with drawing and writing. • Moral Skills: Fairness, sharing, caring, compromising, trustworthy, respectful, honest, speaking out for others, and shunning unacceptable behaviors.

<p>4 to 5 (5 to 6)</p>	<p>Culture and Peace (Democracy and Human Rights)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity • Peaceful coexistence • Peaceful Resolution of Disputes • Community Service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Honesty • Empathy • Solidarity • Diversity • Trustfulness • Listening • Freedom • Rights and Obligations • Responsibility • Equality • Equity • Participation • Justice • Confidence • Cooperation • Self autonomy • Self-identity • Integrity • Self-esteem • Teamwork 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Song <i>(pictures and objects)</i> • Game <i>(pictures and objects)</i> • HOD (tell stories with pictures and objects) • Drama <i>(pictures and objects)</i> • PBL 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kinesthetic • Auditory • Visual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motto Skills: walking, climbing, jumping, hopping, crawling, skipping, running, throwing and catching, neck and eyes movement • Social-Emotional skills: positive self-identity and self-esteem; trust and respect others and get along with them; respect the environment; honest and treat others equally and with equity; exploring transformational leadership dispositions, actively participate in group activities and complete tasks; developing capacity to do things independently, self control; able to clearly express their feeling; and developing love for lifelong learning • Cognitive skills: Describe and explain their rights and responsibilities; share their ideas and interests with others; listen and respond to others appropriately; concentrate and solve problems; are patient, curious and creative; aiming high; and express themselves with drawing and writing. • Moral Skills: Fairness, sharing, caring, compromising, trustworthy, respectful, honest, speaking out for others, and shunning unacceptable behaviors.
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3.4.3 Thematic division and suggested pedagogical approaches

Table 3.4.3: Thematic division and suggested pedagogical approaches

Level	Key stage	Thematic division	pedagogical approaches		
Primary School	Key stage 1	• Constitutionalism and the rule of law	Songs	Game	Drama
		• Democracy and human rights	HOD	QQ	PBL
	Key stage 2	• Elections and electoral processes	Game	HOD	Songs
		• Governance institutions	QQ	Drama	HOD
		• Political, economic and social issues	PBL	Drama	Game
	• Culture and peace	Songs	QQ	PBL	
Middle School	Key stage 3	• Constitutionalism and the rule of law	Songs	Game	PBL
		• Democracy and human rights	QQ	Drama	HOD
		• Governance institutions	PBL	Songs	Game
		• Culture and peace	HOD	QQ	Drama
		• Elections and electoral processes	Drama	HOD	Songs
		• Political, economic and social issues	Game	PBL	QQ
High School	Key stage 4	• Constitutionalism and the rule of law	QQ	Drama	HOD
		• Democracy and human rights	Songs	Game	PBL
		• Governance institutions	HOD	Drama	QQ
		• Culture and peace	PBL	Songs	Game
		• Elections and electoral processes	HOD	PBL	QQ
		• Political, economic and social issues	Drama	Game	Songs
AL Stage	Key stage 5A	• Constitutionalism and the rule of law	HOD	PBL	QQ
		• Democracy and human rights	Drama	HOD	Songs
		• Governance institutions	HOD	PBL	QQ
		• Culture and peace	HOD	Songs	Drama
		• Elections and electoral processes	QQ	Drama	HOD
		• Political, economic and social issues	Songs	HOD	PBL
Tertiary School	Key stage 5B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constitutionalism and Rule of Law, Democracy and Human Rights, Culture and Peace • Government Institutions; Elections and Electoral Processes; Political, economic and social issues 	HOD, QQ, Drama, Song, PBL		

4.4.3 Thematic content per academic term

Key stage 1

Table 3.4.3.1: Thematic content per academic term

Level	Year	Thematic content	Term	
Primary School	Year 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supremacy of the constitution 	First term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizenship 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equality before the law 	Second term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamental rights and freedoms 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children’s rights 	Third term		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women’s rights 			
	Year 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supremacy of the constitution 	First term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children’s rights 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political system 	Second term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental rights 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freedom of expression and media 	Third term			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Democratic culture and practice 				

NOTE: the key concepts per term can be presented in any given order, not necessary as it appears on the table.

Key stage 2 (Table 3.4.3.2: Thematic content per academic term)

Level	Year	Thematic content	Term	
Primary School	Year 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electoral policy/ Legal Framework and Electoral Procedures 	First term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens' Choice of Leader/Representation Peaceful Resolution of Disputes 	Second term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating corruption Accountability and Efficiency in Service 	Third term	
		Year 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender equality and Women Participation in Electoral Processes 	First term
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roles of governance institutions Communal Collective Responsibility and Role of trade institutions 	Second term
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social and Economic transformation , Combating corruption Accountability and Efficiency in Service 		Third term	
	Year 5		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity and Minority Rights 	First term
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human Security and Civic duties/ Responsibilities 	Second term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political parties, Combating corruption Accountability and Efficiency in Service 	Third term	
	Year 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traditional Institutions and Governance, and Political parties 	First term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civic responsibilities and Citizens' Participation 	Second term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community Service; Public service and governance 	Third term	

Key stage 3 Table 3.4.3.3: Thematic content per academic term

Level	Year	Thematic content	Term
Middle School	Year 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electoral policy/ Legal Framework and Electoral Procedures 	First term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women Participation in Electoral Processes 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building Judicial Institutions 	Second term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civilian Control/Oversight of the Military 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unconstitutional Change of Government 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supremacy of the constitution 	Third term
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating corruption and Accountability and Efficiency in Service 		
	Year 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizenship 	First term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political Systems and Separation of Power 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fundamental rights and freedoms; Freedom of expression and media 	Second term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Democratic culture and practice 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social and Economic transformation 	Third term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating corruption and Accountability and Efficiency in Service 	
	Year 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity 	First term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minority Rights and Women’s rights 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children’s rights 	Second term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental rights 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equality before the Law 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public service and governance 	Third term
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating corruption and Accountability and Efficiency in Service 		

Key stage 4 (Table 3.4.3.4: Thematic content per academic term)

Level	Year	Thematic content	Term
High School	Year 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens' Choice of Leader/Representation 	First term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peaceful Resolution of Disputes 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communal Collective Responsibility 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roles of governance institutions 	Second term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional Institutions and Governance 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building Judicial Institutions 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens' Choice of Leader/Representation 	Third term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civilian Control/Oversight of the Military 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unconstitutional Change of Government 	
	Year 11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supremacy of the constitution 	First term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political system 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civic responsibilities/ Participation 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity 	Second term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender equality 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freedom of expression and media 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of trade institutions/ authorities 	Third term
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combating corruption 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accountability and Efficiency in Service 	
Year 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizenship and Diversity 	First term	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political System and Separation of Power and Women's Rights 	Second term	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social and Economic transformation and Combating Corruption 	Third term	

Key stage 5 (Table 3.4.3.5: Thematic content per academic term)

Level	Year	Thematic content	Term		
5A <i>(Final Year in High School OR First Year Tertiary Education)</i>	Year 13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political Systems 	First term		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political parties 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens' Choice of Leader/Representation 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizenship 	Second term		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fundamental rights and freedoms 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community Service 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roles of governance institutions 	Third term		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating corruption 					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accountability and Efficiency in Service 					
5B <i>(Second to Fourth Year Tertiary Education)</i>	Year 14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supremacy of the constitution 	First term		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electoral policy/ Legal Framework 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electoral Procedures 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity 	Second term		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender equality 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Freedom of expression and media 			
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public service and governance 	Third term		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating corruption 					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accountability and Efficiency in Service 					

Level	Year	Thematic content	Term	
5B <i>(Second to Fourth Year Tertiary Education)</i>	Year 15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supremacy of the constitution 	First term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Political parties 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens' Choice of Leader/Representation 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women's rights 	Second term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fundamental rights and freedoms 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Democratic Culture and Practice 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roles of governance institutions 	Third term	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public service and governance 			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Role of trade institutions/authorities 			
	Year 16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electoral policy/ Legal Framework 	First term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electoral Procedures 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women Participation in Electoral Processes 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity 	Second term	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peaceful Resolution of Disputes 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community service 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender equality 		Third term		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combating corruption 				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accountability and Efficiency in Service 				

Note: The curriculum arrangement presented here is simply a sample rubric that the learning hubs in each member state will use to build a stronger and superior curriculum.

3.4.4: Developmental and Conceptual framework for the DGC (Table 3.4.4: Developmental and Conceptual framework for the DGC)

DEVELOPMENTAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR CONSTITUTIONALISM AND THE RULE OF LAW; DEMOCRACY AND HUMAN RIGHTS; CULTURE AND PEACE; GOVERNANCE INSTITUTIONS; ELECTION AND ELECTORAL PROCESSES; POLITICAL, ECONOMIC, AND SOCIAL ISSUES						
LEVELS	GOALS	OBJECTIVES	KEY CONCEPTS	PRACTICES (VALUES)	SPECIFIC CIVIC PROBLEMS	EDUCATION STANDARDS & INSTRUMENTS
Key Stage 1 Ages 6 to 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bringing out the best in each other (By the year 2030, all Africans will exhibit the best qualities in democracy, election and governance) • Empowering Women, Children, and Minorities to enrich and transform their communities (By the year 2030, Women will transform Africa into global power house, Minority groups will become transformational citizens, and children will carry within them the seeds of best democracy, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners know who they are, they love who they are, and respect classmates for who they are: mutual respect • Learners demonstrate active and responsible citizenship based on an understanding of the roles, rights and responsibilities of individuals and groups, the importance of social justice, supremacy of the constitution, and concern for local, national and global issues, and a respect for all of these, including freedom of the press and media. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self –identity • Self-esteem • Family • Community • Constitution • Elections • Rule of Law • Rights, Limits and Responsibilities • Equity and Equality • Respect • Justice • Inclusiveness • Transparency • Accountability • Participation • Children rights • Women rights • Freedom of Speech • Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle • Save 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Love one’s self • Love others • Mutual respect • Listening • Openness • Tolerance • Solidarity • Hospitality • Acceptance • Sharing and Fairness • Valuing diversity • NO to violence • NO to vote rigging • NO to corruption • Respect for properties, goods and services • Compliance with the Rule of Law • Decency and Civility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor self-esteem • Children socializing each other • Hurting others’ feelings • Discrimination and prejudice • Abuse and exploitation of Women and Children • Violent conflicts • Corruption • Poor Saving culture • Environmental degradation • Press and Media repression • Poor land rights for women • Energy crises • Racism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classroom rules • School rules • Family life • Community standards • Convention on Cultural Rights • Convention on the Rights of the Child • Convention on the Rights of Women • World Bank • FAO • National Constitution

	<p>election and governance)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transforming Public and Trade institutions into extraordinary systems that reliably exceed expectations (By the year 2030, public and trade institutions in Africa will serve as molds for extraordinary institutions that reliably exceed expectations) • Ensuring best electoral and political practices (By the year 2030, the electoral and political system in Africa will be referenced for best democratic, electoral and governance practices) • Eradicating Hunger, poverty and Corruption (By the year 2030, there will be zero hunger and zero poverty in Africa) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners identify key actions and build awareness on policies and innovations that will accelerate women's, children's, and minorities' empowerment that have real impact on the quality of life of their community and nation • Learners develop an understanding of external and internal economic influences on political systems and outcomes, mobilize policies to improve campaign finance law, actively adopt early saving dispositions, and participation in transformational economic activities, in order to transform their communities, nation, and the world at large. • Learners develop a healthy and peaceful 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peace • Vote • Security • Love • Sharing • Empathy • Openness • Acceptance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patriotism • participation • Accountability • Transparency • Dignity • Gender Equity and Equality • Self expression • Freedom of speech (Press and Media) • Caring for the environment • Saving to invest • Voting to improve • Peaceful coexistence 		
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Silencing the guns</i> (By the year 2030, all African countries will be free of conflicts, terrorism, and piracy) • <i>Getting better at environmental care and protection</i> (By the year 2030, Africa will have a healthy and productive balance between economic development and environmental sustainability) • <i>Providing Peace Justice and Security for All</i> (By the year 2030, Africa will become the cradle of peace, justice and security for all humanity) • <i>Zeroing down on illegal migration</i> (By the year 2030, there will be zero illegal migration in Africa) 	<p>lifestyle, understand Peacekeeping and Peacemaking in the light of coups d'états, civil war, terrorism, piracy, and tribal conflicts, employ initiatives to curb illegal migration, and actively participate in Peace building programs that would ensure security and justice for all</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners are equipped with the disposition and tools to ensure efficiency in public services, optimal use of resources, practice inclusive leadership, identify and eradicate corruption. • Learners appreciate the interaction between human beings and the environment in terms of the processes and patterns of natural and human features, in different places, and 				
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distinguishing wants from needs from rights (By the year 2030, Africans will champion the rights of all humanity, and the rights of the planet Earth) • Integration of ACDEG values into personal awareness and behaviors (By the year 2030, the behavior of all Africans will be an embodiment of the ACDEG values) 	<p>participate in sustaining, conserving and improving the environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners can identify, describe, analyze, evaluate (social, political and economic issues) and defend positions with appropriate evidence and careful reasoning. They can also interact, monitor, and influence political system in ways that exceed expectations. 				
Key Stage 2 Ages 8 to 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bringing out the best in each other (By the year 2030, all Africans will exhibit the best qualities in democracy, election and governance) • Empowering Women, Children, and Minorities to enrich and transform their 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners appreciate the characteristics and values of their own culture and the influences of culture on human life, and develop a respect for the culture and heritage of other communities: they love who they are, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self • Family • Community • Rule of Law • Check and Balances • Rights, limits, and responsibilities • Elections • Security • Contract • Representation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NO to violence • NO to election rigging • NO to corruption • Informed citizen • Active participation • Empathy • Civility • Decency • Accountability • Transparency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coups d'états • Terrorism • Xenophobia • Unpatriotic citizens • Violent conflicts • Illegal migration • Dismal state of Press Freedom • Political repression • Abuse of power and term limits. • Entrenched leaders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classroom rules • School rules • Family life • Community standards • Convention on the Rights of the Child • Convention on the Rights of Women

	<p><i>communities</i> (By the year 2030, Women will transform Africa into global power house, Minority groups will become transformational citizens, and children will carry within them the seeds of best democracy, election and governance)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transforming Public and Trade institutions into extraordinary systems that reliably exceed expectations (By the year 2030, public and trade institutions in Africa will serve as molds for extraordinary institutions that reliably exceed expectations) • Ensuring best electoral and political practices (By the year 2030, the electoral and political system in Africa will be 	<p>love others for who they are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners demonstrate active and responsible citizenship based on an understanding of the roles, rights and responsibilities of individuals and groups, the importance of social justice, supremacy of the constitution, and concern for local, national and global issues, and a respect for all of these, including freedom of the press and media. • Learners identify key actions and build awareness on policies and innovations that will accelerate women's, children's, and minorities' empowerment that have real impact on the quality of life of their community and nation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusiveness • Open, regular, free and fair • Constitution • Amendment • Consensus • Equity and Equality • Respect • Transparency • Tolerance • Accountability • Children rights • Women rights • Minority rights • Freedom of Speech • Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle • Justice • Save • Peace • Love • Vote • Acceptance • Land rights • Government • Democracy • Corruption • Conflict • Refugees • manifesto • World peace • Empathy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency • Fairness • Hospitality • Tolerance • Dignity • Self expression • Listening • Responsiveness • Consensus oriented • Gender Equity and Equality • Equality before the law • Inclusiveness • Open, regular, free and fair elections • Independent and impartial judiciary • Rule of Law • Freedom of speech (Press and Media) • Absence of Corruption • Mutual respect • Saving to invest • Voting to improve • Accept elections results • Willingness to learn about others' points of view and comprise 	<p>blocking reform that would curb permissive constitutional arrangements and strengthen institutional checks and balances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak Human Rights mechanism • Gross abuse and exploitation of Women and Children • Cosmetic free judiciaries • Poor participation in electoral processes • Racism • Sexism • Poverty and Hunger • Injustice • Ethnocentrism • Passivity • Ignorance • Apathy • Cynicism • Cultural dissonance • Colonialism and imperialism • Refugees • Migration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights • Convention on Cultural Rights • UDHR • History of human rights • Local, national legal systems • Local and national history in human rights terms • UNESCO, UNICEF • World Bank • FAO • Freedom House • National Constitution • UN Covenants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elimination of racism
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	<p>referenced for best democratic, electoral and governance practices)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Eradicating Hunger, poverty and Corruption</i> (By the year 2030, there will be zero hunger and zero poverty in Africa) • <i>Silencing the guns</i> (By the year 2030, all African countries will be free of conflicts, terrorism, and piracy) • <i>Getting better at environmental care and protection</i> (By the year 2030, Africa will have a healthy and productive balance between economic development and environmental sustainability) • <i>Providing Peace Justice and</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners develop an understanding of external and internal economic influences on political systems and outcomes, mobilize policies to improve campaign finance law, actively adopt early saving dispositions, and participation in transformational economic activities, in order to transform their communities, nation, and the world at large. • Learners develop a healthy and peaceful lifestyle, understand Peacekeeping and Peacemaking in the light of coups d'états, civil war, terrorism, piracy, and tribal conflicts, employ initiatives to curb illegal migration, and actively participate in Peace building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing • Openness • Participation • Integrity • Tradition • Custom • Campaign • Entrepreneur • Positive Leadership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peaceful coexistence • Legal, transparent, and equitable land administration and management • Protecting women and children from abuse and exploitation • Peaceful protests • Respect for properties, goods, and services • Respect for Human rights and life • Peaceful resolution of conflicts • Curbing illegal migration • Reducing, Reusing, and Recycling • Valuing diversity • Distinguishing between fact and opinion • Citing evidence in support of ideas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gross Corruption: Africa annually loses over \$50 billion through illicit flows and \$148 billion through corruption. One in four people in Africa paid bribes for public services. • Poor Saving culture • Environmental degradation • Gross lack of transparency, integrity, and accountability in public offices • Fire fighting strategies and policies • Agriculture is 2-4 times more potent than any other sector in reducing poverty in Africa. More than 60% of those who till the soil are women but their effort to improve the sector has come up against three major 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elimination of sexism • Regional human rights conventions • UNHCR • NGOs • Geneva Conventions • Specialized conventions • Evolving human rights standards • ACDEG Charter • IFES • IDEA • FISA • INE • ACE
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	<p>Security for All (By the year 2030, Africa will become the cradle of peace, justice and security for all humanity)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zeroing down on illegal migration (By the year 2030, there will be zero illegal migration in Africa) • Distinguishing wants from needs from rights (By the year 2030, Africans will champion the rights of all humanity, and the rights of the planet Earth) • Integration of ACDEG values into personal awareness and behaviors (By the year 2030, the behavior of all Africans will be an embodiment of the ACDEG values) 	<p>programs that would ensure security and justice for all</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners are equipped with the disposition and tools to ensure efficiency in public services, optimal use of resources, practice inclusive leadership, identify and eradicate corruption. • Learners appreciate the interaction between human beings and the environment in terms of the processes and patterns of natural and human features, in different places, and participate in sustaining, conserving and improving the environment • Learners can identify, describe, analyze, evaluate (social, political and economic issues) and defend positions with appropriate evidence 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doing research/gathering information and creating artefacts • Sharing information • Performing school and community service • Participating in civic organizations • Love • Sharing • Shunning violence • Devolution of power and resources • Servant of the demos, not master • Great 4Cs Skills 	<p>constraints: (1)Lack of land rights, (2) Lack of access to input, (3) Lack of right over final product</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor self-esteem • Children socializing each other • Foreign aid dependency syndrome • Reduction in foreign investment • Western nation have retreated from emphasizing democratic governance principles in their development assistance programs (in favor of geostrategic interests such as competing against China, stemming migration, and fighting terrorism). 	
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		and careful reasoning They can also interact, monitor, and influence political system in ways that exceed expectations.			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • China’s “Ask No Questions” policies in Africa • Economic globalization 	
Key Stage 3 Age 12 to 15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Bringing out the best in each other</i> (By the year 2030, all Africans will exhibit the best qualities in democracy, election and governance) • <i>Empowering Women, Children, and Minorities to enrich and transform their communities</i> (By the year 2030, Women will transform Africa into global power house, Minority groups will become transformational citizens, and children will carry within them the seeds of best democracy, election and governance) • <i>Transforming Public and Trade institutions into</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners appreciate the characteristics and values of their own culture and the influences of culture on human life, and develop a respect for the culture and heritage of other communities: they love who they are, and love others for who they are • Learners demonstrate active and responsible citizenship based on an understanding of the roles, rights and responsibilities of individuals and groups, the importance of social justice, supremacy of the constitution, and concern for local, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self • Family • Community • Rule of Law • Check and Balances • Rights, limits, and responsibilities • Elections • Security • Contract • Representation • Inclusiveness • Open, regular, free and fair • Constitution • Amendment • Consensus • Equity and Equality • Respect • Transparency • Tolerance • Accountability • Children rights • Women rights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civility • Accountability • Transparency • Efficiency • Responsiveness • Consensus oriented • Gender Equity and Equality • Inclusiveness • Open, regular, free and fair elections • Independent and impartial judiciary • Rule of Law • Freedom of speech (Press and Media) • Absence of Corruption • Mutual respect • Saving to invest • Voting to improve • Accept elections results • Peaceful coexistence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coups d’états • Terrorism • Civil wars • Illegal migration • Dismal state of Press Freedom • Political repression • Energy crises • Unpatriotic citizens • Abuse of power and term limits. Entrenched leaders blocking reform that would curb permissive constitutional arrangements and strengthen institutional checks and balances • Weak Human Rights mechanism • Gross abuse and exploitation of Women and Children 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classroom rules • School rules • Family life • Community standards • Convention on the Rights of the Child • UDHR • History of human rights • Local, national legal systems • Local and national history in human rights terms • UNESCO, UNICEF • World Bank • FAO

	<p><i>extraordinary systems that reliably exceed expectations</i> (By the year 2030, public and trade institutions in Africa will serve as molds for extraordinary institutions that reliably exceed expectations)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring best electoral and political practices (By the year 2030, the electoral and political system in Africa will be referenced for best democratic, electoral and governance practices) • Eradicating Hunger, poverty and Corruption (By the year 2030, there will be zero hunger and zero poverty in Africa) • Silencing the guns (By the year 2030, all African countries will be free of conflicts, 	<p>national and global issues, and a respect for all of these, including freedom of the press and media.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners identify key actions and build awareness on policies and innovations that will accelerate women’s, children’s, and minorities’ empowerment that have real impact on the quality of life of their community and nation • Learners develop an understanding of external and internal economic influences on political systems and outcomes, mobilize policies to improve campaign finance law, actively adopt early saving dispositions, and participation in transformational economic activities, in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minority rights • Freedom of Speech • Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle • Justice • Save • Peace • Love • Vote • Acceptance • Land rights • Government • Democracy • Corruption • Conflict • Refugees • manifesto • World peace • Empathy • Sharing • Openness • Participation • Integrity • Tradition • Custom • Campaign • Entrepreneur • Positive Leadership • International law • Legal Rights • Moral Rights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal, transparent, and equitable land administration and management • Protecting women and children from abuse and exploitation • Peaceful protests • Peaceful resolution of conflicts • Curbing Illegal Migration • Reducing, Reusing, and Recycling • Citing evidence in support of ideas • Doing research/gathering information and creating artifacts • Sharing information • Community service and action • Love • Sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cosmetic free judiciaries • Poor participation in electoral processes • Racism • Sexism • Poverty and Hunger • Injustice • Ethnocentrism • Passivity • Economic Globalization • Ignorance • Apathy • Cynicism • Cultural dissonance • Colonialism and imperialism • Gross Corruption: Africa annually loses over \$50 billion through illicit flows and \$148 billion through corruption. 1 in 4 people in Africa paid bribes for public services. • Poor Saving culture • Environmental degradation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freedom House • UN Covenants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elimination of racism • Elimination of sexism • Regional human rights conventions • UNHCR • NGOs • ACDEG Charter • IFES • IDEA • FISA • INE • ACE • National Constitution
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	<p>terrorism, and piracy)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Getting better at environmental care and protection (By the year 2030, Africa will have a healthy and productive balance between economic development and environmental sustainability) • Providing Peace Justice and Security for All (By the year 2030, Africa will become the cradle of peace, justice and security for all humanity) • Zeroing down on illegal migration (By the year 2030, there will be zero illegal migration in Africa) • Distinguishing wants from needs from rights (By the year 2030, Africans will champion the rights of all 	<p>order to transform their communities, nation, and the world at large.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners develop a healthy and peaceful lifestyle, understand Peacekeeping and Peacemaking in the light of coups d'états, civil war, terrorism, piracy, and tribal conflicts, employ initiatives to curb illegal migration, and actively participate in Peace building programs that would ensure security and justice for all • Learners are equipped with the disposition and tools to ensure efficiency in public services, optimal use of resources, practice inclusive leadership, identify and eradicate corruption. • Learners appreciate the interaction 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shunning violence • Devolution of power and resources • Servant of the demos, not master • Great 4Cs Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gross lack of transparency, integrity, and accountability in public offices • Security agencies' dedication to the survival of governments in power rather than the safety and security of citizens • Agriculture is 2-4 times more potent than any other sector in reducing poverty in Africa. More than 60% of those who till the soil are women but their effort to improve the sector has come up against three major constraints: (1)Lack of land rights, (2) Lack of access to input, (3) Lack of right over final product • Torture and Genocide 	
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	<p>humanity, and the rights of the planet Earth)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Integration of ACDEG values into personal awareness and behaviors</i> (By the year 2030, the behavior of all Africans will be an embodiment of the ACDEG values) 	<p>between human beings and the environment in terms of the processes and patterns of natural and human features, in different places, and participate in sustaining, conserving and improving the environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners can identify, describe, analyze, evaluate (social, political and economic issues) and defend positions with appropriate evidence and careful reasoning. They can also interact, monitor, and influence political system in ways that exceed expectations. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor self-esteem • Children socializing each other • Foreign aid dependency syndrome • Reduction in foreign investment • Western nation have retreated from emphasizing democratic governance principles in their development assistance programs (in favor of geostrategic interests such as competing against China, stemming migration, and fighting terrorism). • China’s “Ask No Questions” policies in Africa • Economic globalization • Fire fighting strategies and policies 	
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<p>Key Stage 4 Age 15 to 18</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Bringing out the best in each other</i> (By the year 2030, all Africans will exhibit the best qualities in democracy, election and governance) • <i>Empowering Women, Children, and Minorities to enrich and transform their communities</i> (By the year 2030, Women will transform Africa into global power house, Minority groups will become transformational citizens, and children will carry within them the seeds of best democracy, election and governance) • <i>Transforming Public and Trade institutions into extraordinary systems that reliably exceed expectations</i> (By the year 2030, public and trade institutions in Africa will serve as molds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners appreciate the characteristics and values of their own culture and the influences of culture on human life, and develop a respect for the culture and heritage of other communities: they love who they are, and love others for who they are • Learners demonstrate active and responsible citizenship based on an understanding of the roles, rights and responsibilities of individuals and groups, the importance of social justice, supremacy of the constitution, and concern for local, national and global issues, and a respect for all of these, including freedom of the press and media. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self • Family • Community • Rule of Law • Check and Balances • Rights, limits, and responsibilities • Elections • Security • Contract • Representation • Inclusiveness • Open, regular, free and fair • Constitution • Amendment • Consensus • Equity and Equality • Respect • Transparency • Tolerance • Accountability • Children rights • Women rights • Minority rights • Freedom of Speech • Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle • Justice • Save • Peace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civility • Accountability • Transparency • Efficiency • Responsiveness • Consensus oriented • Gender Equity and Equality • Inclusiveness • Regular, free and fair elections • Independent and impartial judiciary • Rule of Law • Freedom of speech (Press and Media) • Absence of Corruption • Mutual respect • Saving to invest • Voting • Accept elections results • Peaceful coexistence • Legal, transparent, and equitable land administration and management • Protecting women and children from 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coups d'états • Terrorism • Violent conflicts • Illegal migration • Dismal state of Press Freedom • Political repression • Energy crises • Unpatriotic citizens • Abuse of power and term limits. Entrenched leaders blocking reform that would curb permissive constitutional arrangements and strengthen institutional checks and balances • Weak Human Rights mechanism • Gross abuse and exploitation of Women and Children • Cosmetic free judiciaries • Poor participation in electoral processes • Racism and Sexism • Poverty/Hunger 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classroom rules • School rules • Family life • Community standards • Convention on the Rights of the Child • UDHR • History of human rights • Local, national legal systems • Local and national history in human rights terms • UNESCO, UNICEF • World Bank • FAO • Freedom House • UN Covenants • Elimination of racism • Elimination
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	<p>for extraordinary institutions that reliably exceed expectations)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring best electoral and political practices (By the year 2030, the electoral and political system in Africa will be referenced for best democratic, electoral and governance practices) • Eradicating Hunger, poverty and Corruption (By the year 2030, there will be zero hunger and zero poverty in Africa) • Silencing the guns (By the year 2030, all African countries will be free of conflicts, terrorism, and piracy) • Getting better at environmental care and protection (By the year 2030, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners identify key actions and build awareness on policies and innovations that will accelerate women's, children's, and minorities' empowerment that have real impact on the quality of life of their community and nation • Learners develop an understanding of external and internal economic influences on political systems and outcomes, mobilize policies to improve campaign finance law, actively adopt early saving dispositions, and participation in transformational economic activities, in order to transform their communities, nation, and the world at large. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Love • Vote • Acceptance • Land rights • Government • Democracy • Corruption • Conflict • Refugees • manifesto • World peace • Empathy • Sharing • Openness • Participation • Integrity • Tradition • Custom • Campaign • Entrepreneur • Positive Leadership • International law • Legal Rights • Moral Rights 	<p>abuse and exploitation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peaceful protests • Peaceful resolution of conflicts • Curbing Illegal Migration • Reduce, Re-use, and Recycle • Citing evidence in support of ideas • Doing research/gathering information and creating artifacts • Sharing information • Community service and action • Devolution of power and resources • Servant of the demos, not master • Great 4Cs Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil wars • Cultural dissonance • Ethnocentrism • Passivity • Machiavelism • Ignorance • Apathy • Cynicism • Colonialism and imperialism • Gross Corruption: Africa annually loses over \$50 billion through illicit flows and \$148 billion through corruption. 1 in 4 people in Africa paid bribes for public services. • Poor Saving culture • Environmental degradation • Gross lack of transparency, integrity, and accountability in public offices • Agriculture is 2-4 times more potent than any other sector in reducing poverty 	<p>of sexism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional human rights conventions • UNHCR • NGOs • Geneva Conventions • Specialized conventions • Evolving human rights standards • ACDEG Charter • IFES • IDEA • FISA • INE • ACE
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<p>Africa will have a healthy and productive balance between economic development and environmental sustainability)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing Peace Justice and Security for All (By the year 2030, Africa will become the cradle of peace, justice and security for all humanity) • Zeroing down on illegal migration (By the year 2030, there will be zero illegal migration in Africa) • Distinguishing wants from needs from rights (By the year 2030, Africans will champion the rights of all humanity, and the rights of the planet Earth) • Integration of ACDEG values into personal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners develop a healthy and peaceful lifestyle, understand Peacekeeping and Peacemaking in the light of coups d'états, civil war, terrorism, piracy, and tribal conflicts, employ initiatives to curb illegal migration, and actively participate in Peace building programs that would ensure security and justice for all • Learners are equipped with the disposition and tools to ensure efficiency in public services, optimal use of resources, practice inclusive leadership, identify and eradicate corruption. • Learners appreciate the interaction between human beings and the environment in terms of the processes and 			<p>in Africa. More than 60% of those who till the soil are women but their effort to improve the sector has come up against three major constrains: (1)Lack of land rights, (2) Lack of access to input, (3) Lack of right over final product</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Torture and Genocide • Poor self-esteem • Children socializing each other • Foreign aid dependency syndrome • Reduction in foreign investment • Western nation have retreated from emphasizing democratic governance principles in their development assistance programs 	
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	<p>awareness and behaviors (By the year 2030, the behavior of all Africans will be an embodiment of the ACDEG values)</p>	<p>patterns of natural and human features, in different places, and participate in sustaining, conserving and improving the environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learners can identify, describe, analyze, evaluate (social, political and economic issues) and defend positions with appropriate evidence and careful reasoning They can also interact, monitor, and influence political system in ways that exceed expectations. 			<p>(in favor of geostrategic interests such as competing against China, stemming migration, and fighting terrorism).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> China’s “Ask No Questions” policies in Africa Economic globalization Fire fighting strategies and policies Refugees Migration 	
<p>Key Stage 5 (A and B) Age 18 to 23</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bringing out the best in each other (By the year 2030, all Africans will exhibit the best qualities in democracy, election and governance) Empowering Women, Children, and Minorities to enrich and transform their communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learners appreciate the characteristics and values of their own culture and the influences of culture on human life, and develop a respect for the culture and heritage of other communities: they love who they are, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self Family Community Rule of Law Check and Balances Rights, limits, and responsibilities Elections Security Contract 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civility Accountability Transparency Efficiency Responsiveness Consensus oriented Gender Equity and Equality Inclusiveness Regular, free and fair elections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coups d’états Terrorism Civil wars Illegal migration Dismal state of Press Freedom Political repression Abuse of power and term limits. Entrenched leaders blocking reform that 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classroom rules School rules Family life Community standards Convention on the Rights of the Child UDHR

	<p>(By the year 2030, Women will transform Africa into global power house, Minority groups will become transformational citizens, and children will carry within them the seeds of best democracy, election and governance)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transforming Public and Trade institutions into extraordinary systems that reliably exceed expectations (By the year 2030, public and trade institutions in Africa will serve as molds for extraordinary institutions that reliably exceed expectations) • Ensuring best electoral and political practices (By the year 2030, the electoral and political system in Africa will be referenced for best 	<p>love others for who they are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners demonstrate active and responsible citizenship based on an understanding of the roles, rights and responsibilities of individuals and groups, the importance of social justice, supremacy of the constitution, and concern for local, national and global issues, and a respect for all of these, including freedom of the press and media. • Learners identify key actions and build awareness on policies and innovations that will accelerate women's, children's, and minorities' empowerment that have real impact on the quality of life of their community and nation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representation • Inclusiveness • Open, regular, free and fair • Constitution • Amendment • Consensus • Equity and Equality • Respect • Transparency • Tolerance • Accountability • Children rights • Women rights • Minority rights • Freedom of Speech • Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle • Justice • Save • Peace • Love • Vote • Acceptance • Land rights • Government • Democracy • Corruption • Conflict • Refugees • manifesto • World peace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent and impartial judiciary • Rule of Law • Freedom of speech (Press and Media) • Absence of Corruption • Mutual respect • Saving to invest • Voting to improve results • Peaceful coexistence • Legal, transparent, and equitable land administration and management • Protecting women and children from abuse and exploitation • Peaceful protests • Peaceful resolution of conflicts • Curbing Illegal Migration • Reduce, Re-use, and Recycle • Citing evidence in support of ideas 	<p>would curb permissive constitutional arrangements and strengthen institutional checks and balances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak Human Rights mechanism • Gross abuse and exploitation of Women and Children • Cosmetic free judiciaries • Poor participation in electoral processes • Racism and Sexism • Poverty and Hunger • Machiavelism • Ethnocentrism • Passivity • Energy crises • Ignorance • Apathy • Cynicism • Xenophobia • Cultural dissonance • Unpatriotic citizens • Colonialism and imperialism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • History of human rights • Local, national legal systems • Local and national history in human rights terms • UNESCO, UNICEF • World Bank • FAO • Freedom House • UN Covenants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elimination of racism • Elimination of sexism • Regional human rights conventions • UNHCR • NGOs • Geneva Conventions • Specialized conventions
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	<p>democratic, electoral and governance practices)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Eradicating Hunger, poverty and Corruption</i> (By the year 2030, there will be zero hunger and zero poverty in Africa) • <i>Silencing the guns</i> (By the year 2030, all African countries will be free of conflicts, terrorism, and piracy) • <i>Getting better at environmental care and protection</i> (By the year 2030, Africa will have a healthy and productive balance between economic development and environmental sustainability) • <i>Providing Peace Justice and Security for All</i> (By the year 2030, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners develop an understanding of external and internal economic influences on political systems and outcomes, mobilize policies to improve campaign finance law, actively adopt early saving dispositions, and participation in transformational economic activities, in order to transform their communities, nation, and the world at large. • Learners develop a healthy and peaceful lifestyle, understand Peacekeeping and Peacemaking in the light of coups d'états, civil war, terrorism, piracy, and tribal conflicts, employ initiatives to curb illegal migration, and actively participate in Peace building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy • Sharing • Openness • Participation • Integrity • Tradition • Custom • Campaign • Entrepreneur • Positive Leadership • International law • Legal Rights • Moral Right 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doing research, gathering information and creating artefacts • Sharing information • Community service and action • Investment in basic social services • Devolution of power and resources • Servant of the demos, not master • Great 4Cs Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gross Corruption: Africa annually loses over \$50 billion through illicit flows and \$148 billion through corruption. 1 in 4 people in Africa paid bribes for public services. • Poor Saving culture • Environmental degradation • Gross lack of transparency, integrity, and accountability in public offices • Agriculture is 2-4 times more potent than any other sector in reducing poverty in Africa. More than 60% of those who till the soil are women but their effort to improve the sector has come up against three major constraints: (1)Lack of land rights, (2) Lack of access to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evolving human rights standards • ACDEG Charter • IFES • IDEA • FISA • INE • ACE
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	<p>Africa will become the cradle of peace, justice and security for all humanity)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zeroing down on illegal migration (By the year 2030, there will be zero illegal migration in Africa) • Distinguishing wants from needs from rights (By the year 2030, Africans will champion the rights of all humanity, and the rights of the planet Earth) • Integration of ACDEG values into personal awareness and behaviors (By the year 2030, the behavior of all Africans will be an embodiment of the ACDEG values) 	<p>programs that would ensure security and justice for all</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners are equipped with the disposition and tools to ensure efficiency in public services, optimal use of resources, practice inclusive leadership, identify and eradicate corruption. • Learners appreciate the interaction between human beings and the environment in terms of the processes and patterns of natural and human features, in different places, and participate in sustaining, conserving and improving the environment • Learners can identify, describe, analyze, evaluate (social, political and economic issues) and defend positions with 			<p>input, (3) Lack of right over final product</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Torture and Genocide • Poor self-esteem • Children socializing each other • Foreign aid dependency syndrome • Reduction in foreign investment • Western nation have retreated from emphasizing democratic governance principles in their development assistance programs (in favor of geostrategic interests such as competing against China, stemming migration, and fighting terrorism). • China’s “Ask No Questions” policies in Africa 	
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		appropriate evidence and careful reasoning. They can also interact, monitor, and influence political system in ways that exceed expectations.			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic globalization • Fire fighting strategies and policies 	
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3.5. Inclusion

3.5.1 Suitable challenges

- Teachers and Improvement teams should set high expectations for every learner and align resources. They should plan stretching work for learners whose attainment is significantly above the expected standard. They have an even greater obligation to design learning for learners who have low levels of attainment or come from disadvantaged backgrounds. Teachers and improvement teams should use appropriate assessment to set targets which are deliberately ambitious – focusing on the 4Cs. On the hand, there is equally the pressing need for teachers training institutes to sharpen their practices to ensure that their cadres are capable of cultivating cooperativeness, communication, creative and critical thinking skills in the field.

3.5.2 Responding to learners’ needs and overcoming potential barriers for individuals and groups of learners

1. Teachers and improvement teams should take account of their duties under equal opportunities legislation that covers race, disability, sex, religion or belief, sexual orientation, pregnancy and maternity, and gender reassignment.
2. A wide range of learners have special educational needs, many of whom also have disabilities. Lessons should be planned to ensure that there are no barriers to every learner achieving. In many cases, such planning will mean that these learners will be able to study the full DGC curriculum.
3. With the right teaching, that recognizes their individual needs, many disabled learners may have little need for additional resources beyond the aids which they use as part of their daily life. Teachers must design learning so that these learners can study every aspect of the DGC curriculum with their head, hands, and hearts. Potential areas of difficulty should be identified and addressed at the outset of work.

4. Monitoring of progress should take account of the learner's age, previous educational experience, ability in other disciplines and the 4Cs skills (communication, collaboration, creative and critical thinking).
5. Teachers and Improvement teams should aim to provide the support learners need to take part in all subjects.

3.5.3 Developing learners' heads, hands, and hearts

A holistic approach to learning involves engaging the head, heart and hands. It is only by targeting the head, hands, and heart that effective change takes place.

3.5.3.1 Developing learners' heads (*Trivium = Grammar, Rhetoric, and Logic*)

It refers to engaging the cognitive domain through study, inquiry and understanding of democratic and human rights cultures and practice. Developing learners' head through the prism of trivium corresponds to the stages of child development. (Change in perception). Trivium is an active process, not one which learners passively acquire information and skills.

- ***Grammar***

This means the mastering of democratic and human rights language. At key stage 1, it can be learned through drill. At key stage 2 to 5, learners should be able to express their mastery of the language orally and written through persuasive, argumentative, and report writing.

- ***Logic***

Logic is the "mechanics" of thought and of analysis, the process of identifying fallacious arguments and statements and so systematically removing contradictions, thereby producing factual knowledge that can be trusted. It is basically the art of critical thinking.

- ***Rhetoric***

Rhetoric is the art of communicating by expressing oneself eloquently and persuasively. Learners should be taught to speak clearly and convey ideas confidently using the standard language of instruction. They should learn to justify ideas with reasons; ask questions to check understanding; develop vocabulary and build knowledge; negotiate; evaluate and build on the ideas of others; and select the appropriate register for effective communication. They should be taught to give well-structured descriptions and explanations and develop their understanding through speculating, hypothesizing and exploring ideas. This will enable them to clarify their thinking as well as organize their ideas for writing.

3.5.3.2 Developing learners' hands

It refers to the enactment of the psychomotor domain for learning practical skills development and physical work. This requires incorporating educational experiences into learners' everyday lives by designing artefacts such as a brochure on how to solve a specific problem in their community. This enables learners to find purpose in learning. Research, worldwide, shows pupils are naturally kinaesthetic learners. They love hands-on learning. Hands-on learning results to deep engagement. To be engaged is to actively participate, to be involved and invested. Engaged learners exhibit characteristics of being attracted to their task, persistence in their task despite obstacles or challenges and take visible joy in accomplishing their task. (Active engagement).

3.5.3.3 Developing learners' heart

It refers to the emotional and social aspect of learning. Emotions are the reasons for actions and change because emotions are context for interpreting and responding to experience. Learners should feel safe, cared for, and cared about. They should have a sense of belonging and confidence. They should develop compassion, respect and empathy. They should recognize their own feelings and feelings for and of others. Learners should learn the skills of sharing, taking turns, listening to others, practicing acts of kindness. All learners want to feel respected and loved. They want to be heard, and they want to learn and succeed.

3.6. Attainment targets (*Assessments*)

By the end of each term the school must write a report on every child's progress and talk it through with the parents/guardians.

3.6.1 Key stage 1

- For year 1, the mastery faculties are observation and memory. Hence, basic aspects of the constitution and human rights (women and children rights) should be memorized through lyric and narratives.
- For year 2, the mastery faculties are observation, memory, and discursive reason. Hence, learners at this cognitive level are able to produce artefacts such as a brochure addressing a democratic problem.

3.6.2 Key stage 2: Here learners should be able to produce works that demonstrate their collaborative, communicative, creative and critical thinking skills.

3.6.3 Key stage 3: Here learners should be able to produce works that clearly demonstrate their collaborative, communicative, creative and critical thinking skills.

3.6.4 Key stage 4: Here learners should be able to produce works that clearly demonstrate their collaborative, communicative, creative and critical thinking skills.

3.6.5 Key stage 5 Here learners should be able to produce works that clearly demonstrate their collaborative, communicative, creative and critical thinking skills.

3.7. Scope of Key Stages

3.7.1 Key stage 1

During key stage 1 pupils learn about themselves as developing individuals and as members of their communities, building on their own experiences and on the early learning goals for personal, social and emotional development. More importantly, they learn about their individual identity, their communal identity, and their duties and responsibilities towards their community and nation.

They learn the basic rules and skills for keeping themselves healthy and safe and for behaving well. They have opportunities to show they can take some responsibility for themselves and their environment. They begin to learn about their own and other people's feelings and become aware of the views, needs and rights of other children and older people.

As members of a class and school community, they learn social skills such as how to share, take turns, play, help others, resolve simple arguments and take responsibilities. They begin to develop love for school and take an active part in the life of their community and nation.

YEAR ONE (Primary 1)

Knowledge, skills, values, attitude, and tools

1. Developing confidence and responsibility and making the most of their abilities

Pupils should be taught:

First Term (Heart – Song, Game, HOD)

(Supremacy of the constitution and Citizenship)

1. to recognize what they like and dislike as citizens, what is fair and unfair, and what is right and wrong as citizens of an active and prosperous community;
2. to share their opinions on things that matter to them in the constitution and explain their views;
3. to recognize, name and deal with their feelings in a positive way and correlate it to the constitution;
4. to think about themselves as responsible citizens, learn from their experiences and recognize what they are good at;
5. how to set simple constitution and present it as an artifact.

Second Term (Head –HOD, Drama, Song)

(Equality before the law and Fundamental rights and freedoms)

1. to recognize what they like about children’s rights, and what they dislike about those who abuse such rights, what is fair and unfair when dealing with children, and what is right and wrong in the law;
2. to share their opinions on “equality of the law” and explain their views;
3. to recognize, name and deal with their feelings in a positive way;
4. to think about themselves as free citizens, with duties and responsibilities, and recognize what they are good at;
5. how to set simple laws for themselves and their community – and present it as an artifact.

Third Term (Hand - PBL)

(Children’s rights and Women’s rights)

1. to recognize what they like and dislike, what is fair and unfair, and what is right and wrong;
2. to share their opinions on things that matter to them and explain their views;
3. to recognize, name and deal with their feelings in a positive way;
4. to think about themselves, learn from their experiences and recognize what they are good at;

5. how to set simple goals.

2. Preparing to play an active role as citizens

Pupils should be taught:

First Term (Heart – Song, Game, HOD)

(Supremacy of the constitution and Citizenship)

1. to take part in discussions with one other person and the whole class on constitution and citizenship;
2. to take part in a simple debate about issues on constitution and citizenship;
3. to recognize choices they can make, and recognize the difference between right and wrong;
4. to agree and follow rules for their group and classroom, and understand how rules help them;
5. to realize that people and other living things have rights and needs, and that they have responsibilities to meet them;
6. that they belong to various groups and communities, such as family and school governed by the constitution;
7. to contribute to the life of the class and school as responsible citizens.

Second Term (Head – HOD, Drama, Song)

(Equality before the law and Fundamental rights and freedoms)

1. to take part in discussions with one other person and the whole class;
2. to take part in a simple debate about fundamental rights and freedom, and equality before the law;
3. to recognize choices they can make, and recognize the difference between right and wrong;
4. to agree and follow rules for their group and classroom, and understand how rules help them;
5. to realize that people and other living things have needs, and that they have responsibilities to meet them;
6. that they belong to various groups and communities, such as family and school;

7. to contribute to the life of the class and school.

Third Term (Hand – PBL)

(Children's rights and Women's rights)

1. to take part in discussions with one other person and the whole class about children' and women's rights;
2. to take part in a simple debate about children's rights;
3. to recognize choices they can make, and recognize the difference between right and wrong;
4. to agree and follow rules for their group and classroom, and understand how rules help them;
5. to realize that people and other living things have needs, and that they have responsibilities to meet them;
6. that they belong to various groups and communities, such as family and school;
7. to contribute to the life of the class and school.

3. Developing a healthy, safer lifestyle

Pupils should be taught:

1. how to make simple choices that improve their health and wellbeing;
2. to maintain personal hygiene;
3. rules for, and ways of, keeping safe, including basic road safety, and about people who can help them to stay safe.

4. Developing good relationships and respecting the differences between people

Pupils should be taught:

1. to recognize how their behavior affects other people;
2. to listen to other people, and play and work cooperatively;
3. to identify and respect the differences and similarities between people;

4. that family and friends should care for each other;
5. that there are different types of teasing and bullying, that bullying is wrong, and how to get help to deal with bullying.

5. Breadth of opportunities

During the key stage, pupils should be taught the knowledge, skills and understanding through opportunities to:

1. take and share responsibility (for example, for their own behavior; by helping to make classroom rules and following them);
2. to be patriotism and just, have tolerance and empathy, and respect for the Constitution, Human Rights, and Properties;
3. feel positive about themselves (for example, by having their achievements recognized and by being given positive feedback about themselves);
4. take part in discussions (for example, talking about topics of school, local, national, Africa, and global concern, such as 'the peaceful resolution of conflict, peaceful coexistence, fight against corruption, and the strong need for accountability in public services');
5. make real choices (for example, between healthy options in school and home behavior, what to watch on television, what games to play, how to spend and save money sensibly);
6. meet and talk with people (for example, with outside visitors such as religious leaders, police officers, the school improvement team);
7. develop relationships through work and play (for example, by sharing equipment with other pupils or their friends in a group task);
8. consider social and moral dilemmas that they come across in everyday life (for example, aggressive behavior, questions of fairness, right and wrong, simple political issues, use of money, simple environmental issues);
9. ask for help (for example, from family and friends, teachers, older pupils, the police, .)
10. design artefacts on constitution and human rights.

YEAR TWO (Primary 2)

Knowledge, skills, values, attitude, and tools

1. Developing confidence and responsibility and making the most of their abilities

Pupils should be taught:

First Term (Heart – Songs, Game, HOD)

(Supremacy of the constitution and Children’s rights)

1. to recognize what they like and dislike as patriotic citizens, what is fair and unfair, and what are right and wrong behaviors towards children;
2. to share their opinions on things that matter to them in the constitution and explain their views;
3. to recognize, name and deal with their feelings in a positive way and correlate it to the constitution and children’s rights;
4. to think about themselves as responsible citizens, learn from their experiences and recognize what they are good at;
5. how to set simple constitution and present it as an artifact.

Second Term (Head – HOD, Game, Drama)

(Political system and Environmental rights)

1. to recognize what they like and dislike about Political system (and environmental issues), what is fair and unfair in politics (and the environment), and what is right and wrong in political system (and the environment);
2. to share their opinions on “political system and the environmental rights” and explain their views;
3. to recognize, name and deal with their feelings (about the environment and political system) in a positive way;
4. to think about themselves as free citizens, with duties and responsibilities, and recognize what they are good at;
5. how to set simple political system and present it as a drama or create a brochure about environmental rights; or act an environmental drama where students become the voice of inanimate objects.

Third Term (Hand – PBL)

(Freedom of expression and the media, and Democratic culture and practice)

1. to recognize what they like and dislike, what is fair and unfair, and what is right and wrong;
2. to share their opinions on things that matter to them and explain their views;
3. to recognize, name and deal with their feelings in a positive way;
4. to recognize, name and deal with democratic practices;
5. to think about themselves, learn from their experiences and recognize what they are good at;
6. how to set simple goals, and act out drama that show they have understood democratic values such as tolerance, respect, and willingness to learn and compromise.

2. Preparing to play an active role as citizens

Pupils should be taught:

First Term (Heart – Songs, Game, HOD)

(Supremacy of the constitution and Children's rights)

1. to take part in discussions with one other person and the whole class on constitutional matter and children's rights;
2. to take part in a simple debate about issues on constitution and children's rights;
3. to recognize choices they can make, and recognize the difference between right and wrong;
4. to agree and follow rules for their group and classroom, and understand how rules help them;
5. to realize that people and other living things have rights and needs, and that they have responsibilities to meet them;
6. that they belong to various groups and communities, such as family and school governed by the constitution;
7. to contribute to the life of the class and school as responsible citizens;

Second Term (Head – HOD, Drama, QQ)

(Political system and Environmental rights)

1. to take part in discussions with one other person and the whole class on political system and environmental rights;

2. to take part in a simple debate about Environment rights and political system;
3. to recognize choices they can make, and recognize the difference between right and wrong in a political system;
4. to agree and follow rules set by a political system, and understand how rules help them;
5. to realize that people and other living things have rights, and that they have responsibilities to meet them;
6. that they belong to various groups and communities that are parts of a political system;
7. to contribute to the life of the class and school;

Third Term (Hand – PBL)

(Freedom of expression and the media, and Democratic culture and practice)

1. to take part in discussions with one other person and the whole class about freedom of expression, and democratic values and practice;
2. to take part in a simple debate about democratic practice;
3. to recognize choices they can make, and recognize the difference between right and wrong;
4. to agree and follow rules for their group and classroom, and understand how rules help them;
5. to realize that people and other living things have needs and rights, and that they have responsibilities to meet them;
6. that they belong to various groups and communities, such as family and school;
7. to contribute to the life of the class and school;

3. Developing a healthy, safer lifestyle

Pupils should be taught:

1. how to make simple choices that improve their health and wellbeing;
2. to maintain personal hygiene;
3. rules for, and ways of, keeping safe, including basic road safety, and about people who can help them to stay safe.

4. Developing good relationships and respecting the differences between people

Pupils should be taught:

1. to recognize how their behavior affects other people;
2. to listen to other people, and play and work cooperatively;
3. to identify and respect the differences and similarities between people;
4. that family and friends should care for each other;
5. that there are different types of teasing and bullying, that bullying is wrong, and how to get help to deal with bullying.

5. Breadth of opportunities

During the key stage, pupils should be taught the knowledge, skills and understanding through opportunities to:

1. take and share responsibility (for example, for their own behavior; by helping to make classroom rules and following them);
2. to be patriotism and just, have tolerance and empathy, and respect for the Constitution, Human Rights, and Properties;
3. feel positive about themselves (for example, by having their achievements recognized and by being given positive feedback about themselves);
4. take part in discussions (for example, talking about topics of school, local, national, Africa, and global concern, such as 'the peaceful resolution of conflict, peaceful coexistence, fight against corruption, and the strong need for accountability in public services');
5. make real choices (for example, between healthy options in school and home behavior, what to watch on television, what games to play, how to spend and save money sensibly);
6. meet and talk with people (for example, with outside visitors such as religious leaders, police officers, the school improvement team);
7. develop relationships through work and play (for example, by sharing equipment with other pupils or their friends in a group task);
8. consider social and moral dilemmas that they come across in everyday life (for example, aggressive behavior, questions of fairness, right and wrong, simple political issues, use of money, simple environmental issues);

9. ask for help (for example, from family and friends, teachers, older pupils, the police, .)

10. design artifacts on constitution and human and environmental rights.

3.7.2. Key stage 2

During key stage 2 pupils learn about themselves as growing and changing individuals with their own experiences and ideas, and as members of their communities.

They become more mature, independent and self-confident. They learn about the wider world and the interdependence of communities within it. They develop their sense of social justice and moral responsibility and begin to understand that their own choices and behavior can affect local, national or global issues and political and social institutions. They learn how to take part more fully in school and community activities. As they begin to develop into young adults, they face the changes of puberty and transfer to secondary school with support and encouragement from their school. They learn how to make more confident and informed choices about their health and environment; to take more responsibility, individually and as a group, for their own learning; and to resist bullying.

YEAR THREE (Primary 3)

Knowledge, skills, values, attitudes and tools

1. Developing confidence and responsibility and making the most of their abilities

Pupils should be taught

First Term (Electoral policies and procedures/ Legal framework)

1. to talk and write about their opinions, and explain their views on electoral policies and procedures;
2. to recognize their worth as individuals in designing electoral policies and procedures and enforcing them;
3. to face new challenges positively by collecting information, looking for help, making responsible choices, and taking action;
4. about the range of jobs carried out by people in the electoral board, and to understand how they can develop such skills to make their own contribution in the future;

5. to look after their money and realize that future wants and needs may be met through saving.

Second Term (Citizens' Choice of Leader/Representation, and Peaceful Resolution of Disputes)

1. to talk and write about their opinions, and explain their views on their choice of leadership and peaceful resolution of dispute;
2. to recognize their worth as individuals to become transformational leaders by identifying positive things about themselves and their achievements, seeing their mistakes, making amends and setting personal goals;
3. to face new challenges positively, as peace makers, by collecting information, looking for help, making responsible choices, and taking action;
4. to recognize different leadership cultures, representation, and roles;
5. about the range of jobs carried out by people in leadership, and to understand how they can develop skills to make their own contribution in the future;
6. to look after their money and realize that future wants and needs may be met through saving.

Third Term (Combating corruption, and Accountability and Efficiency in Service)

1. to talk and write about their opinions, and explain their views on corruption, and accountability in service delivery;
2. to recognize their worth as individuals, in combating corruption, by identifying positive things about themselves and their achievements, in combating corruption, seeing their mistakes, making amends and setting personal goals to combat corruption;
3. to face new challenges positively in the course of combating corruption by collecting information, looking for help, making responsible choices, and taking action;
4. to advocate and practice the culture of accountable service delivery;
5. to look after their money and realize that future wants and needs may be met through saving.

2. Preparing to play an active role as citizens

Pupils should be taught

First Team (Electoral policies and procedures/ Legal framework)

1. to research, discuss and debate topical issues, problems and events about electoral policies and procedures;
2. why and how rules and laws are made and enforced, why different rules are needed in different situations and how to take part in making and changing rules;
3. to realise the consequences of anti-social and aggressive behaviours, such as bullying and racism, on individuals and communities;
4. that there are different kinds of responsibilities, rights and duties at home, at school and in the community, and that these can sometimes conflict with each other;
5. to reflect on spiritual, moral, social, and cultural issues, using imagination to understand other people's experiences;
6. to resolve differences by looking at alternatives, making decisions and explaining choices;
7. what democracy is, and about the basic institutions that support it locally and nationally;
8. to recognise the role of voluntary, community and pressure groups;
9. to appreciate the range of national, regional, religious and ethnic identities in Africa;
10. that resources can be allocated in different ways and that these economic choices affect individuals, communities and the sustainability of the environment;
11. to explore how the media present information.

Second Team (Citizens' Choice of Leader/Representation, and Peaceful Resolution of Disputes)

1. to research, discuss and debate topical issues, problems and events on citizens' choice of leaders and peaceful resolution of disputes;

2. why and how rules and laws are made and enforced, why different rules are needed in different situations and how to take part in making and changing rules;
3. to realize the consequences of anti-social and aggressive behaviors, such as bullying and racism, on individuals and communities;
4. that there are different kinds of responsibilities, rights and duties at home, at school and in the community, and that these can sometimes conflict with each other;
5. to reflect on spiritual, moral, social, and cultural issues, using imagination to understand other people's experiences;
6. to resolve differences by looking at alternatives, making decisions and explaining choices;
7. what peaceful resolution of dispute is, and about the basic institutions that support it locally and nationally;
8. to recognize the role of voluntary, community and pressure groups in resolving disputes;
9. to appreciate the range of national, regional, religious and ethnic identities in Africa;
10. that resources can be allocated in different ways and that these economic choices affect individuals, communities and the sustainability of the environment;
11. to explore how the media present information on citizens' choice of leader, and how it can be used for peaceful resolution of disputes.

Third Team (Combating corruption, and Accountability and Efficiency in Service)

1. to research, discuss and debate topical issues, problems and events on corruption and accountability;
2. why and how corruption rules and laws are made and enforced, why different rules are needed in different situations and how to take part in making and changing rules;
3. that there are different kinds of responsibilities, rights and duties at home, at school and in the community, and that these can sometimes conflict with each other;
4. to reflect on spiritual, moral, social, and cultural dimension of corruption and its implications, using imagination to understand other people's experiences;
5. to resolve differences by looking at alternatives, making decisions and explaining choices;
6. what corruption is, and about the basic institutions that support its eradication locally and nationally;

7. to recognise the role of voluntary, community and pressure groups in combating corruption;
8. that resources can be allocated in different ways to combat corruption;
9. to explore how the media can be use in combating corruption.

3. Developing a healthy, safer lifestyle

Pupils should be taught:

1. how to make simple choices that improve their health and wellbeing;
2. to maintain personal hygiene;
3. rules for, and ways of, keeping safe, including basic road safety, and about people who can help them to stay safe.

4. Developing good relationships and respecting the differences between people

Pupils should be taught:

1. that their actions affect themselves and others, to care about other people's feelings and to try to see things from their points of view;
2. to think about the lives of people living in other places and times, and people with different values and customs;
3. to be aware of different types of relationship, including marriage and those between friends and families, and to develop the skills to be effective in relationships;
4. to realize the nature and consequences of racism, teasing, bullying and aggressive behaviors, and how to respond to them and ask for help;
5. to recognize and challenge stereotypes;
6. that differences and similarities between people arise from a number of factors, including cultural, ethnic, racial and religious diversity, gender and disability;

7. where individuals, families and groups can get help and support.

5. Breadth of opportunities

During the key stage, pupils should be taught the knowledge, skills and understanding through opportunities to:

1. take responsibility (for example, for planning and looking after the school environment; for the needs of others, such as by acting as a peer supporter, as a befriender, or as a playground mediator for younger pupils; for looking after animals properly; for identifying safe, healthy and sustainable means of travel when planning their journey to school);
2. to be patriotism and just, have tolerance and empathy, and respect for the Constitution, Human Rights, and Properties;
3. feel positive about themselves (for example, by having their achievements recognized and by being given positive feedback about themselves);
4. take part in discussions (for example, talking about topics of school, local, national, Africa, and global concern, such as 'the peaceful resolution of conflict, peaceful coexistence, fight against corruption, and the strong need for accountability in public services');
5. make real choices (for example, between healthy options in school and home behavior, what to watch on television, what games to play, how to spend and save money sensibly);
6. meet and talk with people (for example, with outside visitors such as religious leaders, police officers, the school improvement team);
7. develop relationships through work and play (for example, by sharing equipment with other pupils or their friends in a group task);
8. consider social and moral dilemmas that they come across in everyday life (for example, aggressive behavior, questions of fairness, right and wrong, simple political issues, use of money, simple environmental issues);
9. ask for help (for example, from family and friends, teachers, older pupils, the police);
10. design artefacts on constitution and human and environmental rights.

CHAPTER 4: PEDAGOGY

4.1 Introduction

Faced with the persistent gaps of what is actually learned in schools in terms of civic education, and the continuous vicious cycle of social malice that plague the continent, changes in civic pedagogy and curricula were deemed inevitable. The Sage on Stage, which is the dominant teaching approach in Africa, has been shown by research to be too weak in improving learners' outcomes and opportunities. To achieve the African Union dream of creating a new African citizen who will be an effective change agent for the continent's sustainable development, changes in pedagogy is inevitable. Teaching should value learners' voice and choice; it should equip them with collaboration, communication, creative, and critical thinking skills; learners should be able to explore political and social issues critically, to weigh evidence, debate and make reasoned arguments. The teaching should equip learners with the schema, language and tools to manage their resources such as money on a day-to-day basis, and plan for future financial needs. This form of teaching put learners at center of the learning process. This sort of teaching includes: Higher Order Discussion (HOD) technique, use of Question Quadrant (QQ), Project based learning, use of Drama, use of Songs, use of Games, etc.

The role of a teacher is not only educating but also motivating students who regard traditional ways of learning as dull and boring. Therefore, DGC teachers are supposed to show creativity and enthusiasm as well as openness to new ideas and challenges, while keeping a balance between serious learning and amusement. The aforementioned learner-centered techniques provide teachers with a rich and authentic resource that they can utilize to promote student engagement in the class and to make a satisfactory connection between entertainment and learning.

It is worth noting that Democracy is lived, not taped. We must teach democracy in a way that learners experience it in themselves. To learn democracy, students must do and live democracy. Teach Democracy by doing it. What affect our children most (as teachers) is what we do, is not what we say; and as parents and policy makers, it is what we say and do not do.

Figure 4.1: Sage on Stage versus Guide on the Side

Table 4.1: Sage on Stage versus Guide on the Side

SAGE ON STAGE	GUIDE ON THE SIDE	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active teacher, Passive learners • Does NOT ensure collaboration, communication, creative and critical thinking skills (4Cs). • Less effective for 21st century learners. • Out of date. 	<i>Co-Creative perspective</i>	<i>Directive Perspective</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Based Learning (PBL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher-Order Discussion (HOD)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students as Guides (SG) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Question Quadrant
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Drama 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Songs (with physical synchrony)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Songs (with physical synchrony) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Game 	

Note: The Guide on stage approach constitutes a "Directive perspective" and "Co-Creative perspective" approaches to teaching, and both approaches can effectively be used to improve learners' outcomes and opportunities. The Computing Value Framework (CVF) ensures that both ways are effectively used to address pressing needs. Both introvert and extrovert learners benefit from guide-on-stage pedagogy.

4.2 SAGE ON STAGE Questioning Technique (Ping – Pong)

In a Ping-Pong discussion the teacher asks a question, students raise their hands, the teacher calls on a student, the student responds, the teacher evaluates that response in some way. For example, says good job, and then the teacher asks another question, usually a completely different question. And, again, students raise their hands, and the teacher calls on someone, the student gives an answer, the teacher responds. So it's back and forth, back and forth, like a match in Ping-Pong.

4.3 GUIDE ON THE SIDE Questioning Technique (Pop – Corn or HOD)

In a Popcorn discussion (Higher-Order Discussion - HOD) the teacher poses a really big question. So, it might be something like what are the three most important things the author has told us about democracy? And, then a student responds. But, then a second student might then respond to the first student, and a third student might jump in and say they agree with the first student. And, a fourth student may come in and make a little bit of a different point and so on. And, after a number of different student comments and exchanges, then the teacher might come back in and summarize what has been said and pose a follow-up.

So the teacher might say, well so far I have heard these three things as nominated as important things that the author has told us about democracy. What else might we add to the list? At that point, again, students raise their hands, another student responds, then another student responds to that student, and another student may jump in. The teacher may ask for some clarification and so on. So, the look of it is more like popcorn popping, lots of contributions and interactions across the classroom. This technique reflects a democratic way of doing things.

Research tells us that a popcorn structure of discussion is more effective for learners, in terms of developing their comprehension, and critical thinking skills than a Ping-Pong style of discussion.

Critical to effective higher order discussion is higher order questions. Examples of higher order questions stem include:

- Why did
- What do you think.....?
- If you were the author
- What doesremind you of and why?

Examples of *follow-up questions*:

- What makes you say that?
- What happened in the book that makes you think that?

- Can you explain what you meant when you said.....?
- Do you agree with what said? Why or why not?
- How does what you said connect with already said?
- Let's see if what we read provides us with any information that can resolve’s and’s disagreement.
- What does the author say about that?

So, many questions that start with “**why**” will be effective as higher order questions. Follow-up questions are also critical to ambitious democracy instruction. They deepen students’ thinking, and make them elaborate so that they further develop their communication and critical thinking skills, and move conversations forward in ways that lead to higher order kinds of thought.

Also, in ambitious democracy instruction, we want to see critique and evaluate questions, integrate and interpret questions, as well as locate and recall questions.

There are a number of arguments for Higher-order discussion (HOD) approach:

- HOD puts advanced cognitive demand on students.
- HOD encourages students to think beyond literal questions.
- HOD promotes critical thinking skills because these types of **questions** expect students to apply, analyze, synthesize, and evaluate information instead of simply recalling facts.

4.4 Using Question Quadrant to effectively improve students’ outcomes and opportunities

A question quadrant is a thinking tool to elicit and generate meaningful and purposeful questions to guide learning. Open and Closed questions lie along one axis while, Text, and Life questions lie along the other. It basically contains four quadrant questions, namely:

- **Close text** (dig it out, reading comprehension) questions: these are actually locate and recall questions, and integrated questions.

- **Close life** (find it out, scientific and social research) questions: these are actually research questions.
- **Open text** (work it out, literacy speculation) questions: these are actually analytical or inferential questions
- **Open life** (think it out, open enquiry/philosophical) questions: these are questions related to:

Metaphysics: Is democracy real?

Logic: Is democracy the best form of form of governance?

Ethics: Is democracy good or bad?

Epistemology: How do we know what we know about democracy?

Aesthetic: Is democracy beautiful or ugly?

Figure 4.4: Question Quadrant

There are a number of arguments for using Question Quadrant approach:

- It focuses teaching on diversity and social justice.
- It ensures students are asking more questions than the teacher.
- It calls for higher-order thinking, such as analysis, inference, evaluation, prediction.
- It develops communication, creative and critical thinking skills.
- It is a useful tool for developing philosophical questions with students.

4.5 Project Based Learning (PBL)

Valuing students' choice and voice.

Five Steps to get started with Project-Based Learning

- ***What is the goal?***

First things first, what are you hoping your students will learn? Pin down the exact outcomes you're looking for so you can better plan the path to that destination. For step one, we'll say the goal is to have students learn about the ins and outs of what makes up a country: forms of government, economic plans, and any other considerations you would like to cover. These are big concepts, so they will lend themselves well to this teaching method!

- ***Choose a specific problem or question***

Project-based learning focuses on solving a problem or answering a question. Circling back to our example, let's say the question is, "What do the main forms of government look like and how do they function? What do the main economic systems entail, and which works best with your chosen form of government?" Again, big questions, big topics! The beauty of this teaching method is that learning happens in a more natural and memorable way. Students will be diving in and exploring the topic with a degree of independence that would simply not be there with more traditional methods, such as a very formal lecture.

- ***Plan and facilitate the process***

Now it's time to plan your project. Here are some questions to consider as you prepare the assignment:

- What kinds of resources will your students need to work on their project?
- How could the project and information be presented?
- What kinds of formats would work with the question or problem you're dealing with?
- What will the time frame be like, and how will learning be assessed?

Project-based learning typically occurs in groups or teams, so you will want to keep collaboration in mind during the planning phase.

For a project such as create-your-own-country, students would likely need access to quality research material. Depending on your school, this may require booking computer or tablet time. You will also want to gather some good resources to help students on their way, or to put together a mini-lesson on good online research skills. Be sure to specify how much time to devote to research.

With younger students, you may also want to consider the option of providing background information. There should then be time provided for group discussions and the opportunity for students to debate the merits of the different government forms and economic systems that they are considering. Once they have chosen their desired form of government for their country and the accompanying economic system, how will they present the information? Posters? Slide presentations? Videos? Or Brochure? Perhaps some students are creative and would like to develop a flag, national anthem, and any other emblems. Finally, be sure to provide students with criteria for assessment so that they understand how to best complete their project.

- ***Demo time!***

Now it is time for students to show what they have learned. Regardless of the topic, it is a good idea for students to present their final product to the rest of the class and a variety of targeted audience, such as policymakers, Local real estate agents, and the Chamber of Commerce. This gives them a chance to practice their oral presentation and listening skills. It also allows students to learn from their peers. It is also important to remind students how to be a good audience ahead of time and go over some critical presentation skills (speaking clearly, maintaining eye contact, inflecting one's voice, etc.)

Do not forget to have your chosen criteria ready as you assess the actual final product, the evidence of learning, and the extra skills such as teamwork, problem-solving, and communication. Observe students during the project creation to determine how well some of these targets are being met (teamwork, for one), with a final assessment happening during demonstrations. For example, throughout the project, you may

have students submit vertical slices with accompanying peer evaluations. Then, rubric in hand, you can assess the final in-class presentation yourself.

Encourage groups to divide the presentation equally among their members so that everyone has a chance to speak. Alternatively, you may decide that each student must simply contribute to the presentation in some way that is not necessarily tied to speaking. For example, one student could be in charge of setup or arranging visual effects. Within their groups and with instructor approval, students should detail each member's expected contributions and roles and submit it with the final product.

- ***Reflection***

Part of project-based learning is taking the time to reflect on the progress (or lack thereof). As teachers, we should get in the habit of enforcing some form of reflection after lessons and projects so students can assess their performance and make adjustments in the future. You could have students fill out a short, simple 'exit slip' type of reflection in which they write a brief paragraph or complete a checklist on different aspects of their project — both its creation and the demonstration. They may also write about what they would like to improve on or what they would do differently next time.

You could make these reflections a bit more involved. For example, students could write a report or record a short podcast reflection. In any case, students should discuss what they have learned about the subject and their teamwork and/or presentation skills. You may also wish to encourage students to set realistic goals for future assignments or units.

Many conceptualizations of project-based instruction include the idea that projects occur over an extended time period. So if you have done it in a morning, it is not a project. It is just an activity. The most important feature of project-based approaches is that students need to work to achieve a purpose that is beyond just doing school or satisfying a school requirement.

1. Students might be building something.
2. They might be creating something like a brochure.
3. They might be addressing a question that they have, an authentic question that is arisen for them in their lives.
4. They might address a problem that they are seeing in their community or in the state or province, in the country or in the world.
5. Or they might address a real need that they are seeing.

In every case, they are doing what they are doing for some reason beyond just satisfying school requirements. Project-based approaches often connect students to contexts outside of the school building. So, they might be connected to organizations in their local community, or they might be connected to state, national, or international organizations or individuals.

Projects are usually interdisciplinary. And, this is partly because real world problems and real world needs are typically not easily categorized into the little bits of curriculum that we have in school. Rather, it might take some science, some social studies, a little bit mathematics, and a lot of literacy in order to achieve a project's purpose. And, when we think about project-based learning, we think about students having some choice and some autonomy in the project. So they are not simply doing exactly what the teacher tells them but they are in fact able to exert some voice and some choice in what they are doing.

There are a number of arguments for project-based approaches.

1. Research shows higher academic achievement in project-based learning contexts as compared to more traditional schooling contexts.
2. Research shows students' attitudes towards school is higher in the context of project-based learning.
3. Research shows that project-based learning is not only for gifted children or children with high achieving, it is also good for learners of low socioeconomic status, students with learning disabilities, and students with a wide range of achievement levels.
4. Research shows that project-based learning provides an opportunity for interdisciplinary; that when we teach science and literacy together rather than separately, it actually benefits both science learning and literacy learning.
5. Rather than handcuffing learners to their desks and books, project-based learning offers a fun and creative teaching method to get students involved in their learning. The on-going project will stick with students well beyond the classroom and offer a fantastic opportunity for them to work on developing many important skills.

4.6 Use of Drama

Drama is a valuable teaching tool. It gets students up and moving around and interacting with each other. It's particularly appealing to kinesthetic learners but can be used successfully for all learners.

Students will improve the speaking, listening skills, and democratic values in performing scenes. Also their writing skills will be developed through activities such as dialogue writing. Drama also teaches the “*pragmatics*” of democracy. Finally, drama promotes class bonding: in drama classes, there is usually a great deal of comradeness.

Methods to Incorporate Drama in a Democracy Class

1. *Act out the Dialogue*

One of the easiest ways to incorporate drama in the classroom is to **have students act out the dialogue from their textbooks**. Simply pair them up, have them choose roles, then work together to act out the dialogue, figuring out for themselves the “blocking,” or stage movements. This is effective for a beginning activity of incorporating drama in the classroom.

2. *Perform Reader's Theatre*

Another good beginning exercise is to do Reader's Theatre. Hand out copies of a short or one-act play, have students choose roles, and then read the play from their seats without acting it out. However, do encourage them to read *dramatically*, modeling as necessary.

3. *Act out the Story*

If students are reading a short story such as “*Billu, Appu & Democracy*,” have students act out the story or part of the story, working in groups and assigning roles and determining the blocking. This is particularly effective with “short-shorts”: brief, one-scene stories with limited characters.

4. *Write the Dialogue for a Scene*

Watch a brief clip of a movie without the sound on. Have students write the dialogue for it and act it out.

More Advanced Activities

Once students have had some experience with the basics of character, dialogue, and stage movement, they can move on to some **more advanced dramatics**, involving more of students' own creativity and critical thinking skills.

5. *Act out and Put Words to an Emotion*

Give students an emotion, such as “*anger*” or “*fear*”. Have students, either singly or in groups, first act out that emotion then put words to the emotion.

6. *Give “Voice” to an Inanimate Object*

What would a stapler say if it could talk? Or an apple? **Have students write monologues with inanimate objects as the character.** A monologue is a short scene with just one character talking, either addressing the audience, God, or himself or herself. Hamlet’s “To Be or Not to Be” soliloquy might also be termed a monologue, for example.

7. *Create a Characters*

Have students develop a character, writing a one-page profile on the character’s background, appearance, personality, etc. Have them introduce the character to the class, explaining what interests them about their character.

8. Write a Monologue

Using the character they’ve already developed, have students write a monologue for that character then perform it.

9. *Mime and Dubbing*

Have students act out short scenes without dialogue. The rest of the class then supplies the dialogue, developing the “script.”

10. *Improvise*

Put students in groups of two or three, and assign the characters and the situation to the groups, perhaps using 3x5 index cards. Give a time limit of two to three minutes per scene. Students go from there, extemporaneously creating the dialogue and movement themselves.

With careful planning, use of drama can enhance your Democracy classroom curriculum.

There are a number of arguments for Use of Drama approaches:

1. Drama is part of real life and prepares students to deal with life's problems.
2. Drama engages students in creative problem-solving and decision making.
3. Drama develops verbal and nonverbal communication.
4. Drama can enhance students' psychological well-being.
5. Drama develops empathy and new perspectives.
6. Drama builds cooperation and develops other social skills.
7. Drama increases concentration and comprehension through engagement.
8. Drama helps students consider moral issues and develop values.
9. Drama is an alternative way to assess by observing (ex. Externalization).
10. Drama is entertaining.
11. Drama contributes to aesthetic development.
12. Drama offers a learning avenue that enhances other areas of the curriculum.

4.7 Use of Songs (with Physical Synchrony)

Songs and rhythm have been described as 'a truly African way of communication' and it is therefore not surprising that music has played, and continues to play, an important role in African politics. Music, which is intricately inter- woven with development issues in Africa, is a dynamic and highly charged force that affects and embraces democracy, economic growth, censorship, media, tradition, globalization, and education. Hence, music has the power to move us and to change us. If songs are used in coordination with a DGC lesson, they can be of great value.

Also, psychologists have long recognized that physical synchrony produces psychological synchrony – a sense of oneness and cohesion. Hence, if we sing with physical movements, the psychological retention effect is far greater.

Planning for the use of songs in class

The process of selecting a song is one of the most difficult aspects of using music in a lesson. Here are some things you probably need to think about to ensure you get the right song.

- ***Purpose of the Song***

Carefully think about the democratic values you want learners to develop before choosing a song.

- ***Think about the language level of your class***

The language level of your class will determine not only which songs you can use, but also what other activities – such as games or written exercises – you will use to develop the lesson. Lower levels will become extremely frustrated with fast-delivered lyrics, for instance, while simple repetitive lyrics might not be interesting for more advanced-level learners.

- ***How old are your learners?***

If you are a teacher of young learners, you will probably want to use songs that are repetitive and very easy to understand. For teenagers, however, use contemporary or fairly recent pop and rock songs. It is advisable ask them 'what is cool'. Alternatively, for adult learners, who will probably have a more open approach to classes, use songs that are interesting to their age group.

- ***Musical Preferences of the Students and the Teacher?***

It is unwise to use music that students do not like. It is also unwise for the teacher to use music that he/she do not like. The answer is to find common ground. It is therefore advisable to ask the students to suggest song lyrics of their choice and to select the ones that have instructional values and are most popular with the students. Alternatively, teachers can make a list of different songs and let students choose, which will also involve them in their own learning.

- ***Format of the Song***

Music can be used either in audio or video format. While audio recordings are more readily available, music videos provide contextual information, and teachers can explore “their multimodal features (music, lyrics, and moving images) and their multilayered meanings to increase students’ DGC competence. It is crucial, however, that teachers carefully select music videos to be used in the lessons paying special attention to their content and messages.

- ***What kind of access do you have to the song?***

This is the age of YouTube and you can find practically any song on this website. Nevertheless, an mp3, which doesn’t require a connection, or even a good old-fashioned CD, can often be a useful backup. You can also use your phone connected to a Bluetooth speaker.

- ***Classroom Opportunities***

Teachers should also consider the availability of resources when they design music activities for the classroom. Such basic equipment as a computer with loudspeakers and a video projector will be needed to play songs or music videos in the classroom. In addition, music activities should be possibly conducted in large classrooms with appropriate acoustics. Lastly, care should be taken not to play music loudly so as not to cause inconvenience to other classes.

Methods to Incorporate Songs in a Democracy Class

Once teachers have selected the appropriate songs, they can design or adapt numerous classroom activities that address the lesson objectives. In order to make the experience of learning with music and songs as meaningful as possible for students, it is recommended to divide the music activities into three stages: pre-listening, while-listening and post-listening.

Table 4.7: Three Stages of a Song

<i>Pre-listening stage</i>	<i>While-listening stage</i>	<i>Post-listening stage</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • warm-up questions • presentation of key vocabulary and phrases • prediction activities(song title, content and theme of the singer) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • recognizing theme-specific words • ordering words, lines or verses • listening for detail (gap-fill, true/false, short answers, spot-the-error) • listening for gist (topic of the song) • matching (e.g. definitions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • singing/chanting (for fluency and pronunciation) • re-tell the story in the song • discuss the message of the song • write a summary of the story told in the song • read an article related to the topic of the song

1. *Pre-listening Stage*

The purpose of the pre-listening stage is activating the students' background knowledge as well as generating their interest in the song. This stage can begin with warm-up questions, presentation of useful vocabulary and prediction activities. An example of prediction activities is when the teacher shows a picture or plays the introduction to the song and asks students to predict the title, content or theme of the song.

2. *Listening Stage*

In the second stage, the students are required to listen to the song and to complete a certain task. For instance, the teacher could ask the students to underline specific words, to rearrange words or lines, to fill in gaps, to spot and correct mistakes or to match phrases with definitions. It is important to bear in mind that the song should be played at least two or three times to enable students to complete the task.

1. *Post-listening Stage*

In the post-listening stage, learners can engage in speaking, writing or reading activities. By way of example, they can practice vocabulary retention by singing or chanting the song lyrics as a class or in groups. Besides, the students might sum up the action of the song or its main theme, discuss the message of the song or read a text related to the topic of the song.

2. *Jigsaw read/sing the song*

Print out the lyrics in large font. Cut them up into numbered lines or phrases and distribute them amongst the class. Listen to the song together first and then get them to read/sing the lines in order. Certain songs are really good for this like Africa Unit, peace in Liberia. Sing the chorus together. And then discuss the meaning of the song and its potential impact.

More Advanced Activities

Once students have had some experience with listening to music and exploiting the song lyrics, they can move on to some **more advanced activities**, involving more of students' own creativity and critical thinking skills.

1. *Free-write/free-draw to the music*

The teacher can play different types of music and ask the students to write or draw how they feel about them. Every student can also make up their own stories for the music piece.

2. *Writing alternative verses of lyrics*

Students can be encouraged to write their own lyrics, keeping the original mood or style. Students can do it in groups or individually, whereby each group or student will be responsible for writing a new part of the lyrics. In this way, the alternative lyrics of the entire song can be prepared and presented in the class.

3. *Planning (and filming) a music video*

Groups of students can plan a music video for the song, focusing on the characters, the location and the storyline. After each group has explained the specific details of its plan for the music video in the class, the students can choose the one based on which the actual filming can be done.

4. *Preparing a lyric video*

Students can prepare song lyric visualization videos by using song lyrics and relevant images. By doing this project, the students will not only be challenged to show their creativity and interpretive skills but they will also need to demonstrate that they clearly understand the vocabulary in the song so that they can pick up befitting images based on their understanding of the song.

5. *Presenting on a musician or music genre*

Students can be asked to make a presentation on a chosen musician or music style. In this project students are given the freedom to organize their entire project, including research on the topic of their interest and the presentation of their findings. As a result, the students can develop their academic skills; practice their oral and organizational skills.

There are a number of arguments for Use of songs approaches:

- Effective use of songs and music in teaching has the potential to address multiple intelligences, reduce anxiety, increase motivation, facilitate memory retention and establish an affectively conducive learning environment.
- Songs have a positive influence on vocabulary retention of young learners.
- Whatever setting is used, aural or aural/visual, songs are suitable for different learning styles, and they encourage positive learning experience, and enhance young learners' knowledge.
- Songs aid motivation and help learners develop a love for learning. Students motivated in this way are imaginative, creative, and eager to learn and succeed.
- Songs and music can be utilized to develop cultural awareness and to foster students' creativity.
- Songs are appreciated for their linguistic, pedagogical, cultural and entertaining features and they are precious language learning materials.
- Students feel motivated to participate in classes involving songs.
- Songs enable the students to become better aware of the correct pronunciation.
- Songs contain colloquial language with ample repetitions, which have a facilitative effect on language learning.

- Songs play an important role in the development of young children; it helps the body and mind to work together. The child develops intellectually, socially, emotionally and it can help to develop the motor skills, but most importantly language can be developed through songs.
- One of the big problems we all face, whether teaching children or adults, is maintaining learners' interest throughout our lessons. Consequently, we often have to be very creative in the techniques we use. What makes music such a great teaching tool is its universal appeal, connecting all cultures and languages. This makes it one of the best and most motivating resources in the classroom, regardless of the age or background of the learner.

4.8 Use of Game

Young learners love to play, and they participate in games with more enthusiasm and willingness than in any other classroom task. Yet, games are under-utilized in the teaching and learning process. In general, learners learn better when they are active. Game-Based Learning plays important role in teaching by making students to collaborate, communicate, interact and work in teams. Strategic games improve the functioning of brain.

Five Steps to Implementing Game-Based Learning in the Classroom

1. Determine the Purpose of Using a Game

Are you looking to use a game for intervention, enrichment or reinforcement?

For intervention, look for a game that adjusts itself to player knowledge and learning style. For enrichment, it should build student's processing abilities by presenting content through different media. For reinforcement, students usually like being able to play as a team or against each other.

2. Play the Game Yourself, Making Sure It Is Aligned to Learning Goals

After finding a game you think is appropriate, play it and make note of five factors.

First, you should have some control over the game's content. Second, it should be easy to use. Third, it should be engaging. Fourth, it should offer different types of content. And fifth, it's beneficial if the game adapts content to each player, as previously mentioned.

3. Ensure It Meets Expectations from Parents

Send a letter home with students, explaining your game-based learning plan and its benefits.

This should open the door to parent participation. It will also help avoid confusion when students come home and talk about playing games in class.

4. *Dedicate Time to Consistent In-Class Play*

To ensure your students enjoy adequate play time and reap its benefits, try to:

- Include game time as a designated activity in your lesson plan
- Use a game as an entry or exit ticket
- Create learning stations, one of which is playing the game
- Play group games, eliminating the need for 1:1 device use

5. *Assess Progress Throughout Play, Informing Instruction*

When possible and applicable, collect student performance data through in-game reports, self-reports and class discussions. Create lessons using your findings. For example, focus on a common trouble spot.

Examples of Game-Based Learning Options for Your Classroom

- ***Video Games:*** Many video games offer comprehensive game-based learning experiences, and are becoming more accessible in schools due to increasing numbers of devices.
- ***Adaptations of Common Games:*** The fish game, online, about resolving political conflict in a village can be drawn on the blackboard or poster and used.
- ***Original Games:*** It is not against the rules to create a game from scratch.

Game-Based Learning vs. Gamification

Game-based learning and Gamification are often confused, and each require a separate approach to implement. So, it helps to understand the differences.

Table 4.8 Game-Based Learning vs. Gamification

<i>Game-Based Learning</i>	<i>Gamification</i>
Has defined rules and objectives	May just be a series of tasks with rewards
Presents a chance of losing	May not present a chance of losing
Is inherently rewarding most of the time	Does not always offer intrinsic rewards
Is normally hard and expensive to build	Is easier and cheaper
Morphs content to fit the story	Does not involve changing your content

There are a number of arguments for Use of game approaches:

- Games are activities with rules, a goal to achieve, and an element of fun; they seem to be challenging and interesting enough to keep the learners occupied and eager to complete the task. Games make children play and learn at the same time.
- Games help to create a context in which learners' attention is focused on the completion of a task without realizing that democratic values are being practiced. As a result, democratic learning takes place in a context that learners can directly relate to.
- Playing should be fun! In our great eagerness to teach our children we studiously look for "educational" toys, games with built-in lessons, books with a "message." Often these "tools" are less interesting and stimulating than the child's natural curiosity and playfulness. Play is by its very nature educational. And it should be pleasurable. When the fun goes out of play, most often so does the learning.
- Gaming creates a dynamic that can inspire learners to develop skills and build an emotional connection to learning and subject matter.

4.9 Use of Triple Es Framework (*Engage, Enhance, Extend*)

Using digital tools to effectively improve students' outcomes and opportunities

Research tells us that most Africa teachers are not trained to use technology (ICT/digital tools) in teaching, and even most of those who try to use them, do so ineffectively. Research also tells that most African curricula do not have precise methodology on how to effectively use technology in classrooms.

Studies over the past decades have shown that learning using technology is far more effective than teaching without technology. The purpose of technology in education should be focused on the learning and the learners' needs. And effective technology integration is driven by good teaching practices and not fancy tools. In addition to engaging learners, we know that technology should also enhance learning, value added, and extend learning beyond the classroom in unique ways.

How We Measure Effective Learning with Technology -- Triple Es Framework

For many years we did not actually have a tool to measure the effectiveness of digital tools on learning until the Triple E framework was designed from five years of rigorous research. It ensures the tool is bent on three Es, namely:

- **Engage:** focus on learning goals, time on task, co – use, and co – construct (social construction of knowledge).
- **Enhance:** value added: quick, efficient and flexible feedback; video, simulation; and internal and external communication? If there is not a value added, then do not do it. And keep in mind that we don't only have to use technology tools that are made for education. We can also venture outside and look for tools that really allow students to get to higher-level thinking skills.
- **Extend:** connect learning to everyday life, using learning to solve world problems, and reaching out to authentic audience.

Examples,

- Using mobile devices to collect evidence of community degradation (water, soil, or animals in the park) for further analysis.
- Taking pictures of social unrest for further analysis.
- Bring experts into the classroom through Skype.

- Connecting with experts through Web 2.0 or President 2.0 out of the classroom.
- Connecting one classroom to another classroom through Skype to work on a project.
- Doing some E-pals with students from another country in order to learn new democratic values and cultural norms.

What is and is not Effective Learning with Technology Tools?

There are some don'ts when it comes to technology that we have learned through evidence-based research. We want to make sure that we are not using technology as the focal point in the classroom. It is not about putting some fancy tools in the classrooms to show we are in a new century classroom. We want to make sure that we are avoiding things like “drill and practice software”, knowing that they can have negative effects on learning. We also want to avoid software that distracts from the learning goals or is used in isolation. It should be collaborative. And, we want to avoid software that just focuses on rewards or incentives rather than actual leaning and processing of that learning. It is okay to not use technology all the time. It is perfectly fine to use it a couple of days a week. Or one day a week or a couple of times a month if it is the most effective use of the technology. It is a better choice than trying to use it every single day. We really want to make sure that we are focused on high level thinking skills and not the lower level thinking skills.

Defining Equitable Learning with Technology Tools and Why It Matters

The idea of digital equity is vital if we want to have an effective and inclusive learning environment with technology. First, a little bit about what is the difference between digital equity and digital equality?

When we are looking at ***digital equity***, we want all students have the same opportunity to learn with technology tools. It does not necessarily mean they all have the same tool, but they all are given the same opportunity to learn with technology tools. No assumption is made that everybody is on the same page. Students have personalized infrastructure set up for them both inside and outside of the school to support their learning. And this looks different depending on whether students are coming from higher income areas or lower income areas.

On the other hand, ***digital equality*** is the idea that all students have access to exact same devices and software in the school. So the school hands them all a tablet or a laptop or a mobile device and then you have equality, because they all have the same thing. Students are treated the same in terms of assumptions around skills and prior knowledge, and there is very little consideration of whether or not there is broadband or connectivity access outside of school.

We should focus on equity, rather than equality, because equity is what's going to give all students the best opportunity to succeed through technology tools. Equality tends to only give the students in the higher income brackets those opportunities. So, let's take a deeper look at some of the equity gaps that we have:

- Students in lower income areas tend to have less access to certain technology tools and devices than students in higher income areas.
- In addition to access, we also are dealing with issues around connectivity and broadband. Students who come from more privileged areas tend to have easier and more ready access to broadband Wi-Fi access at home, so they can easily do homework that involves technology. We can create mobile buses, with strong Wi-Fi connection, to supply students from low income communities.
- Also, we know that students from high income area usually have sophisticated smart phones, with unlimited apps, as compare to those from low income area. We need to be wary of this when doing BYOD - bring your own device. We cannot assume that all students can do the same things on their devices.

What are some different ways that schools have been able to creatively address inequities?

- What we are seeing more and more in local communities is that schools are creating what they call mobile hotspot programs where students and their families can have the mobile access without paying.
- We also see things like local mapping, where the schools have actually gone out and map out all the different kind of local shops and restaurants with free Wi-Fi access, so that the families can take their devices to these locations and they can use them for information gathering for homework and other purposes.
- We also see community partnerships, where schools are partnering with local businesses and agencies in order to have them help pay for Wi-Fi, and internet access or devices, and there is a great resource on COSN on the internet. A digital equity toolkit with all sorts of great resources for families to use.

Differentiated Learning with Technology Tools

The phrase “Competency based learning” is widely popular with curriculums in Africa. Technology tools have a strong ability to differentiate instruction in the classrooms to ensure students learn at their own competency level. Differentiating learning with technology means students are able to use technology tools to better meet their individual learning needs, and learn in their zone of proximal development (ZPD). The technology

tools are able to meet different levels of learners in different ways and allow them the challenges they need in a just right way - with scaffolds and support in place.

For example, you can have the same, online, article with four different skill levels to meet the needs of different learners through the same piece of software. Also, teachers can put together their own screen cast or video tutorials for students at different levels of learning. For example in the Khan Academy website, there are video tutorials that have the same content but different teaching ways for different learners.

There are many conceptualizations about the use of technology in classrooms

- There should be a 100% parent engagement – without compromise. All kids need access to digital tools and broad band.
- Sometimes the barrier can be scheduling parents who work in farms all day long. Sometimes language barrier can be the issue. However, all efforts should be put in place to neutralize these barriers. It is not enough to open the door and invite parents in. You have to be willing to walk through the door yourself and go into the community.
- Schools should allow their Wi-Fi on so that students living within the premise, on evenings and weekends, can sit outside the school building to use the school network. Students staying away from the premises, with pressing homework, can go to places that have free Wi-Fi for students. Parents, within a particular community, can use their mobile phones to create internet hotspots for other to benefit. However, we can't have kids out at 10 at night looking for Wi-Fi.
- School or district should incorporate parent engagement in technology planning. Efforts should be made to close the digital divide in communities. Again, parents should be engaged to close the digital divide.
- Research shows that the majority of teenagers, at any given time, when they're accessing the Internet, they are basically accessing it through their smart phones. And the same student, who will not have a desktop or a laptop at home. Using an application where students are able to access it through their phones is another way of leveling the playing field.
- Professional learning is the key part of having a tech integration plan. Giving teachers the Triple Es framework can really make a difference. The goal is to generate Technological-Pedagogical-Content Knowledge teachers, and not just content knowledge teachers.

4.10 Recognize that children can struggle with learning

Research shows most African teachers are not trained to identify children with learning disorders or to know how to begin helping them. These disorders can range from dyspraxia (which inhibits basic motor skills like writing) to attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD).

What are some signs of learning disabilities?

Many children have trouble reading, writing, or performing other learning-related tasks at some point. This does not mean they have learning disabilities. A child with a learning disability often has several related signs, and they do not go away or get better over time. The signs of learning disabilities vary from person to person.

Please note that the generally common signs included here are for informational purposes only; the information is not intended to screen for learning disabilities in general or for a specific type of learning disability.

Common signs that a person may have learning disabilities include the following:

- Problems reading and/or writing
- Poor memory
- Problems paying attention
- Trouble following directions
- Clumsiness
- Trouble telling time
- Problems staying organized

A child with a learning disability also may have one or more of the following:

- Acting without really thinking about possible outcomes (impulsiveness)
- “Acting out” in school or social situations
- Difficulty staying focused; being easily distracted
- Difficulty saying a word correctly out loud or expressing thoughts
- Problems with school performance from week to week or day to day
- Speaking like a younger child; using short, simple phrases; or leaving out words in sentences
- Having a hard time listening
- Problems dealing with changes in schedule or situations
- Problems understanding words or concepts

Some of the things teachers and improvement teams can do to provide first-aid help to children suffering from learning disorder include:

- Break learning into small steps
- Administer probes
- Supply regular, quality feedback
- Use diagrams, graphics, and pictures to augment what is said
- Provide ample independent, well-designed intensive practice
- Model instructional practices that you want learners to follow
- Provide prompts of strategies to use, and
- Engage students in process type questions like “How is the strategy working? Where else might you apply it?”

Chapter 5: EVALUATION

EVALUATION

CLASS ASSESSMENT

PROCESS EVALUATION

PROGRAM EVALUATION

Primary Education Secondary Education Tertiary Education

TEAM 2

GOVERNMENT

AFRICAN UNION

What need to be evaluated?
How to monitor and evaluate it
Monitoring and Evaluation matrix

What need to be evaluated?
How to monitor and evaluate it
Monitoring and Evaluation matrix

- What need to be evaluated
- How to monitor and Evaluate it
- Monitoring and Evaluation matrix

- What need to be evaluated?
- How to monitor and evaluate it (data, process, interview)
- Monitoring and Evaluation matrix

INSPECTORS

- What need to be evaluated
- How to monitor and Evaluate it
- Monitoring and Evaluation matrix

TEAM 4

- What need to be evaluated
- How to monitor and Evaluate it
- Monitoring and Evaluation matrix

5.1: Introduction

Evaluation is a systematic determination of a subject's merit, worth and significance, using criteria governed by a set of standards. It can assist an organization, program, design, project or any other intervention or initiative to assess any aim, realizable concept/proposal, or any alternative, to help in decision-making; or to ascertain the degree of achievement or value in regard to the aim and objectives and results of any such action that has been completed. The primary purpose of evaluation, in addition to gaining insight into prior or existing initiatives, is to enable reflection and assist in the identification of future change.

Traditionally, evaluation within the educational context has largely been based on classroom or school evaluation by teachers, and program evaluation by inspectors. The teachers use formative and summative evaluations to assess learners' outcomes and opportunities, while the inspectors use program evaluation to hold the teachers accountable for the effectiveness of the program. Research has shown that the latter approach is weak in maintaining and scaling up changes in the educational sector. To bridge the existing gap between class and program evaluation, Improvement Science introduces a third layer of evaluation called Process evaluation, which brings developmental evaluation to bear on existing techniques. It employs Deming cycle (Plan-Do-Study-Act), iterating between exploration and adaptation, to improve students' outcomes and opportunities.

5.2: The 3 Layers Evaluation Framework

In traditional education settings, as it is the case all over Africa, there are basically two broad categories of evaluation: Class assessment and Program evaluation. The class assessment is usually conducted by teachers or lecturers as formative and summative evaluation; while the program evaluation is usually done by inspectors. The "Improvement Science" approach in addressing the pressing, complex problems in the educational sector introduced a third layer of evaluation: Process Evaluation. The latter, unlike the former evaluation methods that are focused on accountability, is focused on improving the day to day work in schools. It employs Deming cycle (Plan-Do-Study-Act) to improve students' outcomes and opportunities. Thus, instead of two evaluation mechanisms, the DGC program will be subjected to a 3 layers evaluation framework, namely:

- Class Assessment (Teacher)
- Process Evaluation (Team 2 – Learning Hub)
- Program Evaluation (Government + African Union)

5.2.1: Class Assessment (Teacher)

Class Assessment is any activity which checks how well a learner is learning in order to adapt teaching and learning approaches to improve the learner's outcomes and opportunities. Assessment can either be formative or summative or both. Class assessment is usually both formative and summative, while school assessment is basically summative, usually at the end of a school term. At large, both the formative and summative assessment will be focus on evaluating learners' cognitive and participation skills in the DGC program.

The term "Class Assessment" refers to the following context:

5. Primary School
6. Secondary School
7. Tertiary education

5.2.1.1: Formative Assessment:

- It is also referred to as "Continuous Assessment"
- It is an activity that provides students with developmental feedback on their progress during the learning program and informs the design of their next steps in learning.
- It basically involves questioning and practical activities to provide feedback on learning by both teachers and students (peer and self) to improve learning.
- It also involves observation especially regarding attitude change in area such as empathy, cooperation and participation.

5.2.1.2: Summative Assessment:

- Typically end-of-learning assessment tasks such as examinations and tests, to measure and record the level of learning achieved, for progression to the next level or for certification.

5.2.1.3: Cognitive Skills:

- These skills enable learners to identify, describe, organize, interpret, explain, justify and evaluate information and ideas in order to make sense of their experiences and to make decisions about them.
- These skills also enable learners to synthesize information, persuade and argue eloquently.
- Learners with developed cognitive skills can respond to their experiences reasonably and effectively, and when confronted by a public issue, for example, can make and defend decisions about the matter, as a good citizen should do.

5.2.1.4: Participation skills:

- The individual effort made by learners to participate in School's Human Rights Day, Anti-Corruption Day, Peaceful Co-existence Day, and Accountability in Public Service Day. These days are collectively called HAPA Days.
- The personal effort made by learners to get elected into the school parliament (community chair, local government, or government).
- The individual effort made by learners to cooperate with others to monitor and influence the actions and decisions of their school parliament (community chair, local government or government) and to make their representatives in the school parliament (community, local government, or government) accountable to them.

The DGC assessment method will include:

- Traditional method,
- Essay,
- Project artifact,
- Action participation,
- Self-evaluation,
- Peer evaluation.

Note: both Centralized and Continuous school based assessment will be employed.

					EXAMPLES		
ASSESSMENT	Cognitive Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Locate and Recall Integrate 	Grammar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify 	Identify democratic countries in Africa		
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organise 	Organize the various countries in Africa as military, monarch and democratic rule		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creativity Critical thinking 	Logic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse 	Compare and contrast democracy in Ethiopia and the U.S.A		
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate 	Should Africans embrace democracy?		
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interprete 	How is Ethiopia democratic?		
		Rhetoric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synthesize 	How would your life be different if you live under an ideal democratic set up?			
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain (in words or orally) 	Explain how a government function			
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Argue (in words or orally) 	Argue whether or not democracy is good for Africa			
		Participation Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration 	Internal collaboration (In School)		Interacting Skills	<i>Working in small groups and committees, pooling information, exchanging opinions, formulating plans of action.</i>
	External collaboration (In Community)			Monitoring Skills	<i>Holding public officials accountable for using their authority consistently with basic constitutional principles</i>		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication 		Verbal		Influencing Skills	<i>Participating in civic and political groups, for example, student government; youth groups; local, state, and national political parties; and ad hoc advocacy groups.</i>	
			Non Verbal	Spatial			
				Visual			
Auditory							
Kinesthetic							

Remark: Evaluating learners' cognitive and participation skills, within the DGC program, will require monitoring and measuring four types learning approaches, namely:

- Learning by activity (song, drama, game, etc);
- Learning by discussion (HOD, QQ, etc);
- Learning by action (participation in HAPA Days, school parliament, and community);
- Learning by creating artifacts (for example a brochure on Democracy, Election, and Governance in Botswana since independence).

One core technique that will pervade the teaching and learning approaches is *Comparative analysis and appraisal*. By teaching democracy, election, and governance comparatively, we develop among students a useful method of inquiry that helps them to more readily and accurately understand ideas and information about government, politics, and other aspects of human societies and cultures. By using the comparative method, students can develop high-level intellectual skills. They learn, for example, how to organize and interpret information in terms of categories or concepts, to compare and contrast information according to certain categories or standards, and to make appraisals or evaluations of objects according to particular criteria. Thus, to teach democracy comparatively is to prompt students to think analytically and critically about the constitutions, governments, and political activities at home and around the world.

There are three main types of comparisons that teachers, improvement teams, and students should make in their studies of democracy:

1. Use warranted categories as criteria by which to distinguish a democracy from a non-democracy.
2. Use justifiable categories (concepts) to compare and contrast various democratic countries and thereby to appraise the extent to which particular countries are more or less democratic.
3. They should compare and contrast the constitutions, institutions, and participation of citizens in various democratic countries to understand the different ways that democracy is practiced throughout the world.

5.2.1.5 Primary School Assessment

Primary school assessment involves monitoring and measuring pupils' cognitive and participation skills, in the DGC program, through formative and summative assessment. A combine participation and cognitive score of **75%** is considered as pass mark.

ASSESSMENT %	Cognitive Skills	60%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locate and recall • Integrate 	20%		
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity 	20%		
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical thinking 	20%		
	Participation Skills	40%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration 	20%	Internal	10%
					External	10%
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication 	20%	Verbal	10%
Non verbal					10%	

Note: The pass mark is 75%

5.2.1.6 Secondary School Assessment

Secondary school assessment involves monitoring and measuring students' cognitive and participation skills, in the DGC program, through formative and summative evaluation. A combine participation and cognitive score of **80%** is considered as pass mark.

ASSESSMENT %	Cognitive Skills	50%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locate and recall • Integrate 	15%		
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity 	15%		
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical thinking 	20%		
	Participation Skills	50%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration 	25%	Internal	15%
					External	10%
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication 	25%	Verbal	15%
					Non verbal	10%

Note: The pass mark is 80%

5.2.1.7 Tertiary School Assessment

Tertiary school Assessment involves monitoring and measuring students' cognitive and participation skills, in the DGC program, through formative and summative evaluation. A combine participation and cognitive score of **85%** is considered as pass mark.

ASSESSMENT %	Cognitive Skills	45%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locate and recall • Integrate 	10%		
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity 	15%		
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical thinking 	20%		
	Participation Skills	55%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration 	30%	Internal	15%
					External	15%
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication 	25%	Verbal	15%
Non verbal					10%	

Note: The pass mark is 85%

5.2.2: Process Evaluation (Team 2 – Learning Hub)

Process evaluation is systematic, rigorous, and meticulous application of scientific methods to assess the design, implementation, improvement, or outcomes of a program - focusing on the daily processes of the program. It uses Deming Cycle, iterating between exploration and exploitation, to improve change reliably at scale. Process evaluation, unlike Program evaluation that is focused on accountability, is focused on measurement for improvement, and contains three basic measures, namely:

- Outcome Measure: Direct impact on the Aim;
- Process Measure: Indirect impact on the Aim;
- Balance Measure: a ‘side effect’, ‘barrier’ or ‘area to ‘watch’.

Page 167 of Chapter 6 (Piloting) contains a Process Evaluation matrix.

5.2.2.1: Team 2 Evaluation

Team 2 Evaluation refers to process evaluation within the formal sector.

5.2.3: Program Evaluation (Government + African Union)

Program or curriculum evaluation includes studying how teachers and students interact with each other and with a curriculum or syllabus in a particular setting. Usually, unintended, it is confined to investigating only what students have learned or to analyzing lessons plans, and teachers are told to work hard or else. Program evaluation can involve examination of the goals, rationale, and structure of both the planned and the enacted curriculum; a study of the context in which the enacted curriculum occurs (including inputs from parents and the community); and an analysis of the interests, motivations, reactions, and achievements of the students experiencing the program. More or less, Program evaluation is focused on accountability. Both the government (through inspectors) and the AU (through Team 4) shall evaluate the successful and effective implementation of the DGC program.

5.2.3.1: Government Evaluation (Inspector)

The government inspectors from each member state are expected to conduct evaluation of the program to measure its effectiveness. This might involve conducting a joint evaluation with the AU or doing it separately. However, the expectation is that there should be homogeneity of the evaluation matrix used irrespective of country. It should also be noted that in a successful curriculum implementation and evaluation, emphasis should be on learning and development and not just making judgments.

5.2.3.2: African Union Evaluation (Team 4)

Team 4 will evaluate the effectiveness of each team, and work collaboratively with the state inspectors to conduct program evaluation.

Table 5.2.3.2.1: Team 4 Yearly Evaluation Matrix

Evaluation Questions	Anecdotal Records	Expert Review	Implementation Logs	Designer Interviews	Instructor Interviews	Observations	On-Line Data	Portfolios	Tests	Learner Interviews	Learner Logs	Learner Questionnaire
a. What knowledge was learned by learners?												
b. What skills were developed by learners?												
c. What attitudes were formed by learners?												
d. What were learner reactions to the curriculum content?												
e. What were learner reactions to the pedagogical approach used?												
f. What were instructor reactions to the curriculum content?												

Table 5.2.3.2.2: Team 4 End of Term Evaluation Matrix

MEASURES	LEVELS	PARADIGMS	EXAMPLES
REACTION	Students	In and out of the school context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your opinion of the ACDEG program: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. its curriculum, 2. pedagogical approach, and 3. parent/community education? • How can it be improved to produce citizens that better informed, effective and responsible?
	Teachers		
	Parents		
	Community		
KNOWLEDGE	Locate and Recall	Text (Close)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are civic life, politics, elections, and government? • What are the foundations of the African political systems? • What are the roles of citizens in an actual democracy?
	Integrate	Text (Close)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the relationship of Ethiopia to other African nations and to world affairs? • How does a government, established by a Constitution, embody the purposes, values, and principles of actual democracy?
SKILLS	Intellectual skills (Identify, Describe, Explain, Evaluate, Analyze, Persuade, Argue and Synthesize)	Critical thinking (Open)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As an elected president, write a speech on how corruption, hunger, and poverty will be eradicated in your country with a clear roadmap with time frames.
		Creativity (Open)	<p><i>“Using 1 Stone to Kill 7 Birds”</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As aspiring presidential candidates or councilors, learners should produce “Candidate’s Program”, outlining all the problems in their communities, and provide innovative ways to resolve them. This project shall ensure the followings: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Learners meet their academic expectation holistically

			<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Learners acquire extra skills of preparing “Candidate Program” for aspiring political candidates 3. Learners artifacts will inform government policies and interventions 4. AU will use learners artifacts to identify contextual problems in member states and help them reduce the creative tension between reality and expected vision 5. Learners will acquire investigative skills and also be fully aware of the problems in their community 6. Learners’ artifacts will sold to generate income for the learners 7. Learners will transform their communities beyond expectations
	<p style="text-align: center;">Participatory skills (Interact, Monitor and Influence)</p>	Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To what extent are learners working together (communicating, collaborating, and building coalitions), in and out of the school context, to seek consensus, seek compromise, manage conflicts and influence policies?
Collaboration			
<p>DISPOSITION (Organization)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">“Habits of the Heart”</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Values, Attitudes and behaviors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To what extent are learners and parents involved in service learning, raising awareness, and creating artifacts for the community? • To what extent are learners, with parents, working with civic organizations such an electoral body? • To what extent are learners, and parents, encouraging people to vote? • To what extent are learners voting (with parents)? • To what extent is the community as whole informed, effective, responsible and transformable?

Table 5.2.3.2.1: Participatory Skills Matrix

Interacting skills	Scale
1. <i>Working in small groups and committees</i> , pooling information, exchanging opinions, formulating plans of action.	
2. <i>Listening</i> , gaining information, ideas, different perspectives.	
3. <i>Questioning</i> , clarifying information or points of view, eliciting facts and opinions.	
4. <i>Discussing public affairs</i> in a knowledgeable, responsible, and civil manner in school, with neighbors and friends, in community groups and public forums.	
5. <i>Participating</i> in voluntary associations and interest groups, promoting ideas, policies, interests.	
6. <i>Building coalitions</i> , enlisting the support of like-minded individuals and groups to promote candidates, policies.	
7. <i>Managing conflicts</i> through mediation, negotiation, compromise, consensus building, adjudication.	
8. <i>Performing school and community service</i> , serving as a representative or elected leader; organizing a public issues forum; working for one’s religious, civic, or charitable organizations.	
9. <i>Using media resources</i> , obtaining information, exchanging ideas, advocating public policies.	
10. <i>Deliberating on public issues</i> , for example, health care, employment, environmental concerns.	

11. <i>Assessing others' arguments and positions</i> for their validity rather than because of who it is that utters them, remaining calm in the face of opposition.	
Monitoring Skills	Scale
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Listening</i> attentively to fellow citizens, proceedings of public bodies, media reports. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Questioning</i> public officials, experts, and others to elicit information, determine responsibility. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Holding public officials accountable</i> for using their authority consistently with basic constitutional principles. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Following public issues in the media</i>, using a variety of sources, such as television, radio, newspapers, journals, and magazines. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Researching public issues</i>, using computer resources, libraries, the telephone, personal contacts, the media. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Gathering and analyzing information</i> from government officials and agencies, interest groups, civic organizations. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Attending public meetings and hearings</i>, for example, student council, city council and school board meetings, briefings by members of county boards of supervisors, state legislatures, and Congress. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Interviewing</i> people knowledgeable about civic issues, such as local officials, civil servants, experts in public and private associations, members of college and university faculties. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Using electronic resources</i> for acquiring and exchanging information, for example, the Internet, online university services, electronic bulletin boards. 	

Influencing Skills	Scale
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Voting</i>, for example, in class, student body, local, state, national, and special elections. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Informing</i>, for example, furnishing factual data to legislators and policymakers. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Petitioning</i>, for example, calling attention of representative bodies and public officials to grievances and desired changes in public policy, gathering signatures for initiatives or recall. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Writing</i>, for example, letters and “op-ed” pieces, broadsides, pamphlets, or brochure. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Speaking and testifying before public bodies</i>, for example, student body councils, school boards, special districts, state legislatures, Congress. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Supporting or opposing candidates or positions on public issues</i>, for example, contributing time, talent, or money. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Participating in civic and political groups</i>, for example, student government; youth groups; local, state, and national political parties; and ad hoc advocacy groups. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Employing various media to advance points of view on public affairs</i>, for example, participating in online discussions of public issues, writing newspaper and magazine articles, voicing one’s opinion on radio and television talk shows. 	

5.3 Differences between Process Evaluation and Program Evaluation

Table 5.3: Differences between Process Evaluation and Program Evaluation

	PROGRAM EVALUATION [Measurement for Accountability]	PROCESS EVALUATION [Measurement for Improvement]
Why?	Identify exemplary or problematic performers (teachers, schools, districts)	Develop and evaluate change in practice
What?	End of the line outcomes	Outcomes and processes that are the object of change
How often?	Usually collected once a year (after the fact)	Frequently as practice occurs
Testing strategy?	No tests	Sequential tests
Sample size	Obtain 100% available, relevant data	“just enough” data, small sequential samples
Social conditions of use?	Publically available formal, appearance of neutrality and objectivity is key	Data shared in a low-stakes, safe envmt conducive to change
Aim	Comparison, choice, reassurance	Improvement of outcomes

Chapter 6: RESOURCES

6.1: Introduction

Resource is a stock or supply of money, materials, staff, and other assets that can be drawn on by a person or organization in order to function effectively. There are twenty four (24) distinct potential sources of resources for the successful and effective implementation of the ACDEG program. These pools of resources include government, nongovernmental, local, and international sources. However, it highly recommended for the government of each member state to take full responsibility in providing the resources needed for the successful and effective implementation of the program. And since the new curriculum will absorb the existing Civic and Human rights disciplines, the expected funding weight should be insignificant on the governments' shoulders. And apart of Government resources, the AU will mobilize other potential sources of resources, through asset mapping, to assist the governments in their effort to effectively and successfully implement of the program. Through this way, with the AU working hand in gloves with member states, consistent and transparent funding will be ensured for the successful and effective implementation of the program.

It is worth noting that the AU would work with member states to formulate a DGC Financing policy where all member states must adhere to. A sizeable allocation of annual budget for education and the percent for DGC would be made specific and enforced to all member states. While other resources are very importance, the government allocation is very important to show seriousness and commitment. This will encourage other sources to come.

Examples of the twenty four possible resource outcomes include:

Governmental Personnel or Organization:

1. Government individual **financial** resources: This includes finance raised from politicians, parliamentarians, jurists, and law enforcers to support the effective implementation of the program.
2. Government institution **financial** resources: This includes finance provided by the government through the ministry of Education or other related ministries for the successful and effective implementation of the program.
3. Government individual **human** resources: This might include parliamentarians, politicians, jurists, and law enforcers working hand in gloves with school to support the school parliamentary system. The lawmakers and enforcers might also teach specific lessons.

4. Government institution **human** resources: This might include municipalities, councils, police, and gendarmerie working hand in gloves to with schools to support the school parliament and other related activities. Government teachers also belong to this group.
5. Government individual **material** resources: This might include materials supplied by parliamentarians, politicians, jurists, and law enforcers to schools, to support democratic activities. It can be a personal initiative.
6. Government institution **material** resources: This might include materials supplied by the ministry of education (and other related ministries), municipalities, councils, police, and gendarmerie to support the implementation of the ACDEG program in schools.

Non-Governmental Personnel or Organization:

7. Nongovernmental individual **financial** resources: This might include finance raised from local individual within a community such as local philanthropists, artists, writers and athletes for the successful and effective implementation of the program – see asset mapping for specific examples.
8. Nongovernmental organization **financial** resources: This might include finance raised from philanthropic institutions and companies for the successful and effective implementation of the program.
9. Nongovernmental individual **human** resources: This might include activists, bloggers, academicians, and writers working hand in gloves with school to successful implement the program.
10. Nongovernmental organization **human** resources: This might include Refugees’ organizations, Democratic organizations, opposition political parties, service clubs, and Electoral organizations working hand in gloves with schools to support the school parliament and other related activities and teaching.
11. Nongovernmental individual **material** resources: This might include materials supplied by activists, bloggers, academicians, and writers to improve democratic values in schools.

12. Nongovernmental organization **material** resources: This might include materials supplied by Refugees' organizations, Democratic organizations, political parties, service clubs, and Electoral organizations to support the schools' parliaments and other related activities.

International Personnel or Organization:

13. International individual **financial** resources: This might include finance raised from international celebrities, goodwill ambassadors, and philanthropists for the successful and effective implementation of the program.

14. International organization **financial** resources: This might include fund raised from organizations such as the Gate foundation, World Bank, and the Global Partnership for Education.

15. International individual **human** resources: This might include volunteering individuals from abroad to support the implementation of the program.

16. International organization **human** resources: This might include human resources from UNICEF or the Global Partnership for Education to support schools with the school parliament and other related activities.

17. International individual **material** resources: This might include materials sent by individuals from abroad to support the implementation of the program.

18. International organization **material** resources: This might include materials supplied by UNICEF or the Global Partnership for Education to support learning hubs with the successful implementation of the program.

Local Personnel or Organization:

19. Local individual **financial** resources: This might include finance raised from local tycoons and cheer givers in the community for the successful and effective implementation of the program.
20. Local organization **financial** resource: This might include finance raised from local business, banks, and companies in the community for the successful and effective implementation of the program.
21. Local individual **human** resources: This might include local retired politicians who want to share their experiences, and guide the young seeds, in and out of school, with democratic knowledge, skills and dispositions to transformational leaders.
22. Local organization **human** resources: This might include citizen associations working hand in gloves with schools to support democratic activities.
23. Local individual **material** resources: This might include materials supplied by local retired politicians to support schools.
24. Local organization **material** resources: This might include materials supplied by citizen associations to support democratic activities in schools.

6.2: Government Duties and Responsibilities in providing adequate resource for the Implementation of the DGC Curriculum

The resource requirement for the implementation of the DGC curriculum is appropriately consistent with national means. This makes it imperative for the government of each member states to assume full responsibility in providing resources for the program. This means that available resources should be used intensively and efficiently as possible. There is also the strong need for the public-private partnerships to be efficiently developed to expand implementation capacity with particular attention to the needs of poor pupils. The challenge is to structure these partnerships in such a way that they work effectively and that public and private sector partners can contribute in those areas where they are best placed to do so.

6.3: Proposed Distribution of Resource per the DGC Implementation Sectors.

The identified and acquired pool of resources, either separately or collectively, shall be distributed among five distinct implementation strands, namely:

- The preschool sector
- The primary school sector
- The secondary school sector
- The tertiary education sector
- The organization attachment sector, and
- The learning system (learning hub + school) capacity building sector

6.3.1: Resource Distribution Pie graph

The primary, secondary and tertiary education should be given almost the same priority when it comes to financing. The existing body of literature shows that secondary education has always been less financed compared to the other two sectors. Between 1999 and 2004 total aid commitments to education in Sub-Saharan Africa increased by 75% from \$1.2 to \$ 2.1 billion. Virtually all of this increase was allocated to primary and tertiary education, while commitments to secondary education stabilized in dollar terms but declined to about 5% as a share of education aid commitments. This raises important questions on the way policy priorities are translated into actual aid allocations. It is hard to understand why external support to higher education has increased almost as fast as support to primary education while allocations to secondary education are stagnating, especially when countries are aiming to expand access to lower secondary education as part of their goal of providing 8-10 years of basic education.

CHAPTER 7: PILOTING

7.1: What is piloting

Traditionally, piloting is defined as an act of testing, usually once, (a plan, project, etc) before introducing it more widely. In other words, a pilot program (pilot study) also called feasibility study, or experimental trial, is a small-scale experiment that helps an organization learn how a large-scale project might work in practice. To this end, a good pilot program is considered to be one that provides a platform for an organization to test logistics, prove value, and reveal deficiencies before spending a significant amount of time, energy, and money on large project. This understanding of piloting can be represented diagrammatically as shown below:

Figure 7.1.1: Diffusion Enterprise

This approach (moving from small 'A' to big 'B') requires implementing "fast" and learn "slow". This approach, also known as "diffusion enterprise», within the educational context, has been shown by research to be less effective.

On the other hand, Piloting, as recommended by Improvement Science, is a multiple testing endeavor (of a plan, project, etc) that deliberately start small, incrementally increasing the population and contextual environment, to see what works and doesn't work in different sizes of population, gaining sufficient evidence to implement at large scale. This approach, also known as "evolutionary enterprise", or continuous improvement, ensures we learn "fast" and implement "well". This approach is diagrammatically resented as shown below:

Figure 7.1.2: Evolutionary Enterprise

- At A5B0, we learn what works and doesn't works for context A and it population. Lessons learned here do not truly represent what will happen if we move to full scale implementation.
- At A4B1, the lessons learned at A5B0 are implemented to a relative wider context and population. Here, we will learn the first lesson of what will happen if we increase the sample population.
- At A3B2, the lessons learned at A4B1 are implemented to a bigger context and population. Here, we will learn the second lesson of what happens if we increase the sample population further.
- At A2B3, the lessons learned at A3B2 are implemented to a bigger context and population. Here, we will learn the third lesson of what happens if we increase the sample population further.
- At A1B4, the lessons learned at A2B3 are implemented to a bigger context and population. Here, we will learn the fourth lesson of what happens if we increase the sample population further.
- At A0B5, full–scale implementation, we clearly have a picture of what works and doesn't work, and how to improve it at large scale.

7.2: Piloting within the Educational Sector

Piloting, as a means of carrying out reform, within the school context has seen four major transformations: from Performance Management approach to Evidence-Based Practice Movement approach to School Based Learning Communities approach, and to Improvement Science approach. These approaches represent the four major ways of piloting reforms in the educational sector.

1. Performance Management Approach (PMA)

The Performance management approach pilot once and implement at full scale. It then focuses on accountability to maintain or drive change – teachers are evaluated periodically. The strength of this method is that it focused our attention on data. But there is no working theory of practice improvement in the strategy. Educators are told this is where you should go, work harder to fill the gaps or else.

2. Evidence-Based Practice Movement Approach (EBPMA)

This approach carries out several number of piloting testing or trials over a specific length of time – say five years – and then stop. It then focuses on the fidelity implementation of approved practices irrespective of context, which always changes. Like Performance Management, teachers' accountability is brought in to bear to maintain change. Hence, like the former, no theory of improvement strategy exists after fidelity implementation.

3. School-Based Learning Communities Approach (SBLCA)

In contrast to evidence-based practice movement, School-based learning communities, or communities of practice, tend to focus on the day-to-day problems of improving work in classrooms, schools, and districts. It presents a significant shift from studying programs to addressing the specific problems of practice that educators often confront on daily basis. This approach has endless number of piloting, due to changing context, but with no specific direction in mind.

Also, the research base and empirical grounding for these efforts may appear less rigorous. Most important, these communities have weak mechanisms for detailing this practitioner knowledge and then testing it and refining it under more diverse circumstances. As a result, what gets learned here tends to live and die with those who have learned it. There is no real mechanism for a practical knowledge base to grow out of all of this.

- ❖ **Note:** Each of these three approaches to reform has distinctive strengths, but none alone, or even in combination, will help us close the creative tension gap between current realities and the aspired vision of the ACDEG charter.

4. *Improvement Science Approach (ISA)*

Improvement Science approach uses Evolutionary enterprise approach of pilot testing. Just like School Based Learning Communities approach, it recognizes the strong need to pay attention to the changing face of context while pilot testing. But unlike SBLCA, it is guided by a specific Aim statement which deliberately starts small and incrementally grows within the frame of a learning hub. And unlike performance management approach, ISA sees the strong need to support teachers on daily basis. There is a lot of scaffolding in this approach that reduce errors.

Not long ago, Evidence based strategies was deemed as the perfect approach for successful education reform. However, its emphasis on fidelity implementation paying less attention to the sensitivity of the applying context became its major signature vulnerability. Evolutional enterprise understands the need to “adopt, adapt, or discard” an evidence based technique that is not responding to the context in question. As such, this approach to reform involves adaptation and innovation as recommended by literature. With the evolutional enterprise approach, evidence to implement nationwide does not come from a single experiment, but rather a series of experiments conducted over time and across contexts. More still, this approach recognizes the strong need for broad communication of challenges and achievements, public discussion of policy options and transparency in decision making as key ingredients for effective implementation strategies.

7.3: *Planning DGC Piloting (Using Improvement Science Approach)*

Piloting within the improvement science paradigm first and foremost requires formulating the problem we wish to address. It is only by identifying the core specific problem(s) that intervention will yield good fruits.

7.3.1: *Framing the problem:*

In 2015 at Abuja, Nigeria, a group of experts identified some key social problems impeding the continent’s political, economic and social growth, namely:

- wide spread human rights abuses, and unconstitutional take of government;
- rampant spread of conflict, and alarming corruption;
- poor accountability in public services, and high election rigging culture;
- Lack of citizenship (poorly informed, and unpatriotic citizens)

They came to the conclusion that the Civic and Human Rights education in the continent were not properly addressing those problems. Hence, a new subject on democracy, election and governance should be created.

7.3.1.1 The Problem:

Why has the current Civic, Social Studies, and Human rights education in Africa been unable to arrest the continent' pressing social problems?

- Why? Because of poor subject content scope, sequence and priorities
- Why? Because of poor pedagogical approach, teachers' absenteeism, and poor integration into other learning subjects.
- Why? Because of poor extra-curriculum activities to put civic values into practice.
- Why? Because of poor “parent and community education on civic cultures
- Why? Because of lack of collective effort, with a specific aim statement, among international and local bodies working in the continent to improve civic and human rights education.
- Why? Because of students' mindsets about the discipline
- Why? Because of poor effort from the board of education and principal in offering professional development and materials to teachers
- Why? Because of lack of political will by governing elites to provide a secure environment for a comprehensive civic education to grow.

7.3.2 DRIVER DIAGRAM

7.3.2.1 Change Packages

In all, there are twenty two (22) change ideas to be effected in order to attain the vision Africa Union wants to see in the continent in terms of democracy, election and governance. These change ideas are arranged in eight (8) packages. And each change idea has a Plan-Do-Study-Act template. To this end, each change idea will be subjected to Outcome, Process, and Balance measures.

Change package number 1: Improve content's scope, sequence, and coefficient

- Civic and Human rights education are merged into one subject called Democracy and Good Citizenship. The new subject builds on existing foundation with a wider scope that reflects continent's pressing needs at holistic level. The 2015 meeting in Abuja, of thirty African experts, from the Ministry of Education, identified the content of the new discipline.
- Research shows that 'Linear sequencing' is relatively weak compared to 'Circular' and 'Spiral' sequencing. The DGC curriculum employs both circular and spiral sequencing.
- In most African countries, Civic and Human rights education is Coefficient 1 or 2, while Physics and Math are Coefficient 5 respectively. Social issues should have the same weight as scientific issues, if not more. It is paramount to make DGC coefficient 4 or 5.

Change package number 2: Improve teaching capacity

- Research has made an urgent and pressing call for teachers to use learner-centered pedagogy. By moving from sage-on-stage to guide-on-the-side, teaching capacity is enhanced and extended to contextual environment. By employing student-centered pedagogy, grounded in research, pupils will develop higher democratic values and practices.
- Focusing on teachers' absenteeism is another important way of improving teaching capacity. Ensuring that all teachers are present in classrooms, not just DGC teachers, with the intention of fostering DGC values, higher output is secured.
- Integrating the DGC's objectives into other academic disciplines is a key factor, not just in nurturing democratic values in pupils but also teachers.

Change package number 3: Improve School Programme activities

- School programme activities such school parliament, weekly celebration of human rights day, Anti-corruption day, Accountability in public service day, and monthly celebration of peaceful co-existence day will drastically improve pupils' participation and cognitive skills in governance, election, and democracy. Also, having students stage out public dramas in democratic issues will produce better informed citizens.
- The school parliament ensures that pupils are familiar with concepts such as free, fair, open and competitive elections; representatives; majority, minority; and the protection of minority.
- Weekly celebration of Human Rights Day (HRD) will remind the pupils of their obligations and duties to uphold human rights values.
- Weekly celebration of Anti-Corruption Day (ACD) calls on pupils to eliminate corruption from Africa- an unfortunate malice that has been creating havoc in the continent.
- Weekly celebration of Peaceful Co-existence Day (PCD) calls on pupils to cultivate peace in themselves and in others.
- Monthly celebration of Accountability in Public Service Day (APSD) will remind pupils of their obligations and duties to be accountable in public services.
- Pupils and university students would put up monthly public dramas to sink democratic values in their societies.

Change package number 4: Improve Parent-Community education

- Provide Parent-Community education, enlighten the police and other law enforcing authorities, and invite chiefs, community, and religious leaders to carry out the enlightening campaign every two weeks.
- Research shows that the majority of children who experience physical punishment (or corporal punishment) are in Africa. This disciplinary approach is associated with authoritarian mindset. Moving away from the authoritarian mindset to a democratic mindset will require that parents, families, neighbors, and communities are provided with the necessary schema, language, and tools to make this transition. Education begins at home, and so also democracy begins at home. A parent-community education is highly recommended to attain the ACDEG visions.

- Inviting Police and other law enforcing bodies into the equation will remind them of their duties and obligations to uphold human rights values and promote democratic values in their communities.
- Religious leaders have a very strong influence on society, leveraging their influence is paramount.
- Inviting chiefs and community leaders to embody the ACDEG visions, and to organize monthly meetings with their subjects to make them own and propel the vision.

Change package number 5: Tailor other organizations to the Aim statement

- Invite organizations (international, local, government, and nongovernmental) and share the AIM statement with them in order to generate a stronger synergy for a greater output. By sharing the AIM statement with other organizations in the field, they are invited to support the effort towards a fixed timeline and expectations.

Change package number 6: Improve learners' capacity

- A significant proportion of primary and secondary school pupils think civic and human rights education is for adults, others consider it to be toxic and full of lies, and they don't need to take it seriously. By making them responsible in school and community activities, they will begin to take ownership of the DGC subject.
- Getting learners to sign a contract at the beginning of the program, promising to do well in the subject, is one way of improving their mode per the subject.
- Introducing learners to the concept of Growth Mindset is another way of improving their capacity not only per DGC but the entire academic disciplines.
- Provide equity in school through free meal program during break time is another way of improving their capacity.
- Exploring learners' means of transportation to school and enhancing it, is another way of providing equity.
- Map and reduce learners' absenteeism

Change package number 7: Improve administrators' and teachers' training capacity

- Invite the school principals, inspectors, academic boards, and teachers' training institutes to explore the novelty of using Computing Value Framework, 5 Essential Framework, Positive and Inclusive value Framework, and Improvement Science Framework to improve learners' outcomes and opportunities.
- The principal should do the following:
 - Ensures strong supportive relationship with parents, teachers, and community.
 - Work hand-in-glove with teachers to improve instruction.
 - Challenge teachers out of their comfort zones
 - Set higher, but achievable, expectations for learners and align resources.
 - Cultivate leadership in teachers, parents, and the community.
 - Ensures there is a strong relationship between teachers, parents, and community.
 - Provide time and space for teachers to improve
 - Ensures teachers provide a plan at the beginning of the academic year on how they wish to improve themselves.
- The school inspection role should change to enablers of teachers - not merely holding teachers accountable but help them improve their practice on daily basis.
- The school of education should expedite the pressing needs to improve the educational sector and improve governance in the continent.

Change package number 8: Introduce DGC as a course in tertiary education

- Create and implement a DGC course in tertiary education that will be study by all first year students, irrespective of department or faculty.
By taking a course at the tertiary level, students will once again be reminded of their duties and responsibilities to uphold human rights values, fight corruption, ensures accountability in public services, cement peaceful co-existence, and participate in democratic processes.

7.3.2.2: Assess Priority of Change ideas

The success in curriculum implementation relies on several factors such as: political will; national school environment; availability of resources; teaching-learning methodologies; evaluation strategies; sociocultural setting; and attitudes of learners, teachers and other stakeholders involved in the process. The successful implementation of the new DGC curriculum critically depends on 22 change ideas.

The change ideas, as shown in the driver diagram, are assigned ‘Impact’ and ‘Implementation’ priorities. Some of the change ideas will be easy to implement, while others will be hard. And some of the change ideas might cost more than others. However, it is important to note that all of them will have the same impact on the final outcome. A system only produces what it is designed to produce. By focusing on each component of a system and improving it, the output is equally improved.

7.3.3: Team Formation

Basically, each change package constitutes a team. And the size of a team might vary from two to twenty. In all, there are four teams, and each team has a coordinator or coordinators. Team 0 consists of those who designed the DGC program. Team 1 consists of members of “change package two, three, six, seven, and eight”. This team will be responsible for implementing the DGC program in schools. Team 2 consists of members of “change package four and five”. This team will be responsible for implementing the DGC program out of the school context. Team 3 (probably made up of the sponsors) will be responsible for evaluating team 1 and 2. Team 0, 1, 2, and 3 collectively make a Learning Hub, and when they partner with schools, they form a learning system. The precise members of a team 1 and 2 will be chosen after the piloting country has been approved. It is also possible for a member to be in more than one team.

Team 0, (Name:, Profession:, Responsibility:))

-,,
-,,
-,,

Team 1, (Name:, Profession:, Responsibility:))

-[Primary school]
-[Secondary school]
-[Tertiary education]

Team 2, (Name:, Profession:, Responsibility:))

-,,
-,,
-,,

Team 3, (Name:, Profession:, Responsibility:))

-,,
-,,
-,,

The Learning Hub (Team 0, 1, 2, and 3)

Figure 7.3.3: The Learning Hub

7.3.4: Flow Chart: A flow chart is a visual representation of the steps and decisions needed to solve a problem.

7.3.4.1: ACDEG Program Flow Chart

7.3.4.1.1: The 3 Days Workshop [Training of Trainers]

3 DAYS WORKKSHOP
The 4 Days Workshop shall focus on Sharing and Owning the DGC program, and exploring the Seven Basic Contextual Conditions for effective change and, in particular, for successful curriculum implementation
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Share and Own the DGC program
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Clarity among participants about and identification with new goals and role expectations;• Ability of participants to fulfil the new role expectations;• Availability of adequate resources;• Compatible organizational or social envelope for innovation;• Deliberate process of role socialization, and considerable;• Time, coordination, support, and encouragement; as well as• School leadership in assuring the presence and maintenance of these conditions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Communication Strategy (among team members and between teams)• Look at the unit and lesson plans• Site – Specific information

7.3.4.2: Learner Flow Chart

7.3.4.3: An Example of a Teacher's Flow Chart

7.3.5: Data Collection and Measurement

7.3.5.1: Measurement Strategy

Aim Statement: By the end of the 2022/2023 academic year, at least 90% of the learners who have had contact with the ACDEG program will report increase knowledge and attitude in democratic and human rights dispositions.

Type Outcome, Process & Balance Measures	Name of Measure	Operational definition	Data Collection Methods/sampling/schedule	Reporting: Format & Frequency (Who report to: Sponsor / Project Team / Others)
OUTCOME				
PROCESS				
BALANCE				

Outcome Measure: Direct impact on the Aim

Process Measure: Indirect impact on the Aim

Balance Measure: a 'side effect', 'barrier' or 'area to watch'

7.3.6: Data Analyzing Tools

The following tools will be used to elucidation the data:

- Histogram
- Pie Chart
- Run Chart
- Peroto Chart
- Control Chart

7.3.8: Potential Constraints

Considering the school as the unit of change, we can think of it as having two important dimensions that affect individual's and organization's change efforts: the physical features, such as the size and arrangement of the facility, and the resources, policies, structures and schedules that shape the staff's work; and the people factors, which include the attitudes, beliefs, and values of the individuals involved as well as the relationships and norms that guide the individuals' behavior. **Note:** It is clear from the below list of Potential Constraints that reculturing and restructuring of the school have to be a never-ending process, and that support networks around the school have to drive the process – Learning Hub.

7.3.9: DGC Project Charter Template

Version X, Updated xx/xx/xx

What is the problem we hope to solve? Why are we getting the results we are currently getting?

Problem Description

(Broadly describe what problematic outcome has been observed. Provide any necessary background information and introduce the problem, where in the organization it is located, and who is impacted by it)

.....

.....

Rationale for the Improvement Work

(Define why this project should be pursued. Make a powerful case to all stakeholders about why improvement is needed.)

.....

.....

Problem Investigation Plans

(Identify specific activities you plan to use to develop your understanding of the problem. What do you still need to understand better, and how do you plan to learn it? Will you... leverage data about the problem? Engage users? Visualize current practice?)

Leverage data about the problem:

Engage users:

Visualize current practices:

What specifically are we trying to accomplish?

Aim Statement

(What will be improved? How much? For whom?By when? This will likely change as the project evolves.)

By June 2022, we will increase from 10 to 90 the percentage of primary school pupils that successfully demonstrate democratic values, such as tolerance, respect, and willingness to learn, within nine months of continuous schooling.

How will we know if a change is an improvement?

(Identify potential measures for the project. Provide a brief description of how and when data will be collected).

Process measures will include
Balance measures will include
Outcome measures

What changes might we introduce and why?

(Identify initial change ideas for achieving the above aim. Include a preliminary theory of practice improvement if it exists.)

If we want to increase **from 10 to 90 the percentage of primary school pupils in Africa that successfully demonstrate democratic values, such as tolerance, respect, and willingness to learn, within nine months of continuous schooling, by June 2022**, we need to **fine-tune the Instructional approach by focusing on the use of drama, songs and project based learning** and one way to do that is to use **Improvement teams** which involves the creation of learning hubs

If we want to **increase from 10 to 90 the percentage of primary school pupils in Africa that successfully demonstrate democratic values, such as tolerance, respect, and willingness to learn, within nine months of continuous schooling, by June 2022**, we need to **support learners to productively persist by focusing on ATTENDANCE** and one way to do that is by **assigning Improvement teams to check-in regularly with learners and providing a space for getting absent learners back on track with remedial work.**

Team Membership

(Who is on the improvement team and what knowledge/skills do they bring? Who is the executive sponsor, and what type of resources and support can s/he bring to the project? What subject matter experts will provide support to the team?)

Name	Roles	Responsibilities
TBD		

Project Plan: Timeline, Resource Needs, Constraints

(When will the project take place and what will be the major areas of work? Are there key deadlines or milestones to be accomplished within the project? What resources will be needed to launch and sustain the project?)

Project Phase	Dates	Resources/Supports Needed
PLAN		
DO		
STUDY		
ACT		

Additional Notes:

(Include any additional relevant information about the project. Consider noting any key opportunities or constraints you anticipate in the work.)

7.3.10 Proposed Piloting Countries

The proposed piloting countries include:

- Algeria, Lesotho;
- Nigeria, Comoros; and
- Central African Republic.

The selected countries have signed and ratified the ACDEG charter – with due consideration for regional balance. Algeria from North Africa. South Africa. Lesotho from Southern Africa. Nigeria from West Africa. Comoros from East Africa. And Central African Republic (CAR) from Central Africa. Research shows that French speaking African countries suffer the most from civil unrest and poverty – hence, the ratio 3:2 in the selection process.

Algeria has been a hotbed of political unrest in recent years. The country is considered to have sparked the protest that ended the one party system in Africa. It was also strongly involve the Arab spring that swept the Arab world and change its morphology. And recently, in 2019, the Algerians took again to the streets to force the long-time ruling Abdelaziz Bouteflika from power. One of the greatest challenges for the ACDEG program will be its implementation in the Arab soil, and Algeria provides a fine context to test the program.

7.3.10.1 Case Study No 2: Algeria

Algeria, officially known as the People's Democratic Republic of Algeria, is a country in the Maghreb region of North Africa. With an area of 2,381,741 square kilometers (919,595 sq mi), Algeria is the largest country in the African Union and Arab World, and the tenth-largest country in the world. With an estimated population of over 42 million, it is among the ten most populous states in Africa. It share borders with Tunisia, Libya, Morocco, Western Saharan territory, Mauritania, Mali, Niger, and the Mediterranean Sea. It has 48 provinces and 1,541 communes.

Interestingly, Algeria has the highest human development index of all non-island African countries. It is also one of the largest economies on the continent, based largely on energy exports. The country has the second largest oil reserves in Africa and the 16th largest in world, while it has the ninth largest reserves of natural gas. Sonatrach, the national oil company, is the largest company in Africa, supplying large amounts of natural gas to Europe. Algeria has one of the largest militaries in Africa and the largest defence budget. It is a member of the African Union, the Arab League, OPEC, the United Nations, and the Arab Maghreb Union, of which it is a founding member. Algeria is also included in the European Union's Neighborhood Policy (ENP) which aims at bringing the EU and its neighbors closer. Women make up 70% of the country's lawyers and 60% of its judges and also dominate the field of medicine. Increasingly, women are contributing more to household income than men. 60% of university

students are women, according to university researchers. Ahlam Mosteghanemi, an Algerian, is the most widely read woman writer in the Arab world. Education is officially compulsory for children between the ages of six and 15. And Algeria is considered to have achieved universal primary education with a 97% Primary Net Enrollment Rate in 2015.

However, given its economic might and a woman-centric societal image, there exist deep socio-economic and political problems in Algeria. One such problem has to do with women's rights. There are endless reported cases of mob violence against women, which has a long history and is deeply interwoven into the fabric of the society. Algeria has been categorized by Freedom House as "not free". Homosexuality is illegal in Algeria. High level corruption, the lack of Media and Press freedom has been some of the source of fuel for the social unrest that has plagued Algeria over the years. There are also strong calls for the government to improve the quality of its education.

In April 2019, an unprecedented pro-democracy movement (peaceful "smile revolution"), who have protesting for months, unseated the long-time ruling Abdelaziz Bouteflika from power. The new authorities in Algeria now know they can no longer ignore the citizens they represent. The New President Abdelmadjid Tebboune has promised deep reforms, which includes among others changing the mode of governance. Algeria is in search of a new direction (the youths have discovered a new voice, the voice of peaceful debate and exchange of ideas) and the ACDEG program can help them in this quest.

7.3.10.2 Case study No 8: Lesotho

Lesotho, officially the Kingdom of Lesotho, is an enclaved country within the border of South Africa. Along with the Vatican City and San Marino, it is one of only three independent states completely surrounded by the territory of another country. Its population is around 2 million people and the official language is Sesotho. Its capital and largest city is Maseru. It is a member of the AU, UN, SADC, and the Commonwealth of Nations.

Water and diamonds are Lesotho's significant natural resources. The economy is based on agriculture, livestock, manufacturing and mining. Lesotho is the largest exporter of garments to the US from sub-Saharan Africa. The country is unique in that while most developing countries have education systems that favor men, women have a higher educational attainment rate than men do.

However, half of its population exists below the poverty line. Domestic abuse, sexual violence, and lack of social mobility are persistent issues. An Afrobarometer poll conducted in 2018 showed 25% believe that it is justifiable for a husband to beat his wife. A study in 2014 showed that 86% of women reported experiencing some kind of violence in their lifetime. Even though the government has made progress in decreasing the

prevalence of violence and sexual abuse against women, much remain to be done. According to Lesotho's Minister of Gender and Youth, this problem is difficult to combat due to "a culture of silence and stigmatization associated with the scourge". The country has the second highest rate of HIV prevalence in the world, with 23.8% of the population infected. The number of women affected greatly outnumbers the number of men infected. Only 23 percent of the population uses birth control. Women seeking or receiving abortions are often arrested. There are also claims that while Lesotho is signatory to regional and international Protocols on gender equality, customary laws still prevail. Complaints about child labor and the rights for people with disabilities have refused to go away.

Bringing out the best in Lesotho will require implementing the ACDEG program as soon as possible, with the vigor, rigor, and commitment that its merits.

7.3.10.1 Case study No 1: Nigeria

Nigeria, officially the Federal Republic of Nigeria, is a country located in West Africa. It shares borders with Niger, Chad, Cameroon and Benin. The country is divided into 36 states, with Abuja as the capital, and 774 local government areas. It is the most populous country in Africa with an estimated population of 206 million people. The country has the 3rd largest youth population in the world after India and China. It also has the 5th largest Muslim population in the world and 6th largest Christian population in the world. The official language is English. The country is a member of the AU, UN, ECOWAS, OPEC, MINT, and the Commonwealth of Nations.

Nigeria is a country blessed with natural resources such as petroleum, natural gas, gold, coal, bauxite, tantalite, tin, iron ore, limestone, niobium, lead and zinc. It is the largest economy in Africa and one of the world's largest oil producers. It is considered to be an emerging market by the World Bank and has also been identified as an emerging global power. Next to petrodollars, remittance is the second biggest source of foreign exchange earnings in the country. It has one of the fastest growing telecommunications markets in the world. The tourism and manufacturing industries are also growing. The country is the United States' largest trading partner in sub-Saharan Africa. Its tropical rainforest is believed to contain the world's largest diversity of butterflies.

Despite its riches, many Nigerians continue to live below the poverty line. An estimated 40% of the population lives with absolute poverty. The situation has been made worse by rampant conflicts - left, right and center. In the North-East, Boko Haram continues to claim lives and terrorize citizens. In the middle belt, recurring violence between Muslim herdsmen and Christian farmers continues to fuel religious tensions and claim

hundreds of innocent lives. And in the south, armed militants in Niger Delta continues to operate with impunity, kidnapping foreign workers, attacking oil-producing facilities, and killing government forces.

In the light of these unfortunate circumstances and others, Nigeria's human rights record remains strongly poor. According to the U.S. Department of State, the most significant human rights problems are: use of excessive force by security forces; impunity for abuses by security forces; arbitrary arrests; prolonged pretrial detention; judicial corruption and executive influence on the judiciary; rape, torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment of prisoners, detainees and suspects; harsh and life threatening prison and detention centre conditions; human trafficking for the purpose of prostitution and forced labour; cyber fraud, societal violence and vigilante killings; child labour, child abuse and child sexual exploitation; domestic violence; discrimination based on ethnicity, region and religion.

Oil spillage and other environmental problems have been source of conflict for the country. Some of the environmental issues include poor waste management, deforestation, soil degradation and climate change. Haphazard industrial planning, increased urbanization, poverty and lack of competence of the municipal government are seen as the major reasons for high levels of waste pollution in major cities in Nigeria. The country has recorded notable strides in its fight against corruption but much remain to be done. Official corruption is considered a fact of life.

It is evident that the Nigerian government faces the growing challenge of preventing Africa's most populous country from breaking apart along ethnic and religious lines. Achieving long lasting stability, peace and prosperity in Nigeria will require implementing the ACDEG program as earlier as possible, with the vigor, rigor, and commitment that its merits.

7.3.10.10 Case study No 10: Comoros

The Comoros, officially the Union of the Comoros, is an island country in the Indian Ocean located at the northern end of the Mozambique Channel. It shares maritime borders with Madagascar, Tanzania, Mozambique, and Seychelles. The capital and largest city is Moroni. The country

has three official languages (Comorian, French, and Arabic) with an estimated population 832,322 people. It is a member of the AU, UN, SADC, the Arab League, La Francophonie, OIC, and the Indian Ocean Commission.

Interestingly, the island is the world's largest producer of ylang-ylang, a plant whose extracted essential oil is used in the perfume industry; some 80% of the world's supply comes from the Comoros. The island also exports species such as vanilla, cinnamon, and cloves. Agriculture, including fishing, hunting, and forestry, accounts for about 50% of GDP, and employs more than 56% of the labor force. Remittances from about 300,000 Comorians contribute about 25% of the country's GDP.

With constant political instability, the population of the Comoros lives with the worst income inequality of any nation. The country has experienced more than 20 attempted coups since independence in 1975, most recently in 2013. It also ranks in the worst quartile on the Human Development Index. Government institutions are considered to be deficient and inefficient. As of 2008 about half the population lived below the poverty line of US\$1.25 a day. The country imports roughly 70% of its food. There are also issues of restricted press and media freedom. Same-sex sexual acts are illegal. The quality of its education also begs for improvement.

From all indication, a developed human capital is the key to unlock Comoros' longing stability, peace and prosperity. This can be obtained by implementing the ACDEG program as soon as possible, with the vigor, rigor, and commitment that its merits.

7.3.10.11: Case Study No 11: Central African Republic

Central African Republic (CAR) is a landlocked country located at the central part of Africa (almost the precise center of Africa). It shares borders with Chad, Cameroon, Sudan, South Sudan, and the Democratic Republic of Congo. It has a total land area of about 622,984 square kilometers, of which 2.9% is arable land. It is made up of 16 prefectures. The Central African Republic is a member of African Union, United Nations, Economic Community of Central African States, Organization Internationale de la Francophonie, and the Non-Aligned Movement

Interestingly, CAR is a country abundantly rich in natural resources such as diamond, gold, cobalt, lumber, uranium, timber, crude oil, and hydropower. Despite its small size of population, CAR is one of the most culturally rich countries in Africa, with a beautiful blend of several cultures, ethnic, and racial groups. It remains one of the few countries in Africa today where traditional African belief system (or voodoo) reigns supreme. Traditional believers make up about 30% of the population. It is a country with staggering rare natural beauty and some wonderful wildlife.

However, despite its abundance mineral resources and rich forest, CAR remains one of the poorest countries in the world, with the lowest GDP per capita at purchasing power parity in the world as of 2017. As of 2019, according to the Human Development Index (HDI), the country has the second lowest level of human development, ranking 188th out of 189 countries. It is also estimated to be the unhealthiest country in the world, and the worst country to be young. Central African Republic is also one of the world's least developed nations. The capital Bangui has remained frozen in time since 1970s. The country has experienced several periods of political instability since its independence from France in 1960. Without doubt, CAR faces so many challenges and this includes extreme poverty and hunger, corruption, human rights abuses, poor education (high illiteracy rate especially among girls), deadly HIVS/AIDS, and environmental problems such as deforestation and desertification.

Not so long ago CAR was one of the best places in Africa for encounters with huge forest elephants and western lowland gorillas, and the best place in the world, some say, to see butterflies. Decades of power struggle and civil wars have dug deep trenches on the beautiful face of CAR. However, with a new elected government in place, peace is gradually creeping back into Central African Republic. Perhaps, more than any other country in Africa, CAR provides a fertile soil for the ACDEG program to grow and showcase its prowess.

UNITING FOR THE PROSPERITY OF CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC

KEY STAKEHOLDERS MEETING [date: 11/05/2022]

	Government Institutions (GIs)	International Organizations (IOs)	Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs)	Local Organizations (LOs)
DGC curriculum Partners (DGCCP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Both Ministry of Basic and Higher Education Ministry of Women, Children and Family 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UNICEF, EU, GPE, OCHA, i3d, MUNISCA, OMS, USAID 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Save the Children, Islamic Relief, Christian Aid, GAVI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BEKOU, URU, ENABEL, KYBS, KWATI, AECE, FFPD
Parent Education Partners (PCP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry of National Reconciliation and Social Cohesion & Ministry of Social dialogue, Ministry of Digital Economy and Communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UNHCR, IOM, WHH, EU, SOS Village, UNDP, OXFAM, OAP, CORDAID, CICR, FAO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan International, Mercy Corps, HD, EDEN, INSO, FairMed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mama Clair, CCDS, WALT, LCDH, AFJDSC, ABG, OFE, CB
Out-of-School Youth Program Partners (OSYPP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minister of Youth and Sport Minister of Employment and Vocational Training Ministry of Solidarity and the Fight against Poverty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AU, PAM, MSF, IRAD, ABA, MSF, FIS, SI, UNSC, UNPF, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FCA, ACF, SCG, PUI, AiCL, YVE, PDW, COOPADEM, AA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BE OKOZO, FANGO YAKA, SOBOU, ANEA, RMB, MAH

KEY ASSET MEETING [date: 14-16/05/2022]								
	GIs	IOs	NGOs	LOs	Activists	Philanthropists	Artists	Athletes
DGCCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educators Researchers Economists Jurists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU, UNICEF, MUNISCA, ABA, IDA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mercy corp CRS Oxfam FIS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SSVP AFDD AVCLCP HHI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tatiana Vivienne Cécile Guéret Marguerite Kofio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fidèle Gouandjika Ibrahim Mo Aliko Dangote 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Makombo Bamboté Joseph Akouissoune Ozaguin 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geoffrey Kondogbia Wilfried Zahibo
PCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economists Parliamentarians. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GPE MSF FAO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> P. Urgence FSD IRAD GAVI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DOC AES APDC AJMDC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bernadette Gomina Catherine Samba-Panza 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Baba Ahmadou Danpullo Warren Buffett 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Charles Perrière Gabriel Danzi Jerome Ramedane 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yannick Zachée Romain Sato Christian Nassi
OSYPP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Police Defense Development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> USAID UN Police CORDAID 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NDI AFD OIF 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACCE AMPJF AMSS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adrienne Yabouza 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tony Elumelu Bill Gate Madala Kouma 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sammy Massamba Léandre-Alain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Francky Mbotto Chloe Sauvourel

KEY PRACTITIONERS MEETING (3 Days Workshop) [date: 17-19/05/2022]								
DGCCP								
PCP								
OSYPP								

1 st IMPLEMENTATION PHASE [02/09/2022 – 06/12/2022]								
Zone	Doing	Study	Act	Plan	Do	Study	Act	
Bangui	Date:02/09/22	Date:19/09/22	Date:19/09/22	Date:20/09/22	Date:21/09/22	Date:10/10/22	Date:11/10/22	
2 nd IMPLEMENTATION PHASE [11/01/2023 – 16/04/2023]								
Zone	Doing	Study	Act	Plan	Do	Study	Act	
Bangui to Bambari	Date:16/01/23	Date:23/01/23	Date:23/01/23	Date:24/01/23	Date:25/01/23	Date:13/02/23	Date:13/02/23	
3 rd IMPLEMENTATION PHASE [13/05/2023 – 31/07/2023]								
Zone	Doing	Study	Act	Plan	Do	Study	Act	
Bangui to Birao	Date:03/05/23	Date:22/05/23	Date:22/05/23	Date:23/05/23	Date:24/05/23	Date:12/06/23	Date:12/06/23	

KEY STAKEHOLDERS MEETING: Creating awareness, buy-in, and call for action.

KEY ASSET MEETING: Building the CAPACITY to Implement Well.

KEY PRACTITIONERS MEETING: Looking at lesson plans, support materials, and forming groups

Chapter 8: CONCLUSION

Thus far, due to differences in history, culture and policy choices, the state of civic education varies dramatically across the continent. Most often ideology rather than pragmatism determines civic education benchmarks in the continent. It is evident that such organic benchmarks have sown seeds of some the terrible malice that have plague the continent and stifle economic growth. On the other hand, where benchmarks are based on pragmatism, peaceful coexistence and accelerated economic growth is observed. The AU's aim is to support member states to attain maximum economic growth and stability, by setting basic threshold frequency in civic education for all African learners, irrespective of geopolitical identify and socio-economic status. Achieving such an ambitious dream will require all to work collaboratively together to effectively and efficiently to implement the ACDEG program with the vigour and commitment that it merits.

It is paramount to note that a realistic implementation of the DGC curriculum will disrupt the prevailing obedience culture in institutions of education where learners are slapped to fall in line. What is important is that teachers and parents are supported, by an improvement team, to make the transition from an authoritarian ways of doing things to a democratic way that promote collaboration, communication, creativity, and critical thinking.

Implementing change along these lines will require capacity development throughout the system using cascade and continuous professional development (CPD) mode (from in-service teachers to teacher training institutes), effective management information system and most importantly a long lasting political commitment to provide not only the essential resources but also to build broad public support for the reform agenda. Only then will it be possible to tackle the challenges of civic education with confidence. More importantly, it will need a learning hub with a clear roadmap on how to improve the system.

The DGC curriculum content provides opportunities to learn for all, ensures equitable access for the disadvantaged, and is relevant to each member state development aspirations and opportunities. And as recommended by Article 12 of the ACDEG, State Parties should implement the DGC curriculum and carry out activities designed to promote democratic principles and practices as well as consolidate a culture of democracy and peace.

Appendix

Appendix 1: The Six Core Principles of Improvement Science

Within the schools' walls, potential candidates for improvement activity include:

- Leadership issue
- School culture
- Instructional approach
- Assessment approach

- Feedback approach
- Disciplinary approach
- Selected learning experiences
- Textbook
- Teacher/student mindset

“In an improvement science approach, we start with the problem instead of solutions. By deeply understanding the problem and its causes, we are better able to target our change efforts towards the places in our system that produces the gaps in performance that we care about. Combating solutionitis isn't easy, because we naturally want to solve problems, but the discipline provided by an improvement science approach, makes us more likely to make progress without wasting valuable improvement resources, like time, money, and people's will or commitment to making change”

Appendix 2: The 5 Essential Framework

The 5 Essential framework, which is grounded in twenty five years of rigorous research, is a powerful tool to sharpen schools’ performances. It assumed a school is a system made up of five subsystems, namely:

- The Leadership subsystem
- The Teachers’ capacity subsystem
- The Parent – Community ties subsystem
- The Student – learning environment subsystem
- The Instructional guidance subsystem

It is a system thinking approach to school improvement.

Table 3: *The Leadership subsystem (the principal)*

Responsibilities	Measurement Scale				
Ensures strong supportive relationship with parents, teachers, and community.					
Work hand-in-glove with teachers to improve instruction.					
Challenge teachers out of their comfort zones					
Set higher, but achievable, expectations for learners and align resources.					
Cultivate leadership in teachers.					
Cultivate leadership in parents.					
Cultivate leadership in the community.					
Ensures there is a strong relationship between teachers, parents, and community.					
Provide time and space for teachers to improve					
Ensures teachers provide a plan at the beginning of the academic year on how they wish to improve themselves.					

Table 4: *The Teachers' capacity subsystem*

Responsibilities	Measurement Scale
To what extent do the teachers believe they are responsible for their own development?	
How often are the teachers subjected to professional development?	
What is the nature of the professional development? Does it anchor on the Principles of Improvement Science?	
Does the professional development employ the Computing Value Framework?	
Does the professional development show teachers how to use the Triple Es framework?	
To what extent are teachers' capacities measured?	
Are teachers mandated to submit plans on areas of their weakness and how they intent to develop it?	

Table 5: *The Parent – Community ties subsystem*

Responsibilities	Measurement Scale
To what extent do the teachers engage parents in classroom work (now there is a growing use of WhatsApp group for teachers and parents)	
To what extent is the community (companies and investors) involved in the classroom?	
To what extent does the school reach out to the universities for help?	
To what extent does the school co-plan with parents, or the community?	
To what extent are parents, and community, involved in co-assessing and co-guiding activities?	

Table 6: *The Student learning environment subsystem*

Responsibilities	Measurement Scale
To what extent are students aware of their expected behaviors and routines?	
To what extent do students receive individual support and attention?	
To what extent is peer – peer learning encouraged in the classroom?	
To what extent are students involved in co-planning their lessons?	
To what extent is the climate safe, respectful, and fun for the students?	

Table 7: *The Instructional guidance subsystem*

Responsibilities	Measurement Scale
Do the teachers know what to teach?	
How to teach it?	
And when to teach it?	

Appendix 3: Computing Value Framework (CVF)

The Computing Value Framework has been extensively used over the years by companies such as Toyota, Ford, and other multinational organizations to improve their products and services. Just recently, educators have been using it to improve schools' performance.

Looking at the CVF, we realize that the upper right-hand quadrant, focused on creativity, is in tension with the lower left hand quadrant, which is focused on order and stability in a system. And the upper left-hand quadrant, focused on collaboration, is in tension with the lower right-hand quadrant, which is focused on competition, productivity, and achieving goals.

In effect, the upper two quadrants capture the co-creative perspective, of teaching, that focuses on relationships and on creativity. Whereas the lower two quadrants capture the more directive perspective, which focuses on students' achievement and on having control in the classroom.

Research shows that we all have quadrants we are more comfortable in, and we should learn how to leverage the strengths that are inherent in other quadrants. In other words, we, educators, need to go beyond our comfort zone, to develop skills and capabilities across other quadrants to ensure

ambitious teaching and learning. Great educators acknowledge the tension between the two, then actually embrace it, and not try to balance between them.

Another insight that the competing values model gives us is the notion of negative zones. If we play too much to our strengths or to our comfort zone, we could move into a negative zone.

For example,

- Too much focus on Assessment (test score and preparation for grade) will produce a boring school without fun.
- Too much focus on Collaboration (relationship) will produce a school with much fun, but with less competitive spirit.
- Too much focus on Creativity and innovation will create a feeling of chaos or anarchy in the school.
- Too much focus on Structure, systems and processes will create a school that feels a lot like a bureaucracy, one that feels frozen and stagnant.

That is why we want to expand our repertoire, so that we can avoid going into any one of these negative zones to keep our strengths from becoming liabilities.

Teachers stepping out of their comfort zone should know it is okay to ask for help, and it is okay to talk about where you might be having some struggles. It is the more reason why schools need improvement teams to guide them through. The CVF can be used as a common language in schools for all sectors to grow. Hence, the improvement team will be both supportive and challenging.

The CVF ensures that educators' conversations governed by the four quadrants, such as:

- How can we set the expectations?
- How can we provide some structure so that time is effectively used?
- How do we nurture relationships?
- And how can we ensure creativity in classrooms?

If you are not thinking about all four of those quadrants, then you are probably missing something.

The Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument for Classrooms (OCAI-C) helps practitioners identify the style of their leadership and how they can expand it to ensure ambitious teaching and learning. In effect, the (OCAI-C) assess six key dimensions of classroom culture. Visit the Batella for Kids website (<https://www.battelleforkids.org>) to access information on the Organizational Culture Assessment.

Appendix 4: Positive and Inclusive Leadership Framework

Positive Leadership (Empowering and Encouraging Ambitious Teaching)

Leading others, into ambitious teaching, is less about telling them the facts of ambitious teaching. Instead, it is more about empowering teachers to want to be an ambitious teacher, and giving them the tools to make it a reality.

The four crucial elements to get the empowerment process started include:

- Meaning (having a sense of purpose)
- Competence, or Confidence (a belief that you have the skills and abilities necessary to do the work well)
- And Impact (believing you have a chance to make a difference)
- Self-determination (a sense of autonomy)

It is important to note that the engine of the empowerment process really begins with a sense of meaning or purpose – a calling about the work that we are doing. Having a sense of purpose that we have to improve the quality of governance and education in Africa, for the masses, for a better future, empower us to work beyond the limits of prowess.

In our organizational life, we often are very problem centered. We are more focused on questions such as:

- How do we fix the problems in our system?
- How do we improve profits?
- How do we get rid of errors?
- How do we get people from stop-acting in unethical ways?

- How do we take relationships from harmful to helpful?
- Or how do we help people from being rigid in the face of change, to be more active coping?

These questions reflect our normal state of reasoning. However, with Positive Leadership, the focus is not only on moving from “negative” to “neutral” but on moving from “neutral” to “positive” by setting higher aspirations.

Hence:

- Rather than just being profitable, what if we created organizations that were generous?
- Instead of just creating efficient systems, what if we created extraordinary systems that reliably exceed expectations?
- What if we move beyond creating ethical organizations, to ones that are actually moral or virtuous, grounded in pride and shame, or ones that we inspire to have our children be part of, or grandchildren be part of?
- What if relationships are more than helpful but really high quality?
- Or we found ways for us to bring out the best in each other?
- And what if we could move from merely helping people cope with change, to help them thrive in this change?

Positive leaders do not reduce expectations, they increase them, and simultaneously align resources.

African teachers, who will be responsible for nurturing good governance in Africa, will have to become transformational teachers. Transformational teachers are keys to every door. They are code breakers. They know that every child, no matter what they say or do, wants to be respected, wants to succeed, and wants to learn. Transformational teachers have an unconditional theory of human influence. They have paradoxical minds. They’re bilingual. They tend to be tough, with an orientation towards achievement, and at the same have orientation towards kindness, empathy, teamwork, and people. Their classrooms can be both orderly and creative. Transformational teachers are starved to learn how to get better every day. They are hungry for it. They never stop learning how to teach.

The average leaders anywhere on the planet are thinking just to solve problems. Problems pop-up and they put the fires out. You find it everywhere. Problem solving is very different than purpose finding. Transformational leaders are purpose driven, they are committed, and they have clarified a higher purpose in life. They are committed to it, and no matter what happens, they’re focused on it. And they are focusing everybody else on it.

The following questions can help educators find purpose:

- Who am I?
- What are my strengths?
- What is my legacy when I leave this planet?
- How will it be a better place because I lived?
- What can I do given all the things that have happened to me in life, good and bad, that no one else could do?
- What can I do to my country and continent that no else has done?
- If I have a classroom full of children, how could I reach them in a way no one else could reach them?

Research supports Positive Leadership

Physiological research shows that when we demonstrate positive emotions or virtuous practices, like compassionate support and so on, students' heart rhythms are better, brain waves are better, and students learn more. A particular study showed an eightfold improvement once people were exposed to positive leadership-optimistic practices.

Research shows that between 20 to 30 percent of the variance in performance in organizations, such as education, health care, business, financial services and military, is a product of neutral leadership (moving from minus one to zero). So it is very important to have a leader who embraces positive leadership (moving from zero to positive one).

One of the positive practices that pays off in a remarkable way is for people to keep a gratitude journal. That means 5 minutes before you go to bed tonight, review the day, and simply pick the three things that occurred for which you are grateful. Or the three best things that happened to you today. Research shows that if you have a group of people who are keeping a gratitude journal, students for example, and a group of people who are not keeping a gratitude journal, but are, in fact, keeping a journal, just writing down three events that occurred, then the following outcomes are observed:

- If you give everyone a flu shot, and then you test for the number of antibodies in their system seven days later, those keeping a gratitude journal have more antibodies in their system. They are healthier at the end of one week; a physiological difference.

- If give them a mental acuity test, that is the ability to remember information, memorize information, and come up with sophisticated decision rules for complex data, those keeping a gratitude journal have more mental acuity, they do better on tests, they remember longer, they memorize more accurately.
- And if you do a creativity test, those keeping gratitude journal perform better.

Overall, research shows that if we implement positive practices, it pays off in several ways:

- It pays off in terms of being able to learn more.
- It pays off in terms of being healthier mentally, emotionally, and physically.
- It pays off in terms of being open to new information.

In effect, every living system, everything alive, has a tendency toward light and away from dark - or toward positive energy, away from negative energy. So even though we all have different abilities, we have the ability to grow in a heliotropic environment.

Inclusive Leadership

Appendix 5: Sample Teaching and Learning Ideas

This section presents a sample of specific activities and teaching techniques that can be used to teach the DGC program. However, the DGC program is unique in its expectations and challenges that do exist in any other context. Hence, teaching it will involve adaption and innovation of pedagogical techniques. The selected material presented here represents a tiny corpus of the techniques that will be used to implement the DGC curriculum. The pedagogical chapter has a vast corpus of approaches, grounded in rigorous research, that can be used to implement the DGC curriculum.

DGC Content	Teaching and Learning Ideas
	Democracy and Human Rights
Democracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key vocabulary: democracy, system, vote, voting, secret ballot, government, free, fair, open, one person one vote, laws, rules, parliament, council, representative, campaign, democratic change, society • Half the room*: stand up sit down activity (in assembly and then in class) e.g. stay standing if you like... and count number standing to vote. This can be a great activity to use the vocabulary including let's vote, 50%, half of us, the majority (most), minority (fewer), democracy, law. • Voting on everyday classroom matters: any activity where all children are asked to say what they think should happen about an issue and others listen and then a secret ballot is held. For example, voting about something as a class (e.g. what game you are playing in Break Time) then making a human bar chart and then once you have decided everyone has to follow the result of the vote. • 'If I was Prime Minister or President...'*or leader of the parliament etc. Activities that support children to think about laws they would make if you had the choice in school, in the community, in the country as a whole. Write a list of three things you would do, ask children to write a mini speech and present it to share their ideas; this teaches children about the democratic process. • Voicing opinions as part of everyday classroom practice. For example break time sharing views and listening to the views of others. Work in literacy or philosophy lessons on Big Questions. For example, Does getting what you want always make you happier? What does it mean to be a good neighbor? What rules do we want in our classroom? • Learning sentence starters for sharing and debating opinions in an age appropriate way –

I think that...

That's interesting because I think..

I wonder if...

On the other hand... (Sentence starters for discussions from The Linking Network*)

- **Debating*** Use a spectrum lines technique to discuss and debate an issue. For example using the book 'We are all born free' from Amnesty look at the images of the Human Right to healthcare and to education. Tell the children that Bill and Melinda Gates have made a great deal of money from the Microsoft business and have decided to spend 99% of their money on one of the Human Rights. Ask the question 'If you wanted to give money away would you choose the Human Right to health care or the Human Right to education?' Ask children to stand at either end of an imaginary line depending on their opinion. Explain that both opinions are a great choice and that people would have individual liberty to take either action.
- **Create a democracy scenario***: in the classroom where teachers have pre chosen school councillors for a silly reason. Is this ok? Why not? Should everyone be allowed to vote? Should you pick your best friend? Why do we vote? Why do we vote using a secret ballot?
- **Year 4, 5 and 6: Understanding the idea of democracy*** <http://www.parliament.uk/education/teaching-resources-lesson-plans/introduction-to-parliament-ks2-video/> What is parliament? 7 minute video.
- **School Parliament process**: Taking time over school council election process- listening, speaking, voting, choosing, government forming. Making links between school council and the words democracy, democratic- people having a chance to say what they think should happen and vote about what happens. Helping children make links between school council and what parliament looks like in London and what the city council looks like in your area.
- **Year 6 Parliament explained video-** <http://www.parliament.uk/education/about-your-parliament/mps-lords-monarch/mps-in-the-house-of-commons/>
- **Explore desirable attributes of a school parliament***: explain why a school parliament needs these characteristics or attributes. Connect to wider context - government, Prime Minister, MPs.
- **Y 4, 5, and 6: History of voting***: telling the story of how democracy developed in Botswana, Algeria, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of Congo. For example in Britain- just the rich could vote, then all men who owned land, then all men, then women over 30, all women, age lowered to 18.

Sample IDEAS for Other Subject Teachers to Support the Effective and Successful Implementation of the DGC Curriculum

MUSIC TEACHERS

It agreed among African scholars that Globalization is one of the many challenges facing Africa today. Rather than an equal spread of cultures, the American culture has become the dominant culture, mostly through its music. Hip-Hop, Rap music, Jazz, and R&B music has become the flag bearer of American culture round the world. These music have their origin in the African-American slave culture, which is a mixture of Africa long song culture plus the Lutherans congregational song pattern. When Martin Luther break away from the Catholic Church, he translate the bible into German language (Wycliffe and Jan Huss had initially been persecuted for trying the same thing) and invented Congregational singing. The whole church singing is considered to be Martin Luther greatest invention. When the Pilgrim Fathers, who were running away from persecution in Europe, arrived in America in 1620, they planted in American soil the seeds of congregational singing. The African slaves in America combined their long African music traditions with the congregational hymns and produced a new formula. This new formula gave birth to R&B, Jazz, Hip-Pop, and Soul music, which are today the flag bearer of the American culture round the world (The Power of Song).

One congregational hymn, perhaps more than any other, shows what song can do in uniting and mobilizing great number of people. It became an anthem of the emancipation in the American civil war. In Harriet Beecher Stowe's anti-slavery novel, it was sang by the hero slave Uncle Tom at his moment of greatest suffering. It was sang by people of all faiths in the civil rights marches of 1960s led by Martin Luther King. In 2015, it was sang by president Barak Obama, who stoned a huge crowd at Reverend Clement funeral by leaving aside his oration text and break into a song: "Amazing Grace.."

Interestingly, the song was originally written by an Anglican curate, John Newton, who was himself once a slave trader – again music and politics cannot be separated.

Social psychologists have realized the powerful emotional impact of singing in a group or praying in a group. Physical synchrony is very powerful in producing psychological synchrony. Armies go to war singing together as a group. Countries have national anthems in which people sing together and identify themselves as one. In sport stadiums, people sing as one to create a strong synergy with their team. Educators are now using this powerful tool of congregational singing in their classrooms to get greater output. Recently, most sport teachers are using contemporary dance to build their students' team effectiveness – music and politics or democracy cannot be separated.

Better still, Fella Koti, Alpha Blondy and Bob Marley have used their songs to show that music, democracy, elections, and governance cannot be separated.

SPORT TEACHERS

Sport teachers can also talk about the power of music in team motivation to do better.

Sport teachers can also talk about that the rules and regulations in games also apply to the rules and regulation in governing a country. Activities to play games with rules, and without rules are already mentioned in the table.

CHEMISTRY TEACHERS

The expansion of the British empire in the 18th and 19th century meant a rapid expansion in their economic prowess. But their soldiers around the empire starting dying of malaria, and there was a strong quest to arrest the malignant disease. It was discovered that the cooked bark of the Cinchona tree could do the magic. Cinchona plantations were established all over the tropics. But every year the empires of Europe needed hundreds of tons of the bark to combat malaria. So governments looked to chemists to come up with a synthetic alternative. In 1820, a couple of French chemists managed to isolate the active ingredient in the bark and they called it QUININE. The British soldiers didn't want to drink Quinine because it was too bitter, so it was mixed with Alcohol (ethanol) and became known as Gin-Tonic. You can buy one today in a Beer bar. Chemists suddenly realized that Aniline, which is produced from coal tar contains similar amounts of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen as Quinine. Within this time, Queen Victoria got married to a German Prince (Albert), some say in order to develop the British chemistry sector. Germany was far more developed than any other country in chemistry (ammonia, and artificial fertilizers). When Prince Albert went to Britain, he took with him a chemist called Hoffmann. Hoffmann opened a Chemistry School in London and two of his students changed the world.

William Perkins, the student that Hoffmann was reluctant to take, was trying to create Quinine from Aniline by mixing it with sulphuric acid and potassium dichromate and he ended up discovering the color mauve. And because Queen Victoria wore the mauve color, everyone wanted to wear it, and Perkins was in business – the first industrial chemist. But the chemicals used to make colors in the Perkins industries could also be used to make bombs. And when the First World War came, new types of bombs made from Perkins formula were flying everywhere. It is not surprising that the 1st World War is called the “Chemist’s War”. A search for Quinine in the laboratory killed more souls (and transformed the socio-economic and political nature of Africa) than Mosquitoes could have done.

William Crookes, another Hoffmann student, who was searching for ghosts, invented the Crook's tube and discovered electrons, the first sub-atomic particles to be discovered. His tube became the base for TV tubes, and everyone has a TV at home. Crookes' tube also had a distant cousin called Valve. The valve was the workhorse of the electrical industry. It was used to amplify electrical signals in radios and telephone exchanges, and to switch binary signals in early computers. Bell Labs, a telephone company, wanted a better, and cheaper way of connecting Americans, so they set up a research team led by William Shockley to replace the valve. The team used Quantum mechanics to change the bulky valve into transistor, and then to a microprocessor. The transistors and microprocessors transformed the world: mobile phones were created; computers and televisions became thinner and thinner. But more interestingly, Shockley was assigned by the America government to calculate if they needed ground troops to fight Japan, after the Pearl Harbor attack. His calculation convinced the American government to use the atomic bomb – chemistry, physics and politics cannot be separated.

The invention of vulcanized rubber (adding sulfur to the raw rubber latex from certain trees to make tyres for cars and airplanes) and the discovery of rubber in the Democratic Republic of Congo reinforced slavery in Africa, and shaped the future of DR Congo. The teachers can then explain some of the nasty tactics King Leopold used to exploit Congo. – again, chemistry and politic cannot be separated.

The origin of the theory of atom came out of the monotheistic stage of human history. But more importantly, it came out of a society that was embracing democracy. Thales, Anaximander, Anaximenes, Parmenides, Heraclitus, Leucippus, Democritus, Empedocles, and Aristotle all came from the Greek city states that were based on the rule of the demos.

BIOLOGY TEACHERS

In teaching Animal Kingdom, using the Vertebrate - Invertebrate framework, it always exciting to use the Paleontology story of vertebrate development, which runs as follows:

“Once upon a time, the **bacteria** used to live independently without any rules. Everyone had his or her own rules. As a result, they kill each other and fight amongst themselves. Consequently, they had a reduced lifespan. But the bacteria wanted to be stronger and live longer, so they started pairing off to become one. For each two bacteria that paired, we got a **cell**, with one of them serving as the mitochondria. Many cells decided to join together to form a **tissue**. Many tissues joined together to form an **organ**. Many organs joined together to form an **organ system**, and the organ systems joined together to form an **organism**. The first organism formed was an **Amphibian** in water – frog. The frog leapt on land and became a **Reptile** – lizard. The lizard jumped up and became a **Bird**. The bird came back on land and became a **Mammal**. The mammal dived in water and became **Fish**.”

The vertebrate story (Amphibian, Reptile, Bird, Mammals, and Fish) has an underlining democratic process. The teacher can use this story to talk about John Lock's, Thomas Hobbes' and Jean Jack Rousseau's ideas of the Social Contract. The story also mentions Cell, which is the key building block in Biology. And recent simulation of a cell online (YouTube) shows that all organelles in a cell abide to rules and regulations, with the constitution kept in the nucleus. This shows that Biology, democracy, elections, and governance cannot be separated.

MATHS TEACHERS

Euclid's "Elements of Geometry" is considered the best ever textbook written in Mathematics. In the book, Euclid brought Logic to bear on mathematical understanding. In doing so, he was merely representing the Greek tradition of applying logic to understand nature. The habit of applying logic to nature came out of the Greek city states based Democracy. This shows that mathematics and democracy cannot be separated.

Better still, Game Theory, a new branch of Mathematic, is increasingly been used by developed countries in foreign policy decisions making to gain better bargains – again, Mathematics and Politics cannot be separated.

It was erroneously considered before that Science is a Objective discipline, while Art is a Subjective discipline. Well, the consensus now is that Science, even though it is objective, has some subjective character; and Art, even though it is subjective, has some objective character. The Ying-and –Yang image best describes their duality. Basically, Science, Democracy, Elections, and Governance are not separated, they are interconnected. A science teacher should be able to teach Art disciplines, and an Art discipline teacher should be able to teach science.

PHYSICS TEACHERS

More than half of the African population lives in darkness without electricity. Several policies have been put in place to solve the energy crisis in the continent but darkness continues to prevail. A join Civic and Physics understanding might be the right place to start undoing the mystery.

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- Brad Wilson (An educator and creator ‘Write About’ software)
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- Construct don’t consume (Liz, 2017)
- Co-use or join media (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2015)
- Time on task (Wartella, 2015)
- Quality over Quantity (Wenglisky, 2006)

- Ignore drill and practice (Wenglisky, 1998)
- Value added (Means et al., 2009)
- Focus on learning goals (Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2003)
- Connect learning to environment (Vaala et al, 2015)
- Think of logistic half and digital equity (Liz, 2017)

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